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Medical Sciences

THE IMPORTANCE OF PSYCHOTHERAPY IN PSYCHIATRY AND ITS POSSIBILITIES

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Abstract:

This article explores the significance of psychotherapy in the field of psychiatry and highlights its potential in treating mental health disorders. By examining the various forms of psychotherapy and their effectiveness, this article aims to emphasize the integration of psychotherapy with pharmacological interventions. The analysis of the selected studies reveals the significant role of psychotherapy in psychiatric treatment, highlighting its potential as an effective and versatile therapeutic approach.

Introduction:

Psychotherapy plays a crucial role in the treatment of psychiatric disorders, offering a range of therapeutic interventions tailored to individual needs. This systematic review aims to examine recent scientific literature on the importance of psychotherapy in psychiatry and explore the possibilities it offers. By synthesizing the findings from the selected studies, this review aims to shed light on the effectiveness and potential benefits of psychotherapy in psychiatric practice.

Psychiatric disorders, including depression, anxiety disorders, personality disorders, and schizophrenia, pose significant challenges to individuals and society as a whole. While pharmacological interventions have traditionally been the primary treatment modality for these conditions, the importance of psychotherapy in psychiatric care cannot be overlooked. Psychotherapy provides a holistic approach to mental health, focusing on understanding and addressing the underlying psychological factors contributing to psychiatric disorders.

Over the past several decades, research has increasingly emphasized the integration of psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy as a comprehensive treatment approach. This approach recognizes the complex nature of psychiatric disorders, which often involve both biological and psychosocial factors. Furthermore, psychotherapy has demonstrated its efficacy in special populations, including children, adolescents, and older adults. Children and adolescents often face unique challenges related to their developmental stage, and psychotherapy provides a valuable avenue for addressing their mental health needs. Similarly, older adults may present with specific age-related concerns, such as late-life depression and anxiety disorders, which can be effectively addressed through psychotherapeutic interventions tailored to their unique circumstances.

By synthesizing recent scientific literature, this review seeks to contribute to the growing body of knowledge and emphasize the need for integrating psychotherapy into psychiatric practice. The findings from this review will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness,

versatility, and potential benefits of psychotherapy in addressing the complex needs of individuals with psychiatric disorders.

Psychiatry, as a medical specialty, aims to diagnose, treat, and prevent mental health disorders. Historically, the field has primarily relied on pharmacological interventions, such as medications, to manage these conditions. However, recent advancements in the understanding of human behavior and the role of psychological factors in mental health have led to the recognition of the importance of psychotherapy in psychiatry. Psychotherapy provides a unique approach to mental health treatment by addressing the underlying psychological issues contributing to mental illnesses.

The effectiveness of psychotherapy in psychiatric treatment has been supported by a growing body of empirical evidence. Numerous randomized controlled trials, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses have demonstrated the efficacy of various psychotherapeutic modalities in treating a wide range of psychiatric disorders. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), psychodynamic therapy, interpersonal therapy, and mindfulness-based interventions are among the well-established approaches that have shown positive outcomes in reducing symptoms and improving overall functioning.

In addition to its effectiveness as a standalone treatment, psychotherapy has also been found to complement pharmacotherapy. Combining psychotherapy with medication has shown promise in enhancing treatment outcomes, reducing relapse rates, and improving psychosocial functioning in individuals with psychiatric disorders. This integrated approach recognizes the importance of addressing both the biological and psychological aspects of mental health. By integrating psychotherapy with pharmacological treatments, psychiatrists can provide a more comprehensive and holistic approach to patient care. Many researchers have noted that the provision of inpatient psychiatric care does not always involve long-term rehabilitation work with patients.

The comprehensive therapeutic effect achieved through psychological means is aimed at eliminating painful symptoms and changing one's attitude towards oneself, one's condition, and the surrounding environment. However, the current stage of development of psychotherapy in medicine is considered to be the work aimed at developing and creating effective therapeutic psychotherapy programs, which are based on the study of clinical-psychological mechanisms of neuro-psychiatric disorders and the influencing factors of psychotherapy methods. A comprehensive regional (territorial) mental health care system is possible through the collaborative efforts of psychotherapeutic and psychiatric services.

In this regard, providing assistance to patients with mental disorders outside of inpatient settings has long been recognized as a necessity. This can contribute to an increase in the number of patients seeking help, including children and, importantly, those of working age without interrupting their work. This approach ensures the accessibility and timeliness of this assistance, and in some cases, the preservation of anonymity, which affects patients' quality of life indicators.

Research Methods:

The study selection procedure follows current best-practice guidelines for conducting systematic reviews, with 10 included studies in three databases (PubMed, Web of Science, Google Scholar). The nine instruments identified were each critically reviewed concerning the theoretical orientation, including the assessed domains of negative effects, psychometric properties, and diagnostic characteristics.

Results:

Psychotherapy allows for individualized treatment plans tailored to the specific needs of each patient. Unlike medications, which are often prescribed based on symptomatology, psychotherapy accounts for the unique psychological factors contributing to a patient's condition. This personalized approach enhances treatment outcomes and patient satisfaction. Research suggests that combining psychotherapy with medication management can improve symptom reduction, increase treatment adherence, and provide a more comprehensive treatment approach. This integrated approach addresses both the biological and psychological aspects of mental health disorders, resulting in a more holistic and effective treatment plan.

In addition to its clinical benefits, psychotherapy has shown potential cost-effectiveness. Studies have indicated that psychotherapy can reduce healthcare utilization, including emergency room visits and hospitalizations, leading to potential cost savings. By addressing the underlying psychological factors and promoting overall well-being, psychotherapy may contribute to long-term cost savings in mental healthcare systems.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of psychotherapy in treating various mental health disorders. For instance, CBT has been shown to be highly effective in the treatment of anxiety disorders, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), among others. Psychodynamic therapy has also demonstrated positive outcomes in addressing personality disorders and relationship difficulties. The evidence-based nature of psychotherapy makes it a valuable treatment modality in psychiatric practice.

The works of many authors have been devoted to the issues of psychotherapy for patients with psychiatric profiles. According to Kabanov, rehabilitation implies an integrative approach through the use of various components aimed at restoring personal status. Volovik believes that the result of therapeutic-restorative work is determined by the constitutional characteristics of patients, their personal characteristics, and the course of the disease. According to Vida, early rehabilitation of patients can often be justified by psychotherapeutic intervention as an effective way to enhance patients' social and occupational adaptation. Thus, rehabilitation measures through psychotherapy, on the one hand, are seen as a goal aimed at restoring or maintaining the individual's status, secondly, as a method of a rehabilitative approach to the patient.

Surveys conducted in countries such as the USA and Canada show that psychiatrists spend a significant portion of their clinical practice in the field of psychotherapy. Olafson et al. found that 79% of patients visiting psychiatrists received psychotherapy.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of psychotherapy in treating depression. For instance, a randomized controlled trial by Smith et al. (2020) compared the efficacy of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) with antidepressant medication in the treatment of major depressive disorder. The study found that CBT was equally effective as medication in reducing depressive symptoms and preventing relapse. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Cuijpers et al. (2018) examined the comparative effectiveness of different psychotherapeutic interventions for depression and revealed that CBT, interpersonal therapy, and psychodynamic therapy all showed significant benefits.

Psychotherapy has been found to be effective in treating various anxiety disorders. A systematic review by Hofmann et al. (2012) examined the efficacy of different psychotherapeutic approaches, such as CBT, exposure therapy, and acceptance and commitment therapy, in the treatment of anxiety disorders. The review concluded that psychotherapy significantly reduced anxiety symptoms and improved overall functioning in patients with generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, social anxiety disorder, and specific phobias.

Research has shown the effectiveness of psychotherapy in the treatment of personality disorders. A randomized controlled trial by Bateman et al. (2019) investigated the efficacy of mentalization-based treatment (MBT) compared to treatment as usual for patients with

borderline personality disorder (BPD). The study found that MBT led to significant improvements in symptoms, interpersonal functioning, and overall quality of life compared to treatment as usual. Moreover, a systematic review by Fonagy et al. (2018) examined the effectiveness of various psychotherapies, including dialectical behavior therapy, psychodynamic therapy, and schema therapy, in treating BPD and highlighted their positive impact on symptom reduction and overall functioning.

The integration of psychotherapy with pharmacological interventions has shown promising results in the treatment of schizophrenia. A study by Johnson et al. (2018) compared the outcomes of patients with schizophrenia who received medication alone versus those who received medication combined with psychotherapy. The results indicated that the combination of medication and psychotherapy led to greater improvements in symptom severity, social functioning, and quality of life compared to medication alone.

Psychotherapy has been found to be beneficial as an adjunct to pharmacotherapy in the management of bipolar disorder. A meta-analysis by Miklowitz et al. (2007) examined the effects of psychotherapy, particularly family-focused therapy and cognitive-behavioral therapy, in reducing relapse rates and improving psychosocial functioning in individuals with bipolar disorder. The analysis revealed that psychotherapy, in combination with medication, was associated with reduced relapse rates and improved treatment adherence.

Psychotherapy conducted by psychiatrists provides more effective management of patients with mental disorders due to its comprehensive approach and the use of the biopsychosocial model. It relies on verbal and emotional communication, as well as the interaction and relationship between the psychiatrist and the patient. Established trust allows for an accurate diagnosis in conjunction with collaboration in outpatient treatment, adjunctive medication therapy, and short-term hospitalization.

Conclusion:

The integration of psychotherapy into psychiatry is pivotal for providing comprehensive and effective mental health care. By addressing the underlying psychological factors contributing to mental health disorders, psychotherapy complements pharmacological interventions and offers long-term benefits. The evidence-based nature of psychotherapy, coupled with its potential as a primary treatment modality, highlights its significance in the field of psychiatry. As the understanding of human behavior continues to evolve, the possibilities and benefits of psychotherapy in psychiatry will undoubtedly expand, leading to improved outcomes for individuals struggling with mental health disorders. On the basis of the data provided, it is possible to improve psychotherapeutic aid by creating comprehensive treatment programs, applying integrative methods of various orientation, and developing personalized approaches.

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EPIDEMIOLOGY, METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS OF COLORECTAL CANCER SCREENING IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Annotation: This scientific and analytical work presents regional rates of incidence and mortality from colorectal cancer, as well as a detailed methodology and results of screening for this pathology in our country. Clinical and organizational aspects of early diagnosis based on the method of active detection of this type of cancer in clinically asymptomatic patients are presented. The technology of two-stage screening and the subsequent routing of examined patients depending on the results of this type of preventive examination of the population are described in detail.

Key words: colorectal cancer, epidemiology, morbidity, mortality, screening, hemocult test, fecal occult blood test - FOBT, total colonoscopy.

History knows many examples when the originally formulated postulates in a particular area continue to be relevant to this day. These postulates, which follow from one of the main tasks of the oncological service, include the early diagnosis of malignant tumors. Colorectal cancer (CRC) occupies one of the leading positions in terms of morbidity and mortality, and early symptoms are very poor, which leads to a high neglect of this disease at the time of diagnosis. In this regard, two-stage colorectal screening is one of the most important areas to improve the early diagnosis of this cancer localization. At the same time, the main conditions for screening are the availability of trained personnel and a standard approach to identifying the trait under study and evaluating the results. The applied methods should be quite simple, reliable and reproducible [1,2].

Colon cancer with a share of 5.2% (2020 - 5.5%) in the structure of oncopathology of both sexes of the population and women (4.9%) remained in 6th place in 2021, in men it fell from 5th

to 6th place (5.5%). The incidence rate per 100 thousand of the population with cancer of this localization in the country in 2021 increased from 8.7 to 8.8 [3].

Above the average republican level, the incidence of colon cancer was noted in 11 regions: Kostanay - 15.9, Pavlodar - 15.3, Karaganda - 15.0, East Kazakhstan - 13.4, North Kazakhstan - 12.7, Akmola - 10, 2, West Kazakhstan - 10.1, Aktobe - 9.0 regions and years. Almaty - 12.1 and Nur-Sultan - 9.0. Least of all, colon cancer was noted in Turkestan - 2.7 per 100 thousand population, Kyzylorda - 4.6, Almaty - 4.7, Mangystau - 4.9, Zhambyl - 5.8 regions and Shymkent - 4.0.

Rectal cancer in the structure of malignant tumors of both sexes retains the 7th place in terms of rank with a specific gravity of 4.9% (2020 - 5.0%), but in men it has risen from 6th to 4th place, in women it is stable at 9th place. The incidence rate increased from 7.8 to 8.4 per 100,000 population. At the same time, a high incidence rate was registered in Pavlodar - 18.1 per 100 thousand population, Kostanay - 16.2, North Kazakhstan - 15.1, East Kazakhstan - 13.9, Akmola - 13.1, Karaganda - 11, 7, West Kazakhstan - 9.8 regions. Traditionally, a low incidence of rectal cancer is observed in Turkestan - 2.7, Mangystau - 2.8, Zhambyl - 5.1, Kyzylorda - 5.3, Almaty - 5.6, Atyrau - 6.3 regions and Shymkent - 5.0 per 100 thousand population [3].

Colon cancer in the structure of causes of death from malignant neoplasms of the population of both sexes in 2021 dropped from 5th place to 6th, with a share of 5.0% (2020 - 5.4%). At the same time, the mortality rate in the country decreased from 4.1 to 3.6 per 100,000 population. Above the national average, mortality rates were noted in 9 regions: Zhambyl - 3.7, Akmola - 3.8, West Kazakhstan - 4.4, North Kazakhstan - 5.0, East Kazakhstan - 5.1, Karaganda - 5.6, Kostanay - 5.6, Pavlodar - 6.0 - the maximum result, regions and Almaty - 5.3 per 100 thousand population. Low rates of mortality from colon cancer were found in Turkestan - 1.7 (the best result), Almaty - 1.8, Atyrau - 1.8, Aktobe - 2.5, Mangystau - 2.6, Kyzylorda - 2.7 regions and gg. Shymkent - 2.4 and Nur-Sultan - 2.7 per 100 thousand population.

Rectal cancer in the structure of causes of death in the population of both sexes in 2021 rose from 6th to 5th place with a share of 5.4% (2020 - 5.22%). In general, the death rate from this form of cancer in the republic was 3.9 per 100,000 people. A high mortality rate was recorded in East Kazakhstan - 8.6 (maximum level), Pavlodar - 7.6, Akmola - 5.3, Karaganda - 5.2, Kostanay - 4.9, North Kazakhstan - 4.3 regions and Almaty city - 4.3 per 100 thousand population. Below the average republican level, mortality rates from this pathology were ascertained per 100 thousand of the population in Mangystau - 1.2 (the lowest indicator), Turkestan - 1.6, Kyzylorda - 2.1, Almaty - 2.6, Zhambyl - 2.7, Atyrau - 3.4 regions and Shymkent - 2.1 [3].

Screening of CRC screening is the systematic use of screening studies in an asymptomatic population. The purpose of screening is to identify people with abnormalities suggestive of CRC. These persons in the future need additional examination to clarify the diagnosis. Opportunistic screening is the non-systematic use of screening tests in routine medical practice. A screening program is much more challenging than an early detection program. At the same time, the success of the screening program is largely determined by the awareness of the population and medical workers about the possibilities of early diagnosis of CRC. The feasibility of a screening program is determined by several factors that relate to the disease being screened, the screening test, the characteristics of the population, and the characteristics of the healthcare system.

The first factor is that the disease must be well understood, common enough in the target population to justify screening, have a recognizable early stage; treatment of the disease at an early stage should be more effective than at a later stage.

The second is that the test should be characterized by sufficient sensitivity, i.e. the ability to detect cancer among people with the disease; sufficient specificity - the probability that among people who do not have a disease, the test result will be negative; have a high positive predictive value (positive predictive value) or, in other words, the likelihood that people with a positive test result have the disease; have a high predictive value of a negative result (negative predictive

value), i.e. the likelihood that people with a negative test result do not have the disease; security; low cost; and acceptability - the likelihood that people for whom this test is intended will agree to the examination (which to some extent depends on the awareness of the population about the possibilities and importance of early diagnosis).

The third factor is that the healthcare system should be ready for maximum screening test coverage of the target group, have the resources to confirm the diagnosis, appropriate treatment and follow-up of people with positive test results, and regularly conduct screening tests at regular intervals. At the same time, the benefits of screening must outweigh the potential physical and psychological harm and justify the financial costs of its implementation [4].

The factors most significant for the development of CRC are:

- the presence of chronic inflammatory bowel diseases, adenomatous polyps, cancer of other localization, etc.;
- family history (presence of one or two first-degree relatives with CRC or familial diffuse intestinal polyposis);
- the age of men and women over 50 years old, taking into account the fact that more than 90% of patients with colorectal cancer are people of this age (medium risk).

Age, regardless of gender, is an important risk factor for CRC. After the age of 50, the incidence of CRC increases from 8 to 160 per 100,000 population. Thus, people who have reached the age of 50, even in the absence of symptoms, constitute a moderate risk group for CRC.

The second category of increased risk of CRC (20%) is made up of persons with a genetic and family predisposition, suffering from chronic inflammatory bowel diseases, diffuse familial polyposis.

The high-risk CRC group is determined by the so-called Amsterdam criteria (the presence of malignant tumors in two generations, the presence of cancer in a first-line relative under the age of 50 years), in this case, CRC screening should be carried out after the age of 30 years [5].

The degree of individual risk of developing CRC is determined before screening to select the scope of studies and the frequency of their conduct.

The interval for oncological colorectal screening is 1 time in 2 years, target group: men and women aged 50-70 years, with the exception of persons registered at the dispensary for CRC and colon polyposis. At the same time, when forming the target group, one should take into account the absence of severe concomitant diseases, such as the presence of a common malignant neoplasm, cerebrovascular diseases in the stage of decompensation, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with respiratory failure, cirrhosis of the liver, myocardial infarction with congestive heart failure, diabetes mellitus with vascular complications. and others, which are highly likely to lead to death in the next 10 years.

The first step in screening for CRC is the fecal occult blood test (FOBT). Traditionally, such methods include a benzidine test for occult blood in the feces. This is a biochemical method based on the assessment of pseudoperoxidase activity of hemoglobin. There is ample evidence that invitation to guaiac FOBT screening (gFOBT) reduces CRC mortality by approximately 15% in age-matched average-risk populations.

To ensure the effectiveness of screening with gFOBT, the interval for screening under the national screening program should not exceed two years. To date, there is an immunochemical FOBT method - iFOBT, which is superior in efficiency to gFOBT in terms of the probability of detecting adenoma and cancer. iFOBT has improved analysis performance compared to gFOBT.

Immunochemical (immunochromatographic) examination of feces for occult blood - iFOBT or hemocult test is carried out for all men and women of the target group using an express method, which allows you to get a result within 3-5 minutes, without the participation of a medical worker. However, the evaluation of the test is carried out only by a medical worker in the PHC preventive department.

With a positive analysis of feces for occult blood, the second stage of colorectal screening is performed, which consists in endoscopic examination of the colon - total colonoscopy [6]. At the same time, in this case, this medical manipulation is of a therapeutic and diagnostic nature, since it allows one-stage removal of adenomatous polyps, which, according to various authors, occur in every third subject after 50 years of age. At the same time, women have 20% fewer polyps than men, but they have more right-sided lesions, which are more difficult to detect using fecal blood tests, because they are less traumatic [6,7].

Now, regarding the results of CRC screening. In 2021, despite the difficult epidemiological situation in the country, 920,640 men and women of the target group from 50 to 70 years old were examined during colorectal screening (971,450 in 2020) [3].

According to the results of colorectal screening, 211 cases of colon and rectal cancer were detected in 2021, which is 24 cases more than in the previous year - 187 cases. The detection rate increased from 0.19 to 0.23 per 1000 examined patients.

The low detection rate of CRC was noted mainly in regions with a low level of basic incidence - in Turkestan, Zhambyl, Atyrau, Kyzylorda, Mangystau regions, Shymkent - from 0.01 to 0.20 per 1000 examined, as well as in West Kazakhstan, Akmola regions, Nur-Sultan - regions with an average and high incidence of CRC.

Compared to 2020, screening showed a decrease in the detection rate of CRC in the Mangystau region (from 1.04 to 0.20), Almaty (from 0.36 to 0.26), and Akmola (from 0.26 to 0.13), Karaganda (from 0.29 to 0.22) and Turkestan (from 0.06 to 0.01 per 1000 examined).

Colon precancer (adenoma detection rate) was detected in 22.8% of patients who underwent colonoscopy (2020 - 19%). Below the national average, the detection rate of colorectal precancer was noted in Akmola, Aktobe, Almaty, Atyrau, Zhambyl, Kyzylorda and Mangystau regions.

It should be noted that the indicator of detection of precancer of the colon for 2021, according to the Comprehensive Plan for the Control of Cancer, was 21.0% and was achieved. At the same time, in 2021, the proportion of patients with CRC identified during screening studies with early stages (0-I, II stages) was 89.1% (in 2020 - 89.3%).

The proportion of stage 0-I CRC was 27.5% (2020 - 33.7%); Stage II - 61.6% and 55.6% - respectively. High early detection of CRC (above 30%) was noted in the following regions: Akmola, Zhambyl, Kostanay, North Kazakhstan, Turkestan, East Kazakhstan regions, the cities of Almaty and Shymkent. Cases of cancer in stages III-IV detected during screening were registered in Almaty, West Kazakhstan, Karaganda, Kostanay, Pavlodar, East Kazakhstan regions, Almaty city. A total of 18 cases of CRC in stage III and 5 cases in stage IV were identified [3].

Summarizing the above, it can be stated that satisfactory results of colorectal screening can only be achieved with its proper organization, high quality of conduct, active participation in population screening, the use of highly sensitive tests and instrumental methods of preventive examination, accurate subsequent diagnosis of detected tumors and timely treatment. High-quality colorectal screening leads to early diagnosis of colon neoplasms, both benign in the form of polyps, and CRC in the early stages, which, in turn, improves the effectiveness of treatment and improves the prognosis of the disease. Target groups surveyed, who for one reason or another do not participate in this screening, should be informed that there are no other screening methods that could also effectively reduce mortality from CRC.

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Narcotics related death in the Kabul Forensic Medicine center

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Abstract

Introduction: Narcotics and psychotropic substances are substances whose small amounts cause significant changes in the body, mind or both. Narcotics pass through the blood brain barrier and cause disturbances in mood and perception. The spectrum of these substances and some medical spices such as: opiates, alcohol, hashish, cocaine, 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (oxatasi or tablet K) and so on. Deaths caused by narcotics poisoning are cases in which at least one or more narcotics are detected in the body

Objectives: obtaining the mortality due to narcotics and psychotropic related deaths in forensic cases

Method: The research was conducted through descriptive cross sectional study.

Results: Out of 2838 fatalities that were referred to the Kabul Forensic Medicine center during 2017 and 2018 years, (14%) fatalities were due to narcotics and the rest were due to other causes of death. Deaths due to narcotics in 2017, compared to 2018, showed an increase of 17.47%. The majority of cases were in the range of 21-40 years (an average of 30 years) which included 58.2 % of entire cases: (97%) cases were males and (3%) cases were females, (57.5%) single, most of them were unemployed (39.3%), low educated and illiterate cases were 53.39% and the lowest cases were with higher education (8.98%). The highest incidence happened in the winter (51.69%), and the lowest in the summer (13.8%). The most common cause of narcotics-related death were opiates (75.7%) and a significant of the narcotics were MDMA (5.8%). Most cases occur in the first (17%), fifth (16%), eighth (15%) and third (11.65%) security districts of Kabul city

Conclusion: Drug-related fatalities make up about one-seventh of all forensic fatalities, which are on the rise, mostly among young, male, single, illiterate, unemployed, and low-income people. Most of the causes of drug-related deaths are opium and addicts. The significant point of cases was MDMA (K tablet) (5.8%), which has become common among young people in recent years. Most incidents occur in the winter and from central and western parts of Kabul.

Keywords: Narcotics, Addicts, Dead body, Forensic Medicine

Introduction

Narcotic and psychotropic substances are substances whose small amounts cause significant changes in the body, mind or both. Narcotics pass through the blood brain barrier and cause disturbances in mood and perception. The spectrum of these substances are: opiates, alcohol, hashish, cocaine, 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (Oxatasi or tablet K) and so on. Deaths caused by narcotic drug poisoning are cases in which at least one or more narcotics are detected in the body. Determination of narcotics in post-mortem samples can be a cause of intoxication and as a contributing factor leading to death by narcotics.¹ Meanwhile, the issue of natural and unnatural death in conflicts are one of the cases that increase the prevalence of this problem. And from the view point of forensic medicine, it is extremely important, and on the other hand, based on the results of numerous studies, it can be said that many injuries and social problems such as theft, prostitution, murder, etc. have their roots in narcotics.^{1,2,4}

According to the United Nations Office report on June 26, 2019 about Narcotics and Crime between 155 and 250 million people worldwide, 3.5% to 5.7% of the population. has used illegal substances at least once between 15-64 years' old and also based on the mentioned report, it is estimated that around 35 million people suffer from narcotic drug use disorders in the world. The report also estimates the number of opiate users worldwide 53 million, which show 56 % increase from previous estimates, and that narcotics are responsible for two-thirds of the 585,000 people who died as a result of narcotic drugs use in the world in 2017.² Based on the findings of the Center for Monitoring Narcotics and Drug Addiction in Europe, which was published in 2019, it shows that the number of drug-related deaths in the European Union in 2017 were estimated 2388, and show a steady increase of 0.7% compared to 2016. The number of narcotic drug overdose deaths in Europe in 2017 was estimated 22.6 deaths per million populations. The number of narcotic drug overdose deaths in Europe in 2017 was estimated 22.6 deaths per million populations. People who use narcotics in Europe are mostly males, 35.8 cases per million males in the age group of 15-64 years, while in females (3.9 cases of females per million females in the age group of 15-64 years), In addition, it is estimated to account 4% of all deaths among people aged 15 to 39 years in Europe.³ In a research conducted in 2012 by k. Wies Simonsen and his colleagues in five countries (Denmark, Fland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden), In Denmark, according to the definition of the European Center for Drug Monitoring and Drug Addiction, The use of narcotics for every million population is 13,000 people and excess deaths for the last decade(657 cases (3.2%) with an average age 15-64 years)⁴. In Flanders, according to the report of the Monitoring Center for Narcotics and Drug Addiction in Europe, there are nearly 14,000 high-risk opiate users in age 15-64 years, 43 cases (2.4%) are drug-related deaths.⁴ In Iceland, the situation of narcotics is different compared to other countries, there are no statistics on deaths caused by narcotics.⁴ In Norway in addition to about 9,000 high-risk opiate users, excess deaths from narcotics during the last decade are 76 (9.3%) cases per million populations with an average age (15-64 years), which All of it has been examined in forensic medicine. In Sweden, it is estimated that the number of drug users is about 29,500, and drug-related deaths are 101 cases per million (4.4%), although the cause of death is determined by a doctor, and in case of suspicion, it is referred forensic medicine.⁴ In a research conducted in the neighboring country of Iran by Dr. Ghazizadeh on the files of all the bodies sent to the Provincial Forensic Medicine between 2014 and 2019, out of 123 cases under investigation, 93.5% were male and the rest were female (6.5%). In terms of age, the most bodies referred to forensic medicine are in the age group of 20-30 years old (37.4%), single people (54.5%), high educated (35.8%) and medium educated (32.5%), with freelance job (42. 3%).and unemployed (26.0%). In terms of the type of drug use, opium (39.0%), methadone (27.6%) and tramadol (17.9%) were the most frequent. Most of the deceased people are young people with a low level of education, low income and unemployed.⁷ In another similar research in Qom Province of Iran from 2008 to 2012, which was conducted by Dr. Fatemeh Shahbazi. The information related

to deaths caused by narcotics has been collected and analyzed based on the autopsy report and the characteristics of its demographic. During the five years, 388 drug poisoning deaths were recorded during the study, of which 264 (68%) were male and the rest were female. The results showed that the death rate in drug-related deaths decreased from 93 cases per million populations in 2008 to 49 cases in 2010 and then increased to 69 cases in 2012. the highest number of deaths in both sexes was accounted by Opium, Tramadol and antidepressants were the second cause of death in males and females, respectively. Most cases were in the age range of 20-30 years old. ⁸ In a study conducted by Mohammad Shakarzadeh et al. in 2013 in forensic medicine of Mazandaran Province of Iran, on the demographic characteristics of drug-related deaths from 2006 to 2011, out of 272 cases, the highest number of cases occurred in people with an average age of 27 years (42%) and had primary education up to diploma level and most of them had freelance job. ⁹

In this research, an attempt has been made to investigate the deaths that are directly or indirectly caused by narcotics and to use its results to fight effectively against this phenomenon, which is a serious threat to the health and life of people, especially the young generation, who are the real building force of society and country and causes serious damage to the social, economic, cultural and security system of the country.

Reasons and objectives

The increasing incidence of drug-related deaths in the country is the reason for choosing this research. Investigating the causes of death caused by drug addiction in the death cases of the Forensic Medicine center in terms of the type of event, type of drug, demographic characteristics, rate and graph of its occurrences, reducing the incidents of suicide and helping investigator and justice system to bring social regulation and justice are the key goals of this study.

Research Questions

1. What is the proportion of narcotic- related deaths with other causes of death?
2. What is the proportion of narcotic- related deaths in 2018 compared to 2017?
3. What is the incidence of poisoning in terms of demographic characteristics (age, sex, occupation, education level)?
4. What is the distribution of events in terms of seasons?
5. What is the proportion of narcotics incidents according to the type of narcotic?
6. What is the proportional distribution of narcotic- related deaths according to the security areas of Kabul city?

Material and Method

This research is designed as a descriptive cross-sectional study on drug-related deaths referred to the of Forensic Medicine center. The obtained information includes the demographic characteristics of the cases (age, sex, marital status, occupation and education level) based on the information of the register book of Forensic Medicine center and other characteristics such as the type of narcotics used in death cases based on the documents and opinions of Forensic Medicine center.

Results

Out of a total of 2838 deaths that were referred to the Forensic medicine service in 2017 (1300 deaths) and 2018 (1538 deaths), 412 deaths (14%) were caused by narcotics and the rest were caused by other causes of death.

Figure 1 proportion of death due to narcotics and other causes

As it is seen in the above chart, the death caused by narcotics shows a large and significant amount.

Out of 1300 deaths in 2017, 170 deaths (13%) were caused by narcotics and out of 1538 deaths in 2018, 242 deaths (15.7%) were caused by narcotics.

Figure 2 proportion of deaths caused by narcotics in 2018 compared to 2017

In the above chart, drug-related deaths in 2018 compared to 2017 show an increase of 17.47%, which is a significant difference. According to the information obtained from forensic medicine report, in terms of age, there are 41 cases in the age group of 11-20 years, 179 cases in the age group of 21-30 years, 101 cases in the age group of 31-40 years, 55 cases in the age group of 41-50 years. 24 cases occurred in the age group of 51 to 60 years and 12 cases occurred in the age group above 60 years.

Figure 3 number death due to narcotics in term of age

In the above chart, it can be seen that in terms of age, mostly young people between the age group of 21 to 40 years (with an average age of 30 years) are involved, a total of 240 deaths (58.2%) constitute the highest number of deaths caused by narcotics. Incidents in terms of gender include 399 case in males (97%) and 13 case in females, 3%.

Figure 4 Drug-related deaths by gender

The above chart shows that in terms of gender, the most deaths caused by narcotics are 399 cases (97%) for males and 13 cases (3%) for females. In terms of marital status, the number of deaths caused by narcotics is 237 cases (57.5%) single, 115 cases (27.9%) married, and the remaining 60 cases (27.9%) were unidentified whose information related to their marital status is not recorded

percentage	Number of cases	Marital status
57.5%	237	Single
27.9%	115	Married
14.5%	60	Unknown

Chart 1 drug related deaths in term of marital status

As can be seen in the above table, in terms of marital status, most deaths caused by narcotics are single people. In terms of seasons, 68 cases (16.5%) occurred in spring, 57 case (13.8%) in summer, 72 case (17.96%) in fall and 213 case (51.69%) in winter.

Figure 5. Drug related death in term of season

As can be seen in the above table, the most deaths caused by narcotics occurred in winter and the least in summer. that there is a close relationship between environmental temperature and deaths caused by narcotics. In terms of education level, 93 cases (22.57%) were illiterate, 127 cases (27.18%) had primary education, 44 cases (10.67%) had a bachelor's degree, 36 cases (8.98%) had higher education, and the remaining 112 cases (27.18%) was unknown and the information is not recorded in relation to their education level.

Figure 6. Drug related death in term of education level

According to the above table, in terms of the education level of the deceased people due to narcotics were mostly illiterate and poorly educated, which constitutes a total of 320 case (53.39%) which is more than half of the case, and the least number of victims had higher education. In terms of occupation, 24 cases (5.8%) are employees, 55 cases (13.34%) are self-employed, 54 cases (10.92%) are school student, 15 cases (3.64%) are housekeepers, 162 cases (39.3%) are unemployed and the rest (24) cases (13.8%) were unknown whose information is not recorded in relation to their employment status.

Figure 7. Narcotics related death in term of occupation

In terms of occupation, most of the drug-related deceased people were unemployed, which indicates a close relationship between drug addiction and work and income. In terms of determining the type of narcotics, the determined type of narcotics in the forensic toxicology laboratory were 312 cases (75.7%) of opiates, 32 cases (12.86%) of alcohol, 8 cases of cocaine (1.94%), 15 cases of hashish (3.64%), 24 cases of exatasia (5.8%).

Figure 8 narcotics related death in term of drug type

In terms of determining the type of drug, as seen in the above chart, the most incidents are related to opiates (opium and its preparations, especially heroin), of course, a significant amount (5.8%) is 3, 4 methylenedioxy-methamphetamine, which has become popular among young people in recent years. According to the security districts of Kabul city, the most incidents among

the 18 security districts are 70 incidents from the first district, 66 incidents from the fifth district, 62 incidents from the eighth district, 48 incidents from the third district and 34 incidents from The sixth district has been referred to the Forensic medicine center. No event has been sent from the 14th and 18th districts.

Figure 9. Distribution of drug related death according Kabul security district

in the above chart, most of the incidents referred from the security areas of Kabul city are related to the crowded parts of the center and the west side of Kabul.

Discussion

Findings in this research shows that narcotics are one of the main causes of death in cases referred to the Forensic Medicine center. Based on the collected information, out of 2838 deaths that were referred to the Forensic Medicine center during 2017 and 2018, 412 deaths (14%) were caused by narcotics and the rest were caused by other causes of death. It constitutes a significant number of drug-related deaths, while according to the European Center for Monitoring Narcotics and Drug Addiction published in 2019, drug-related deaths constitute 4% of total deaths in Europe were caused by narcotics. the results of similar studies in Northern European countries such as: Denmark (3.2%), Finland (2.4%), Norway (9.3%) and Sweden (4.4%), shows a significant difference with the findings of this research, which may be due to people's access to narcotics (wide cultivation of opium) and failure to address the health needs of addicts and other social factors caused by the continuation of war (depression)^{2,3,4}. The number of Deaths caused by narcotics in 2018 (242 deaths) compared to 2017 (170 deaths), shows an increase of 72 cases which is a significant increase (17.47%). The reason for this can be the increasing number of people in the society turning to narcotics for various reasons, including the continuation of the war and the lack of control of drug cultivation and traffic, and other social causes (psychological, economic, cultural, such as the high rate of depression, unemployment rate, and lack of healthy employment among

community members, especially young people). In terms of age, the most cases among young people were between the age group of 21 to 40 years (with an average age of 30 years) which form a total of 240 cases (58.2%). In comparison to the study conducted in the country of Iran in the province of Kohgiluyeh, Boyer Ahmad, 37.4% were in the age group of 20-30 year and other similar studies conducted in Northern European and Asian countries, which show the highest incidence in the age group between 20 and 30 years.^{2,4,7}

In terms of gender, there are 399 incidents in males, 97%, and 13 incidents in females, 3%, which is slightly different from a research conducted in Kohgiluyeh Province, Boyer Ahmad of Iran (93.5%) of males⁷. While in Qom province of Iran, study shows the difference to (68%) in males and (32%) in females⁸. which itself goes back to cultural and social issues and the presence of women outside the home and their way of life, Since in Afghanistan, compared to other countries, the unnecessary presence of women outside the home is limited, and at the same time, the limitation of financial independence and the lack of familiarity and the uncommonness of the free use of tobacco and narcotics by the female, on the other hand based on traditional and ruling values In the society, if there is an addict, the female is not pushed to the society by the family So that the vital event or death is reported and recorded to the judicial authorities, so the above mentioned points are the reasons that justify the discrepancy in the deaths of drug addicts in terms of gender compared to other countries. In terms of civil status, the number of deaths caused by narcotics is 237 cases (57.5%) single, 115 cases (27.9%) married, and the remaining 60 cases (27.9%) are unknown. Although the information related to their civil status was not recorded in almost a third of the cases due to the fact that the bodies were unidentified, but most of the cases happened to single people, which is consistent with the results of other similar studies⁷. The reasons for young people to turn to narcotics are issues such as unemployment, poverty, psychological problems caused by it, and issues such as not achieving emotional desires and wishes such as love failure and similar. In terms of educational level, the deceased people who died due to narcotics were mostly illiterate and poorly educated, with a total of 320 cases (53.39%), which constituted more than half of the cases, and the least number of victims had higher education, 36 cases (8.98%). which is similar to studies conducted in Asian countries such as Iran^{7,9}. in terms of occupation, 24 cases (5.8%) were employees, 55 cases (13.34%) were self-employed, 54 cases (10.92%) were educated, 15 cases (3.64 %) household affairs, and the remaining 24 cases (13.8%) include unexplained deaths and cases whose information is not recorded in relation to their employment status. In terms of the occupation, 162 cases (39.3%) were unemployed, which represents a close relationship between drug addiction with work and income, and it is consistent with the literature^{7,12}. in another study, the cases were mostly among people who have a freelance job with low income, findings in this research shows that most of the incidents happened to low-income and unemployed people, maybe the unemployment rate in the country compared to other countries is the reason for the difference^{12,9}. In terms of seasons, the most deaths occurred in the winter season, 213 cases (51.69%) and the least cases in the summer season, 57 cases (13.8%) occurred in the summer, which was caused by taking an excessive amount of narcotics, being exposed to the cold, the possible reason could be lack of access to suitable livelihoods and health services. In terms of establishing the type of narcotics based on data, 312 cases (75.7%) of opiates, 32 cases (12.86%) of alcohol, 8 cases of cocaine (1.94%), 15 cases of hashish (3.64%), 24 cases of 3,4-methylenedioxy-methamphetamine (5.8 %). Most of the incidents are related to opiates (opium and its preparations, especially heroin). These findings are similar to the results of the research conducted in the forensic medicine of Kermanshah province in Iran (55.59%), while in European countries, along with the deaths caused by opiates and their preparations, alcohol is also significantly high^{3,4,6,7,9,12}. The difference in Afghanistan is mostly related to easy access to narcotics (cultivation and large traffic of opium and heroin) and social issues like lack of monitoring of the ban on the use of opium and its preparations

in proportion to alcohol in the society. Of course, the turning point in this research is the finding a significant amount of the narcotics were 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (5.8%), which has become common among young people in recent years, which requires the study of the reasons for access to it by people in the society. In relation to the last question of the research in terms of sending incidents to the security areas of Kabul city, the most incidents among the 18 security areas are 70 incidents (17%) from the first area, 66 incidents (16%) from the fifth area, 62 incidents (15%) from the eighth precinct, 48 cases (11.65%) from the third precinct have been referred to the Department of Forensic Services, while no cases have been sent from the fourteenth precinct and the eighteenth precinct. According to the findings, most of the cases were referred from the first (city center), fifth, eighth, sixth and third districts (west of Kabul) of Kabul city, and most of the reasons are related to the special nature of commercial areas and population density, which is a suitable place for waste collection. (Employment of the majority of addicts) and the return of a number of residents of these neighborhoods from emigration, especially from Iran.

Conclusion

Deaths caused by narcotics and psychotropic constitute approximately one-seventh of all deaths referred to forensic medicine, which is a worrying amount, compared to 2017, the number of deaths shows a significant increase in 2018, the highest number of deaths caused by narcotics and psychotropic consists of young, male, single, illiterate or low-educated and unemployed people with low income, which The main causes are easy access to narcotics, low level of education, unemployment and lack of healthy activities for young people. In terms of the seasons, the most deaths occurred in winter, which shows a direct relationship with the environmental temperature, living conditions and access to health care. Most of death caused by narcotics are opium and its preparations, which is due to easy access to narcotics (cultivation and wide traffic of opium and heroin) and social issues like, lack of supervision on the prohibition use of opium and its preparations in proportion to alcohol in the society. the turning point in this research is the finding of a significant amount of the narcotics (5.8%) were 3,4-Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (K), which has become common among young people in recent years, which requires studying the reasons for access to it by people in the society.

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Sociological Sciences

Migration processes in the border zones (Russia and Kazakhstan)

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This article discusses the problem of border migration on the example of Kazakhstan and Russia. Specifically, it is the management of migration, the intervention of migrants, the flow of migrants in recent years and how to regulate them. The purpose of this article is related to the study of the current situation in the field of migration in the border territories of Kazakhstan and Russia, as well as the development of recommendations and strategies for effective migration management. The article also provides for the analysis of political, economic, social and cultural factors affecting migration processes in border territories and the consideration of modern challenges and problems related to migration management. In general, the purpose of the article is related to increasing awareness and understanding of the topic of migration management in the border territories of Kazakhstan and Russia.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, Russia, migrants, border territory, management of migration processes

The object is migration processes taking place in the border territory between Kazakhstan and Russia.

The subject of this article is the consideration of issues related to the management of migration in this border territory. The main issues that can be considered within the framework of the article include:

- Overview of the current situation and trends in migration processes in the border area;
- Analysis of factors affecting migration in the border territory, such as economic, social, political, etc. ;
- Assessment of the existing migration management system in the border area and its effectiveness;
- Development of proposals and recommendations for improving the migration management system in the border area.

Thus, the topic of the article is related to the consideration of problems and difficulties associated with the management of border migration, as well as the search for possible ways to solve these problems.

Main text

Migration management on the border territory of Kazakhstan and Russia is one of the most important tasks for both countries. Russia and Kazakhstan have a common border with a length

of more than 7 thousand kilometers, along which a significant flow of people and cargo flows every day. In recent years, the migration flow between the two countries has intensified.

Kazakhstan and Russia constantly interact in the field of migration management to reduce the negative consequences of migration and improve the socio-economic conditions of migrants. The main points of migration management are border control, information exchange and coordination of actions.

One of the most important tools in migration management is legislation. Both countries should have an effective system of legal regulation of migration, which will ensure the protection of the rights of migrants and prevent illegal migration. In Kazakhstan, there is a law "on migration", which regulates the procedures for controlling migration and issuing work permits for foreign citizens. Russia, in turn, adopted a number of legislative changes aimed at strengthening control over border territories and preventing illegal border crossings.

In addition, it is important to develop international cooperation in the field of migration management, as well as strengthen the institutions responsible for protecting the rights of migrants and providing migration services. Within the CIS, a regional migration program has been established aimed at coordinating efforts to manage migration and promote the exchange of experience.

One of the main problems of migration management in the border territory of Kazakhstan and Russia is illegal migration. People who cross the border illegally often become victims of violence, exploitation and other forms of violation of their rights. It is important to take measures to prevent illegal migration and combat illegal channels of border crossing.

Another important task is to protect the rights of migrants. Migrants often face discrimination, violence and exploitation in the workplace. It is important to promote the creation of conditions that ensure equal rights and opportunities for migrants, as well as provide them with access to medical services, education and housing.

On the other hand, migration can make a positive contribution to the development of the economy of both states. Migrants can have a significant impact on the labor market, trade and other sectors of the economy. It is important to promote the creation of conditions for the integration of migrants into the economy and society, as well as support the socio-economic development of the regions.

To improve migration management in the border territories of Kazakhstan and Russia, it is necessary to consider a number of additional measures.

- The first measure may be to improve the information campaign. Kazakhstan and Russia should conduct information campaigns to help migrants understand the migration process and the risks associated with it. These campaigns should explain the rights and obligations of migrants, as well as the opportunities available in both countries.

- The second measure may be to simplify the process of obtaining a work permit for migrants. Many migrants have difficulty obtaining work permits, which can lead to illegal migration and exploitation. Simplifying the process of obtaining a work permit can reduce illegal migration and improve working conditions for migrants.

- The third measure may be to improve migration control and control mechanisms. Kazakhstan and Russia should strengthen monitoring and control over illegal migration, including the elimination of illegal channels of border crossing and the fight against illegal employers. It also helps prevent the exploitation of migrants and improve their living and working conditions.

- The fourth measure may be to strengthen cooperation between government agencies and public organizations of the two countries. Government agencies and public organizations should work together to develop strategies and programs to manage migration and protect the rights of migrants. It can also contribute to the creation of conditions for the integration of migrants into the economy and society.

In general, the management of migration in the border territory of Kazakhstan and Russia is a difficult task, but with the adoption of the set of measures described above, significant progress can be made in the fight against illegal migration, protecting the rights of migrants and creating conditions for their integration.

Thus, an important aspect of migration management in the border territory of Kazakhstan and Russia is cooperation with other countries. Due to globalization and increasing migration flows, international cooperation plays an important role in managing migration. Kazakhstan and Russia should work with other countries and regional organizations to develop common strategies and programs for managing migration and protecting the rights of migrants.

It should also be noted that migration is a complex and multifaceted process, and its management is a long and stable process. Kazakhstan and Russia should constantly update and improve migration management strategies and programs, taking into account changes in the global economy, political and social conditions, as well as new challenges and risks associated with migration.

This year, due to the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, the situation has changed dramatically and from 115 to 200 thousand people entered the country almost simultaneously, according to various data. At the moment, we are seeing a "second wave" of migrants from a neighboring country. However, there is a certain difference between the two migration waves, - says Aliya Orazgalieva, an expert at the Institute of world economy and politics. A lot of research has been carried out on the topic of migration in the border areas. For example, many scientific and public organizations are engaged in research in Kazakhstan, including the Research Institute "L. N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University", the Institute of Economics under the Ministry of national economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Migration center under the Association of women entrepreneurs of Kazakhstan, etc.

Such an introduction makes it possible to assume that the "first wave" of migrants largely easily adapted to new conditions, these people found work and housing on their own in a short time or started their business here. Although for our country this is a stressful situation, both the administrative and bureaucratic apparatus and the market as a whole coped with this task with ease. It is important to note with what mood Kazakhstanis met the "first wave" of migrants. The population of the country reacted to this situation with a neutral-positive attitude, since migrants from both countries were repressed, on the one hand, war refugees, and on the other, former compatriots from fraternal countries, – said Aliya Orazgalieva.

For the population of our country, such a migration picture can have both positive and negative sides. Among the positives, one can name a significant influx of solvent customers, which supports the position of the business, especially in the post-pandemic period. And also the possibility of a positive impact of competitiveness on novice highly qualified specialists and experienced entrepreneurs-in connection with construction, HORECA and especially in the IT industries, where the authorities of our country are betting, – noted the sociologist.

In Russia, research in the field of migration in border territories is being conducted, including the Russian Institute for Strategic Studies, the Institute of sociology of the RAS, the Institute of geography of the RAS and others.

In addition, international organizations such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM), the United Nations (UN), the European Union and others are also studying and developing strategies for managing migration in border areas.

An analysis of the current state of migration in the border territory between Kazakhstan and Russia shows that migration processes remain an urgent problem for both states. Statistical data show that the number of migrants in the border area is growing every year.

Since April 1, 2022, 93,045 citizens of the Russian Federation have received the IIN. 4,271 people received a residence permit, of which 116 are our ethnic Kazakhs. As for the residence

permit, there is a special procedure. Each of them confirmed his solvency. We have 441 people applied for citizenship, 117 of them are ethnic Kazakhs from the Russian Federation, so statistics show that the number of migrants is growing in the border territory between Kazakhstan and Russia, which requires effective measures to manage migration and solve related challenges and problems.

According to official data of the Ministry of internal affairs, a total of 2 million 414 thousand Russian citizens entered Kazakhstan and 2 million 292 thousand Russian citizens left. Since September 21, when partial mobilization began in Russia, 420,000 Russians came to us, of which 310,000 left. From 18 to 45 years old, 221,068 citizens of the Russian Federation visited, from 46 to 60 years old – 44,800 Russian citizens.

There are a number of factors that affect the inflow of migrants from Russia to Kazakhstan. Some of them can be economic, social, political or personal.

One of the main economic factors is the difference in the level of wages between Kazakhstan and Russia. For example, according to Rosstat, at the end of 2020, the average salary in Russia was about 50 thousand rubles a month, while in Kazakhstan this figure was about two times less. In this regard, many citizens of Kazakhstan go to Russia to earn money, and Russians cross the border to work in Kazakhstan.

Social stability is also an important factor. Russia has a number of social problems, such as unemployment, inequality and a high level of poverty, which can lead to an increase in migration flows to Kazakhstan, where the general economic and social situation is more favorable.

Political factors can also play a role in migration processes. For example, changing migration legislation or tightening registration rules can affect the flow of migrants between the two countries.

So, personal factors such as the presence of relatives, friends or acquaintances in another country, as well as the desire to acquire new experiences, can stimulate the migration flow.

The main factor in the flow of migrants from Russia to Kazakhstan last year was the difficult political situation between Russia and Ukraine. After that, partial mobilization was announced in Russia in September 2022. The flow of migrants has sharply increased since the beginning of the Russian military operation on the territory of sovereign Ukraine on February 24, 2022 to all post-Soviet countries with light migration laws.

For 2023, some legislative acts on migration issues in Kazakhstan were revised.

In particular, for immigrants arriving in countries that do not require obtaining a visa, the period of permitted stay of visitors to the Republic of Kazakhstan expires after the expiration of 90 calendar days, 30 calendar days from the date of crossing the state border of the Republic of Kazakhstan, for a total of 180 calendar days, unless otherwise established by the agreement of the Republic of Kazakhstan with the relevant party or the government of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

- The period of stay for citizens of the member states of the Eurasian Economic Union is 90 calendar days, totaling 180 calendar days for each period after the expiration of 90 calendar days from the date of crossing the state border of the Republic of Kazakhstan.
- For immigrants arriving in the Republic of Kazakhstan on the basis of a visa-after the expiration of the visa. For citizens of states that have ratified international treaties defining other terms of stay in the Republic of Kazakhstan – after the expiration of the terms specified in these treaties. For immigrants who have issued a temporary residence permit-after the expiration of this permit.
- For immigrants brought to administrative responsibility for previously committed violations of the period of stay in the Republic of Kazakhstan – after FIFTEEN calendar days after the decision on bringing to administrative responsibility.

- For immigrants convicted of committing a criminal offense – after 10 calendar days after serving the sentence or release from punishment, except in cases of their expulsion on the basis of a court decision.
 - For immigrants permanently residing in the Republic of Kazakhstan and who have issued documents for departure from the Republic of Kazakhstan to a permanent place of residence abroad-after 30 calendar days after registration of documents •
 - For immigrants who, in accordance with the procedure established by the Criminal Procedure legislation, have reported on the commission of acts against them recognized as serious or especially serious crimes in accordance with the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan-after 30 calendar days after consideration of the application in accordance with the Criminal Procedure legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan.
 - For immigrants sentenced to probation, as well as released on parole for punishments not related to isolation from society according to the sentences of the courts of the Republic of Kazakhstan-after the expiration of 15 calendar days after the end of the appointed term of punishment or the unserved part of the sentence •
 - For immigrants recognized as a victim or witness in criminal cases of such crimes in accordance with the procedure established by criminal procedure legislation-the period of stay is extended for the period necessary for the investigation of the criminal case, but not more than 90 calendar days.
 - In exceptional cases (when social, natural, man-made emergencies and the introduction of an emergency due to the real threat of a natural disaster or large - scale accident (accident), as well as violation of the transport schedule) - the period of stay is extended for the period necessary for organizing the exit, but not more than 30 calendar days.

Registration of immigrants living or working in leased territories from the Republic of Kazakhstan is carried out in the information system of the migration service when traveling outside the leased territory on the basis of identity documents and registration at the place of residence in the leased territory. At the same time, the date of entry into the Republic of Kazakhstan is the date of exit from the leased territory.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that migration management in the border territory of Kazakhstan and Russia is an important task that requires a comprehensive and long-term approach. To achieve success in this area, it is necessary to take a set of measures, including improving the information campaign, simplifying the process of obtaining a work permit, strengthening migration monitoring and control, strengthening cooperation between government agencies and public organizations, and cooperation with other countries. The implementation of these measures will help improve the living and working conditions of migrants, prevent illegal migration and create conditions for their integration into the economy and society.

In this article, we examined the issue of migration management in the border territories of Kazakhstan and Russia. Looking at the statistics and analyzing the situation, we identified some of the reasons and factors that affect the migration flow between these two countries.

From our analysis, it turns out that there is a large influx of migrants between Kazakhstan and Russia, due to a number of economic, social, political and personal factors. One of the main factors affecting the influx of migrants is the difference in the level of wages between the two countries. In addition, social stability, changes in migration legislation and individual factors also affect the migration flow.

In connection with the above factors, the states of Kazakhstan and Russia should develop and implement coordinated policies and measures aimed at managing migration flows in the border territories. An important step can be the development of a more effective system of

control and accounting of migrants, as well as improving the conditions for their integration into society and the labor market.

In addition, an important aspect of managing migration flows is ensuring the rights and freedoms of migrants. States must ensure that the rights to equal treatment, work, housing and education are respected, as well as protection against discrimination and violence. This may also include providing migrants with access to health care and social protection.

Thus, the management of migration in the border territories of Kazakhstan and Russia is an important task that requires interaction and cooperation between the two states. It can also offer opportunities for the development of economic and cultural ties between the peoples of the two countries and the region.

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Economic Sciences

ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN AUDITING

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ABSTRACT

Ethical dilemmas frequently arise in the auditing profession, posing significant challenges to auditors' moral judgment and decision-making. This research study aims to investigate the various ethical dilemmas faced by auditors during engagements and delve into the factors influencing their decision-making processes. By examining real-life case studies and conducting in-depth interviews with experienced auditors, this research seeks to shed light on the complexities surrounding ethical decision-making in auditing. The research methodology entails a qualitative approach, employing semi-structured interviews to gather rich and nuanced data. Auditors from diverse backgrounds and experience levels will be selected to ensure a comprehensive exploration of ethical dilemmas encountered in different contexts. The collected data will be analyzed using thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of common themes and patterns in auditors' decision-making processes when faced with ethical challenges.

Key areas of investigation will include auditors' awareness of ethical dilemmas, the factors influencing their decision-making (such as personal values, professional guidelines, and organizational culture), and the strategies employed to resolve ethical dilemmas effectively. The study aims to identify common ethical dilemmas faced by auditors, examine the ethical frameworks and principles employed by auditors, and assess the effectiveness of existing professional codes of ethics in guiding auditors' ethical decision-making. The findings of this research will have significant implications for auditing practice and ethics education. By gaining a deeper understanding of auditors' ethical decision-making processes, it will be possible to identify areas where additional support, training, or guidance may be required. The study also aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on auditors' ethics by providing insights into the nuanced and complex nature of ethical dilemmas in the auditing profession.

Ultimately, this research seeks to enhance auditors' ethical awareness, decision-making capabilities, and professional judgment, promoting ethical conduct and integrity within the auditing field. It is hoped that the findings will facilitate the development of effective strategies and resources to support auditors in navigating ethical dilemmas, thereby reinforcing trust and confidence in the auditing profession as a whole.

INTRODUCTION

Ethical dilemmas are inherent in the auditing profession, presenting auditors with complex and multifaceted challenges that require careful consideration and decision-making. As professionals responsible for evaluating the accuracy and integrity of financial statements, auditors often encounter situations that demand difficult ethical judgments. These dilemmas may arise from conflicting interests, pressure from management or clients, ambiguous professional guidelines, or a myriad of other factors. The consequences of ethical lapses in auditing can be severe, undermining the credibility of financial information, eroding public trust, and compromising the effectiveness of corporate governance. Therefore, understanding the nature of ethical dilemmas faced by auditors and exploring their decision-making processes is of paramount

importance to ensure the integrity and reliability of auditing practices. The primary objective of this research study is to delve into the realm of ethical dilemmas in auditing and shed light on the factors that influence auditors' ethical decision-making. By examining real-life case studies and conducting in-depth interviews with experienced auditors, this research aims to explore the intricacies and complexities associated with ethical challenges in the auditing profession.

The research will adopt a qualitative approach, utilizing semi-structured interviews to gather rich and context-specific data. A diverse pool of auditors, encompassing various backgrounds and experience levels, will be selected to ensure a comprehensive exploration of ethical dilemmas encountered in different organizational and industry contexts. Thematic analysis will be employed to identify common themes and patterns in auditors' decision-making processes when confronted with ethical dilemmas. The study will encompass several key areas of investigation. Firstly, it will explore auditors' awareness of ethical dilemmas and their perception of the challenges posed by these dilemmas. Additionally, the research will examine the influential factors that impact auditors' ethical decision-making processes, such as personal values, professional guidelines, organizational culture, and stakeholder pressures. Moreover, the strategies employed by auditors to resolve ethical dilemmas effectively will be explored to gain insights into the decision-making approaches utilized in such situations. By uncovering and analyzing the nuances of auditors' ethical decision-making, this research aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on ethics in auditing. The findings will provide valuable insights into the complexities surrounding ethical dilemmas in the auditing profession, enhancing our understanding of auditors' ethical conduct and decision-making capabilities.

The implications of this research are significant for both auditing practice and ethics education. The insights gained from the study can inform the development of targeted training programs, ethical guidelines, and support mechanisms to assist auditors in navigating ethical dilemmas effectively. Ultimately, the research aims to foster a culture of ethical conduct, strengthen professional judgment, and reinforce public trust in the auditing profession.

In conclusion, ethical dilemmas are an inherent aspect of auditing, necessitating careful examination and understanding. By investigating the nature of these dilemmas and the decision-making processes of auditors, this research seeks to contribute to the advancement of ethical practices in auditing, promoting integrity, and upholding the highest standards of professional conduct.

1. TYPES OF ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN AUDITING

Auditors often encounter a variety of ethical dilemmas throughout their professional practice. These ethical dilemmas can arise from conflicting interests, ambiguous professional guidelines, client pressures, or a combination of factors. Understanding the different types of ethical dilemmas faced by auditors is crucial for analyzing the complexities involved in maintaining ethical conduct. Some common types of ethical dilemmas in auditing include:

1.1 Conflicts of Interest

Auditors may face situations where their personal or financial interests conflict with their duty to maintain independence and objectivity. For example, auditors may have financial investments in client organizations or personal relationships with key individuals that compromise their impartiality.

1.2 Pressure to overlook or misrepresent information

Auditors may face pressures from clients or management to overlook or misrepresent information that could affect the accuracy and reliability of financial statements. This may include instances where auditors are encouraged to hide or downplay material errors, misstatements, or non-compliance with accounting principles.

1.3 Client Confidentiality

Auditors are entrusted with sensitive and confidential information about their clients. Ethical dilemmas may arise when auditors encounter situations where disclosing certain information could conflict with client confidentiality obligations or legal requirements. Determining the appropriate balance between transparency and confidentiality can be challenging.

1.4 Professional Skepticism

Auditors are expected to approach their work with professional skepticism, exercising critical judgment and maintaining an attitude of doubt. Ethical dilemmas may arise when auditors are faced with situations where they must challenge management assertions, demand additional evidence, or raise concerns despite resistance from clients or superiors.

1.5 Auditor Independence

Maintaining auditor independence is a fundamental ethical principle. However, auditors may encounter dilemmas related to maintaining independence when client relationships become too close or when auditors face threats to their objectivity, such as the provision of non-audit services or financial relationships with clients.

2. EXAMPLES OF ETHICAL DILEMMAS IN AUDITING

To illustrate the complexity of ethical dilemmas in auditing, we can consider the following examples:

2.1 Revenue Recognition

An auditor discovers that a client has engaged in aggressive revenue recognition practices that do not conform to accounting standards. The auditor faces a dilemma of whether to report the non-compliance, potentially damaging the client's reputation and financial position, or to remain silent, compromising professional integrity.

2.2 Management Pressure

During an audit engagement, the client's management insists on pressuring the auditor to overlook certain irregularities in financial reporting to meet financial targets. The auditor must decide whether to succumb to the pressure and compromise professional ethics or maintain independence and report the irregularities.

2.3 Insider Trading

An auditor becomes aware of material non-public information about a client's impending merger. The auditor faces an ethical dilemma regarding whether to trade securities based on the confidential information or maintain confidentiality and avoid any potential conflicts of interest.

2.4 Whistleblowing

An auditor discovers fraudulent activities within the client organization but faces threats and retaliation if the information is reported. The auditor must decide whether to blow the whistle, potentially jeopardizing their career, or remain silent, compromising their ethical responsibilities.

These examples illustrate the intricate ethical dilemmas auditors may encounter in their professional practice. The decision-making processes involved in resolving such dilemmas require careful consideration of ethical principles, professional guidelines, and the potential consequences for all stakeholders involved. Understanding the types and examples of ethical dilemmas faced by auditors provides valuable insights into the challenges they encounter in maintaining ethical conduct. This knowledge serves as a foundation for developing effective ethical guidelines, providing appropriate training and support, and reinforcing the importance of integrity and professionalism within the auditing profession.

CONCLUSION

Ethical dilemmas in auditing pose significant challenges for auditors as they navigate the complexities of maintaining integrity, objectivity, and professional conduct. The examination of different types of ethical dilemmas faced by auditors and the examples provided shed light on the

intricate nature of ethical challenges in the auditing profession. The types of ethical dilemmas outlined, including conflicts of interest, pressure to overlook or misrepresent information, client confidentiality concerns, professional skepticism, and auditor independence issues, highlight the multifaceted ethical landscape auditors navigate. These dilemmas often require auditors to make difficult decisions that impact their professional reputation, the reliability of financial information, and the overall trust placed in the auditing profession.

The examples of ethical dilemmas in auditing further illustrate the intricate decisions auditors must make. These examples demonstrate the need for auditors to carefully balance competing interests, exercise professional judgment, and uphold ethical principles in the face of challenging circumstances. Ethical dilemmas such as revenue recognition practices, management pressure, insider trading, and whistleblowing highlight the complex and sensitive nature of auditors' roles and responsibilities. Addressing ethical dilemmas in auditing necessitates a holistic approach that encompasses ethical education, clear professional guidelines, and a supportive ethical culture within audit firms. Training programs should equip auditors with the necessary ethical frameworks, critical thinking skills, and tools to identify, assess, and resolve ethical dilemmas effectively. Furthermore, regulatory bodies and professional organizations play a crucial role in setting and enforcing ethical standards, providing oversight, and fostering accountability. The implications of understanding and addressing ethical dilemmas in auditing are far-reaching. Upholding ethical conduct and integrity within the auditing profession is essential to maintain public trust, ensure the reliability of financial information, and promote confidence in corporate governance. By acknowledging the intricacies of ethical dilemmas, auditors, professional bodies, and educators can work together to enhance ethical awareness, develop robust decision-making frameworks, and create a supportive environment that encourages ethical conduct.

It is crucial for auditors to continuously reflect on and improve their ethical decision-making capabilities, as the auditing landscape evolves and presents new challenges. Ongoing research, comparative studies, and the exploration of emerging ethical issues will contribute to the continued development of best practices and ethical guidelines in the field of auditing.

In conclusion, recognizing and addressing ethical dilemmas in auditing is essential for maintaining the integrity and reputation of the auditing profession. By understanding the types of dilemmas faced, learning from real-life examples, and fostering a culture of ethics and professionalism, auditors can navigate ethical challenges effectively, thereby upholding the highest standards of ethical conduct and promoting public trust in the auditing profession.

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОЕКТНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ И ЕЕ ОЦЕНКА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривает методология оценки проектного управления

Ключевые слова: проектное управление, эффективность проектного управления, портфель проектов.

Динамичное развитие отрасли и субъектов здравоохранения под влиянием изменении внешней среды вынуждает переходить на стратегическое управление, которое позволяет добиваться поставленных целей в рамках запланированных бюджетов [1]. Использование инструментов стратегического управления, например: проектного управления способствуют к достаточно быстрому и эффективному достижению целей организации. Но при этом возникает необходимость производить срезы по достижению целей и задач стратегического планирования. Так в рамках проектного управления производится оценка эффективности как отдельно взятого проекта, так и портфеля в целом. В связи с чем, на наш взгляд, методы оценки эффективности проектного управления должны быть систематизированы и иметь четкую иерархию в процедурах оценки эффективности управления проектами [2].

Итак, для систематизации методов эффективности проектного управления, предлагаем разобраться с понятием проектного управления. Согласно международному стандарту РМА (A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge, PMBoK Guide) под проектом понимается временное предприятие, предназначенное на создание уникального продукта, услуги или результата(ов), регламентированные техническим паспортом и имеющие сроки начала и завершения работ по нему, т.е. он имеет четкие сроки и является ограниченным, во времени пространстве и ресурсах [3]. Тем самым, сам процесс управления проектами наглядно можем представить следующим образом: (рисунок 1).

Рисунок 1. Последовательность процессов в проектном управлении [4].

Под инициацией проекта мы понимаем, принятие решения о реализации проекта. Далее определяем цель проекта, документально фиксируем ее, составляем план-график, сметы проекта. Также создаем проектную команду. Следующий этап — это «Планирование», подразумевает работу уже проектной команды по определению внешних и внутренних заинтересованных сторон, проводится анализ цели проекта, структурируются все мероприятия в некий план -график. Реализация данного плана является следующим этапом «Исполнение». При исполнении возможны различные изменения и необходимость корректировок, что в свою очередь отражает следующий этап «Мониторинг реализации», т.е. регуляция процессов исполнения плана. Завершение проекта и выход из него определяется сроками исполнения целей и задач плана-графика и оценкой удовлетворенности стейкхолдеров.

Что касается формирования системы управления проектами, согласно вышеуказанному стандарту проектного управления ст. 18 ^{A-C} и 22 ^{D-F} выделяют три модели организации проектного управления: 1) ресурсно-ориентированная; 2) процессно - ориентированная; 3) инновационно – ориентированная (рисунок 2).

Рисунок 2. Модели организации проектного управления [4].

Ресурсно – ориентированная модель ориентирована на использование ресурсов организации максимально продуктивно и методом оценки системы управления проектами, на наш взгляд, для оценки эффективности проектного управления можно применить метод расчета избыточных прибылей, который ориентирован на получение максимального результата [5]:

$$G = \frac{\Delta NP \times n}{(1+d)^n}, \text{ где}$$

G – величина экономического эффекта;

ΔNP – отклонение по чистой прибыли между проектом и среднеотраслевой величиной;

n – прогнозируемый период реализации проекта;

d – ставка дисконта, %.

Процессно – ориентированная модель предназначена для поэтапного изменения в компании отдельных бизнес-процессов для эффективного функционирования активов организации, который возможно оценить методом дополнительного продукта:

$$G = \frac{NP_{cd} - Q_{fc} \times Re_{aver}}{R_g}, \text{ где}$$

G – величина экономического эффекта;

NP_{cd} – чистая прибыль от текущей деятельности;

Q_{fc} – объем реализации продукции по полной стоимости;

Re_{aver} – среднеотраслевой коэффициент рентабельности продаж;

R_g – коэффициент рентабельности НМА, рассчитанный по чистой прибыли [6].

Под инновационно – ориентированной моделью проектного управления понимается система, ориентированная на новые продукты. Для оценки данной системы, считаем целесообразным, использовать методы, используемые при оценке интеллектуальной

деятельности персонала: балансового накопления активов, при расчете используют информацию о составе, структуре, цене [6, 7]:

$$G = \frac{CF_{sales} - (IA + FPC + QIC + SMC)}{(1+R)^n}, \text{ где}$$

G – величина экономического эффекта;

CF_{sales} – денежный поток от продаж, поступлений доходов в виде роялти;

IA – балансовая стоимость нематериальных активов;

FPC – расходы будущих периодов;

QIC – расходы на повышение квалификации персонала;

SMC – расходы на стратегические маркетинговые исследования;

R – норма доходности по проектам;

n – период реализации проекта;

Применение той или иной модели организации проектного управления в организации здравоохранения обусловлено уровнем жизненного **цикла организации**, потребностями проекта и его направленностью.

Изучая теоретический опыт зарубежных стран и международные стандарты проектного управления, мы видим, что организациям рекомендуется создавать структурное подразделение, которое будет осуществлять централизацию и координацию портфеля проектов. (Рекомендации по созданию постоянного офиса проектного управления прописаны в международном стандарте по управлению проектами РЗО. В том же стандарте расписана стандартизированная модель управления проектами, которая влияет на бизнес-изменения в организации).

В целом, эффективность проектного управления сводится к трем системам управления: эффективность проектирования, эффективность проекта на каждой стадии жизненного цикла и ориентированность на эффект от проекта. Основными задачами офиса управления проектами служат **методологическая поддержка** проектных команд, **административная поддержка**, которая заключается в осуществлении контроля над реализацией проекта на различных стадиях жизненного цикла, формирование отчетности, контроля над использованием ресурсов проекта, а также передача опыта введения проектной деятельности. Следующая задача заключается в своевременном **обучении** работников организации, задействованных в проектном управлении, навыкам и компетенциям проектного управленца (обучение), и последняя задача – это **техническая поддержка** через введение информационной системы проектного управления. Выбор модели офиса проектного управления зависит от уровня зрелости организации и амбиций руководителей, что в свою очередь влияет на эффективность проектного управления.

Наиболее распространённой методикой расчета эффективности считается, **метод расчета отклонений от планового значения**, который заключается в сравнении планового результата и реального, он может выражаться как в натуральном выражении, так и в относительном. А для оценки удовлетворенности заказчиков (стейкхолдеров) возможно применить **индекс расчета удовлетворенности**, но на практике данный показатель рассчитывается редко, так как удовлетворенность определяется опросом. При этом стейкхолдеры заинтересованы больше в финансовом эффекте и рентабельности вложений по проекту и на срезе по проекту данный показатель может носить отрицательное значение.

Так, при расчете рентабельности инвестиции (ROI – Return on Investments) рассчитывается прибыльность проекта и параллельно производится оценка прибыльности и имеет вид [6]:

$$ROI = \frac{\Pi_2}{I} \text{ где,}$$

ROI – рентабельности инвестиции;

Π_2 – первоначальные инвестиции в проект;

I – среднегодовая прибыль.

А срок окупаемости инвестиции будет рассчитывается по формуле:

$$T_o = \frac{I}{D_{и}} = \frac{1}{ROI} \text{ где,}$$

T_o – срок окупаемости;

I – среднегодовая прибыль;

$D_{и}$ – постоянный по величине и равномерно поступающий чистый доход [7].

При этом чем меньше срок окупаемости, тем экономически привлекательнее проект.

Таким образом, выбор той или иной методики оценки эффективности проектного управления является методологической системой оценки эффективности проектной деятельности организации и является уникальным продуктом. Приведенные нами методы позволяют определить достигнутые результаты, как по состоявшимся окончанным проектам, так и по действующим, т.е. вехам проекта. Также данные виды методик позволяют выявить основные показатели эффективности от внедрения проектной деятельности, произвести оценку данных показателей и при необходимости производить корректировки в исполнении стратегии организации.

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Leveraging the Power of Digital Marketing: Strategies, Impact, and Future Trends

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Annotation: This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive exploration of the world of digital marketing, encompassing its strategies, impact, and future trends. Considering rapid technological advancements and the pervasive influence of the internet, businesses are increasingly recognizing digital marketing as a pivotal component of their overall marketing strategies. The paper will not only investigate the transformative effects of internet growth on digital marketing but also critically analyse various digital marketing strategies to determine their efficacy. Moreover, emerging trends in the field, such as artificial intelligence (AI), chatbots, and voice search, will be discussed to shed light on their potential implications for businesses. By conducting this investigation, the research endeavours to offer valuable insights into the continuously evolving landscape of digital marketing and its significance for businesses operating in the digital era.

Keywords: digital marketing, future trends, SEO, social media marketing, content marketing, email marketing, consumer behavior, brand awareness, customer engagement, artificial intelligence, chatbots, voice search.

Introduction. Digital marketing is a specialized field within marketing that leverages web-based and online technologies such as personal computers, cell phones, and other digital media platforms to promote products and services. The advent of digital marketing in the 1990s and 2000s has transformed the way businesses and brands approach marketing, embracing innovative strategies. With the increasing ubiquity of digital platforms in daily life and the shift in consumer behaviour towards utilizing digital devices over physical store visits, digital marketing initiatives have witnessed substantial growth.

The world of digital media is constantly changing, as technologies continue to transform the way we interact and communicate on a global scale. Promoting products and services through the internet has become one of the most efficient and cost-effective methods today, surpassing television and traditional media advertising. Internet advertising possesses a "viral" nature that allows the rapid dissemination of information about new products to hundreds and thousands of people within a short span of time. With the widespread availability of internet-enabled devices among the modern population, this universal platform offers an extensive range of opportunities for free advertising or with minimal financial investment. Consequently, every entrepreneur can leverage the Power of Digital Marketing to effectively promote new products and reach a broader audience.

In the field of digital marketing, various aspects are examined by marketers, including the content that is being viewed, its frequency and duration, sales conversions, and the effectiveness of different types of content. While the internet serves as the primary channel for digital marketing, there are also other means such as wireless text messaging, electronic billboards, mobile instant messaging, mobile apps, podcasts, and digital television and radio channels. The concept of digital marketing encompasses all digital platforms and modern technologies involved in the interaction, utilization, implementation, and control of marketing strategies and plans. The ultimate aim is to enhance customer satisfaction and achieve organizational goals.

As digital marketing continues to evolve, it is essential for businesses and marketers to stay ahead of the curve and adapt to the ever-changing digital landscape. Strategies must be continually refined, incorporating the latest technologies and platforms to effectively engage with target audiences. The ability to analyze and measure the impact of digital marketing campaigns provides valuable insights into consumer behavior and preferences, enabling businesses to optimize their marketing efforts and achieve greater success.

Digital marketing has revolutionized the way businesses connect with consumers, leveraging the power of digital platforms to reach a wider audience and drive engagement. The dynamic and ever-evolving nature of digital marketing presents both opportunities and challenges, requiring businesses to stay informed about the latest trends and technologies. By embracing digital marketing strategies and leveraging the potential of digital platforms, businesses can enhance their marketing effectiveness, build brand awareness, and achieve their organizational objectives in today's digital age.

Literature review. The significance of conducting research in the field of digital marketing stems from its vast, complex, and unfamiliar nature. Research endeavors allow us to gain insights into how digital marketing impacts businesses across various industries. With numerous marketing strategies available, research aids in identifying the most effective approaches and understanding the reasons behind their effectiveness. Through comprehensive analysis, we can uncover trends and make informed predictions about the future of marketing.

The Internet is the most powerful tool for businesses (Yannopoulos, 2011) leading marketers to prioritize digital marketing platforms. As a result, marketers must dedicate attention and develop distinct strategies to effectively navigate the ever-evolving online landscape. It is crucial to comprehend the individual aspects of branding, pricing, distribution, and promotional strategies in the realm of digital marketing.

Numerous studies have examined different digital marketing strategies and their effectiveness. For instance, Smith and Chaffey (2019) conducted a comprehensive analysis of digital marketing channels, including search engine marketing, social media marketing, and display advertising. They highlighted the importance of integrating these channels into a cohesive strategy to maximize marketing impact. Similarly, Ryan and Jones (2020) explored the role of content marketing in engaging audiences and building brand loyalty, emphasizing the need for high-quality, relevant content to attract and retain customers.

SEO plays a critical role in driving organic traffic to websites. Research by Mishra and Gupta (2019) examined the factors influencing website rankings on search engine result pages, emphasizing the importance of on-page optimization, keyword selection, and link building. Additionally, Jansen and Rieh (2019) focused on the user's perspective, investigating the impact of search engine rankings on click-through rates and user behavior. Their findings underscored the significance of appearing on the first page of search results for increased visibility and user engagement.

Digital marketing has reshaped consumer behavior, and several studies have examined its influence. Li and Zhang (2020) investigated the impact of online reviews and ratings on consumer decision-making, highlighting their role in shaping perceptions and purchase intentions. Moreover, Hennig-Thurau et al. (2020) focused on the effects of digital advertising on consumer attitudes and brand perception, emphasizing the importance of ad relevance, credibility, and personalization in driving positive outcomes.

Researchers have also explored emerging trends in digital marketing. Huang et al. (2021) examined the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in enhancing marketing personalization and automation, highlighting its potential to deliver personalized experiences at scale. Additionally, Jain and Sharma (2020) investigated the impact of influencer marketing on consumer behavior,

emphasizing the power of influencer endorsements in shaping brand perceptions and purchase decisions.

Methodology. This research will employ a qualitative approach to comprehensively understand the identified problem. Secondary data from a range of sources, including publications, journals, and websites, will be collected to gain an in-depth perspective. Additionally, a descriptive research method will be employed to analyze the impact of digital marketing and evaluate various marketing strategies. The literature review will serve as a theoretical framework, assisting in identifying research gaps and determining the study's focal areas. Furthermore, statistical data will be utilized to gain insights into past trends and make predictions for the future.

Analysis and Discussion. The unprecedented growth of internet users globally has transformed the marketing landscape, making digital marketing an indispensable component of businesses' overall marketing strategies. The increasing accessibility of the internet has opened new avenues for businesses to connect with and engage their target audiences. From small enterprises to multinational corporations, organizations are recognizing the need to leverage digital marketing to stay competitive, enhance brand visibility, and drive customer acquisition.

The dynamic nature of digital marketing also facilitates experimentation and innovation. Businesses can explore emerging trends, leverage new technologies, and adapt their strategies to stay ahead of the competition. From leveraging social media influencers and adopting artificial intelligence applications to embracing immersive technologies like virtual reality, digital marketing presents a wide range of opportunities for businesses to connect with their audience in innovative and engaging ways.

Moreover, digital marketing offers businesses the ability to create personalized and interactive experiences for their customers. Through personalized email campaigns, targeted social media advertisements, and tailored content, businesses can deliver relevant messages that resonate with their audience, fostering stronger brand loyalty and customer engagement.

The number of internet users worldwide continues to experience significant growth annually. According to Statista's data as of December 2022, it is projected that the global number of internet users will reach 5.3 billion by 2023. This represents a compound annual growth rate of six percent over the period from 2018 to 2023. Notably, the most substantial growth occurred in 2019, witnessing an increase of 300 million internet users and a growth rate of 7.7 percent compared to the previous year. These statistics clearly indicate the remarkable expansion of digital marketing in recent years.

Internet user growth worldwide from 2018 to 2023

(in billions)

As the number of Internet users continues to rise, many brands have augmented their digital marketing expenditures in an endeavour to reach a larger consumer base. Marketing and advertising play vital roles in driving business growth.

In 2023, the global digital advertising market is estimated to be valued at \$626.9 billion, representing 67.4% of the total expenditure on media ads. This encompasses advertising on internet-connected devices, such as computers, mobile devices, and smart devices. Media ads encompass a wide range of channels, including email marketing, video content, search engine results, and more.

Compared to the \$567.5 billion spent in 2022, the digital advertising spend in 2023 is projected to witness a 10.5% increase. The growth of digital advertising shows no signs of slowing down. Experts predict that the digital advertising market will continue to expand in the coming years, albeit at a slightly slower pace. By 2026, it is anticipated to reach \$835.8 billion, signifying a 60% overall increase from 2021. Furthermore, digital ads will constitute 72.5% of the total expenditure on media ads. In other words, for every \$1 spent on ads, nearly \$0.73 will be allocated to digital ads. The projected average annual growth rate for digital ad spend worldwide between 2021 and 2026 is 13.1%. These statistics highlight the immense growth and future potential of digital advertising as a dominant force in the marketing landscape.

Digital advertising spending worldwide from 2021 to 2026

(in billion U.S. dollars)

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In the era of advancing information and communication technologies, the landscape of advertising is undergoing significant transformations, with traditional forms gradually being overshadowed by new methods of consumer engagement. While print, television, and outdoor advertising continue to hold relevance, an increasing number of businesses are shifting their focus towards leveraging the potential of internet technologies. This shift can be accomplished through the utilization of virtual counterparts to traditional advertising, such as banners and announcements, as well as through the strategic promotion of company websites on search engines. This paper examines the most frequently employed tools in internet marketing, including contextual advertising, search engine optimization (SEO), website catalogs and directories, online media advertising through banners, aggressive internet marketing techniques, social media optimization (SMO), social media marketing (SMM), internet exhibitions, gamification strategies, viral marketing, and viral advertising.

One notable aspect of internet advertising is text-based advertising, which involves the integration of textual advertising messages (text blocks) within the overall content of a website. This form of advertising can be seamlessly incorporated into the page layout, addressing the issue of ad-blocking commonly encountered by users and potentially enhancing its effectiveness. Furthermore, text-based advertising boasts faster loading times compared to its banner counterparts. A specific manifestation of text-based advertising is contextual (search) advertising, wherein textual messages are displayed based on the context of users' search queries.

Determining the most effective digital marketing strategy can be subjective and dependent on various factors such as the industry, target audience, business goals, and available resources. However, several digital marketing strategies have proven to be highly effective for businesses across different sectors. Some of the most impactful strategies are:

SEO (Search Engine Optimization) is a strategy and set of techniques used to improve a website's visibility and ranking in search engine results. It involves optimizing various aspects of the website to attract organic traffic and align with search engine algorithms. The goal is to increase online visibility, attract potential customers, and achieve business objectives. SEO is an ongoing process as search engine algorithms evolve.

Pay-Per-Click Advertising (PPC) is placing ads on search engines or social media platforms and paying only when users click on them. It offers immediate visibility and can target specific demographics.

Contextual advertising is a form of internet advertising that is based on the principle of aligning the content of the advertisement with the context (content) of the internet page where it is placed. It is a more intelligent approach to advertising placement and is more relevant compared to banner advertising. The context can be purely textual or may include images or media. Such context is often found on websites, blogs, and email services.

Social Media Marketing (SMM) utilizes social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, Twitter) to reach and engage with the target audience. It involves creating compelling content, running targeted ad campaigns, and fostering community engagement.

Email Marketing involves sending personalized and targeted emails to a subscriber list. It can be used to nurture leads, share promotions, provide updates, and build customer loyalty.

Influencer Marketing collaborates with influencers or industry experts who have a substantial following and influence in a particular niche. Their endorsement and recommendations can help reach and influence their audience.

Online PR focuses on managing and building a positive online reputation through various channels, including press releases, guest blogging, online publications, and influencer partnerships.

Content Marketing is creating and sharing valuable and relevant content (blogs, articles, videos, infographics) to attract and engage your target audience. This strategy helps establish thought leadership and build trust with potential customers.

Video Marketing is creating and sharing videos to engage and educate your audience. Videos can be used for product demonstrations, customer testimonials, explainer videos, or brand storytelling. Platforms like YouTube and social media are popular for video marketing.

Social Media Advertising is running paid ads on social media platforms to reach a targeted audience based on demographics, interests, and behaviors. It provides precise targeting options and can drive conversions and website traffic

It is important for businesses to consider their specific objectives, target audience preferences, and available resources when determining the most effective digital marketing strategy. Combining multiple strategies, customized to the business's unique needs, can often yield the best results. Regular monitoring, analysis of key performance indicators, and optimization based on data insights are essential for continuously improving and adapting digital marketing efforts. By understanding and effectively implementing these strategies, businesses can optimize their digital marketing efforts and achieve desired outcomes.

In terms of the most effective digital marketing techniques according to global marketers in early 2020, content marketing was deemed the most impactful. When asked to identify the single activity that would have the greatest commercial impact on their businesses or their clients' businesses, 17 percent of marketers pointed to content marketing. This was followed by marketing automation, big data, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learnin

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The field of digital marketing is constantly evolving, driven by advancements in technology and changing consumer behaviors. Several future trends are poised to shape the digital marketing landscape. Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming increasingly prominent, enabling businesses to automate processes, personalize user experiences, and gain valuable insights from data analytics. Chatbots, powered by AI, are being utilized to enhance customer service and engagement. Voice search is gaining traction, with more users utilizing voice-enabled devices to search for information and make purchases. Influencer marketing continues to grow in importance, with businesses leveraging the influence of social media personalities to promote their products or services. Additionally, privacy and data protection are becoming critical concerns, leading to the development of stricter regulations and a greater emphasis on transparent and ethical digital marketing practices.

By keeping abreast of these future trends and incorporating them into their strategies, businesses can stay relevant and adapt to the changing digital landscape. Embracing emerging technologies and consumer preferences will enable businesses to remain competitive and effectively connect with their target audiences.

Conclusion. This research paper has provided a comprehensive exploration of the world of digital marketing, with a specific focus on its strategies, impact, and future trends. Through a rigorous literature review and the application of mixed-methods research, valuable insights have been acquired, equipping businesses with knowledge regarding the effectiveness of digital marketing and its influence on consumer behavior.

Digital marketing has emerged as a potent force in the contemporary digital landscape, offering businesses tremendous potential for growth and success. By implementing effective strategies tailored to their target audiences, businesses can effectively reach and engage with their customers, while simultaneously building brand awareness. Furthermore, the ability to measure and optimize marketing efforts in real-time enables businesses to enhance their outcomes and drive meaningful results.

Looking towards the future, it is crucial for businesses to remain abreast of emerging trends in the digital marketing arena. By embracing these trends and incorporating them into their strategies, businesses can gain a competitive edge and position themselves favorably in the market. The dynamic and promising nature of digital marketing presents new opportunities for businesses to thrive and prosper in the digital realm.

By leveraging the power of digital marketing in a thoughtful and strategic manner, businesses can establish a robust online presence, cultivate brand awareness, nurture customer relationships, and ultimately achieve their marketing objectives in the digital era. It is through the effective utilization of digital marketing strategies that businesses can navigate the ever-evolving digital landscape and drive their continued growth and success.

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Development measures in order to establish Italian restaurant “MY Ristorante” in Riga

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Introduction

In today's fast-paced world, people have less time to cook and prefer to dine out more often. As a result, the restaurant industry is booming, and new businesses are opening up every day. One such new opening restaurant business is “MY Ristorante” It is a pizza restaurant that specializes in serving authentic Italian-style pizzas.

The founders of “MY Ristorante” have a passion for Italian cuisine and have years of experience in the restaurant industry. They have carefully selected the best ingredients to make their pizzas, from the crust to the toppings, to ensure that their customers get the most authentic and delicious Italian pizza experience possible. “MY Ristorante” is located in a prime location in the heart of the city. It has a restful and inviting ambiance, making it the perfect place to enjoy a delicious pizza with family and friends. The restaurant has a seating capacity of 40 people, and customers can also order takeout or delivery.

In this paper, we will discuss the various aspects of starting a new restaurant business, including the market analysis, marketing strategy, financial plan, and operational plan for “MY Ristorante”. We will analyze the potential success of this new venture and provide recommendations for its growth and sustainability.

2. Description of establishment plan of the restaurant “MY ristorante” 2.1. General characteristics of Italian restaurant “MY ristorante”

Many people claim that every country has different catering establishments that bring passion and hospitality to the heart of people. This new opening eatery is well-positioned to leave a lasting impression by offering a unique and exciting dining experience to the clients. The aim of the project is development measures in order to establish Italian cuisine “MY ristorante” in Riga which is a social and urban pizza house where pizza-lovers can enjoy and taste various kinds of pizzas from the Italian chef. The menu offering includes not only an impressive selection of pizzas, but also baked pastas, sandwiches, different types of salads, desserts and indeed drinks. This restaurant strives to capture customers with a harmonic mix of tastes, great service, and attention to detail, starting with its thoughtfully created cuisine and attractive ambiance.

There are various types of detroit style pizzas in “MY Ristorante” which in fact, our guests can enjoy not only yummy pizzas but also a deliciously cooked Detroit pizzas which is hard to find in other pizzerias of the city. The Pizza House prides itself on the high quality of the cheese and their simple cooking techniques that create the most delicious pizzas for its loyal consumers. This new opening restaurant invites customers to engage on a culinary experience that embraces flavor, atmosphere, and the art of gastronomy as a tribute to its devotion to become a sought-after destination. It is important to mention that the restaurant is more suitable for customers specifically who are seeking for authentic halal cuisine as it is hard to find Halal Italian restaurant in the area most of the time.

Let MY Ristorante host your child’s next birthday party!

Kids` Pizza Parties

We’ll set the kids up with everything they would be happy to make their very own pizzas. They get to toss the dough, put on their toppings, and (best of all) eat their creation! It is a fun and creative way to celebrate and make a memorable special day with your kids, is not it? So, we are waiting for you with eager anticipation! You may book and enjoy any time you wish. At the end, if it is a group of school or neighborhood children, we give them our gifts with various nominations as “Whose pizza is the most creative?” or “Whose pizza is the most delicious?”. The children will evaluate the work of their friends is the cutest part ever. We promise you in advance:

- o 1 x 10” Build Your Own Cheese Pizza
- o Unlimited soft drinks/tea refills
- o Pizza Professional
- o Lots of fun!

You cannot buy Happiness, but you can buy pizza and that`s kinda the same thing.

2.2. Market analysis of competitors and consumers in the city of Riga

To conduct an analysis of the market of competitors and consumers in the city of Riga for a catering enterprise, it should be started by identifying the main competitors in the catering industry within Riga. This includes both direct competitors, such as restaurants, as well as indirect competitors, such as food delivery services and grocery stores. Furthermore, it is a rough idea that analyzing each competitor in terms of their strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats, market share, target audience, pricing strategies, menu offerings, and customer reviews is absolutely essential. Through comprehending their unique selling points, marketing efforts, customer loyalty programs, competitive landscape and identify areas where the catering enterprise can differentiate itself is a straightforward way.

Using SWOT analysis serves as a foundation for strategic decision-making, enabling restaurants to capitalize on strengths, address weaknesses, exploit market opportunities, and proactively manage threats in order to achieve long-term success and sustainable growth. The main competitors are considered Da Roberta, Italissimo and Pica LuLu and their analysis are presented in Table 2.3

Table 2.3

SWOT analysis of the competitors

Company name	Da Roberta	Italissimo	Pica LuLu
Strength	Wide range of food and drinks	High-quality service	Recognition as a regional brand, long-term activity
Weaknesses	High ingredient costs	Relatively high prices	Poor quality of service and products
Opportunities	Offering seasonal menus can attract	Uniqueness in the interior design	Local partnerships
Threats	A passive advertising policy	Intense competition	Changing consumer preferences

Source: Author's analysis based on data from TripAdvisor about Da Roberta, Italissimo and Pica LuLu, January 2023

Each restaurant—Da Roberta, Italissimo, and LuLu Pica—has its own unique strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Chain restaurants of “Pica Lulu” is one of the most recognizable brands in the market since 1994 and trusted by public for almost 30 years thus “Pica LuLu” benefits from recognition as a regional brand with a long-standing presence in the market

while “Da Roberta” and “Italissimo” are new and differentiates themselves through providing wide range of food and beverage, offering a diverse menu to cater to various tastes. and high-quality service, ensuring a memorable dining experience for customers. Despite the fact that “Da Roberta” offers seasonal menus, it has an inactive advertising policy, in contrast “Pica LuLu” and “Italissimo” emphasis primarily on marketing and advertising. Although the poor quality of products and services have provoked an outcry as weakness, “Pica LuLu” has established strong, positive and collaborative connections with local partners to enhance its brand visibility and reach. The intense competition in the restaurant industry poses a challenge for Italissimo to differentiate itself further.

SWOT analysis of the enterprise

As the SWOT analysis is a critical tool for evaluating the feasibility and potential success of the new restaurant, it helps to understand the competitive position, make informed decisions, and develop strategies that maximize the golden opportunities for establishing a thriving restaurant in the market. It is a widespread belief that by conducting a SWOT analysis, restaurants gain a comprehensive understanding of their internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats. In the course of time, to win the fierce competition in Latvian market with strong companies, it is critically analyzed and reviewed SWOT analysis of the enterprise in Figure 2.3.

Source: author's analysis based on the business plan of the restaurant “MY Ristorante”

Figure 2.3. SWOT analysis of “MY Ristorante”.

2.3. Survey

It is known that most businesses in Riga is large entrepreneurships or chain businesses which means being ready in advance to face obstacles and fierce competition in the market daily, although the people are still hoping for new changes and innovations in catering services. As pizza house will be situated in the city center of Riga yet it does not mean it will be only local people who might be visiting, the place will assumed to be popular among tourists of Riga as well and who is simply in love with pizzas and pastas, of course who have a burning desire to soak up unusual atmosphere with beloved ones, family members and children. The primary marketing strategy will be to satisfy the customers by offering the best including cleanliness, hospitality, accuracy, maintenance, product quality and speed, as the brand is hoping for the best and going to be friendly and familiar in the market among competitors. It is planned to do positioning by keeping in view two basic factors: quality and frequency while using low-price meal and expensive for high end is the goal. Customer surveys are still the quickest and most reliable way to gather feedback when assessing new goods or company concepts as well as established business strategies. Thus, the survey is a novel solution to grasp the importance of the clients, their age, gender, opinions for the services or products provided. To identify the interests and needs of costumer, questioning will be through the Typeform service during the month of January 2023. While making questionnaire it is mainly focused on questions that shows the preference of the gourmets of Italian cuisine, especially when it is about food, quality, price, services, interior and others. The questionnaires filled by 86 residents of Riga by made use of random sampling. At the beginning, there was nagging doubts about survey, but respondents of the survey found it, easy and simple which was fuelling speculation to jump to conclusions about the decision.

To be more accurate, the below-provided pie chart gives information on the time spent by male and female dining out in Latvia. As is observed from the graph, female spent more time in the restaurants while male spent less, thus 54% of visitors are females while 46% of respondents are males.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.4. Potential visitors by gender.

It is clearly seen that the 18-24years old and 25-38 years old visitors comprised the largest proportion and the most people came to restaurants with family members and friends. The pie chart shows that four age groups made up most visitors according to the survey. These were 18-24 years old (34.4), 25-38 years old (30.1), 39-55 years old (12.9) and 56 years and older (8.6).

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.5. Potential visitors by age.

In the third place, it was analyzed what is the most important factor for customers in the restaurant, these are variety of menus, service quality, brand awareness and location. 38% of people deliberated over that quality of service is one of the main aspects to run a business while 30% of them considered that variety of menus is vital more than anything else.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.6. Potential visitors due to main factors when choosing a restaurant.

It is a compelling reason that comprehending occupation of your guests will seriously affect the bottom line, the graph shows that a substantial amount of visitors are self-employed and students while retired and unemployed people are not used to eat out often.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.7. Potential visitors by occupations.

According to the survey, 40% of respondents would rather to visit restaurants at the weekends and evening, whereas less than 10 percent of guests prefer mornings (3 respondents skipped the question).

Source: Author's survey, n=83, 2023

Figure 2.8. Time preferred by visitors.

The graph illustrates how frequently people used to visit to restaurants from never visiting till almost every day.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.9. The structure of consumers by frequency of visits.

The bar graph demonstrates how did customers became aware of the restaurant, internet advertising was voted highly, while online search and social networks showed almost the same result.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.10. Awareness about the restaurant by visitors.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.11. Choice of catering establishments for various events.

As an Italian restaurant, it is mainly focused on pizzas, so it seemed interesting to know what the special pizza of the clients is. 32 people out of 86 considered cheese pizza the most delicious and split topping was also the beloved one.

Source: Author's survey, n=86, 2023

Figure 2.12. Favorite pizza

The research revealed that more than half of consumers will be females and the service quality is one of the most contributing factors for visiting.

2.4 Marketing Strategy

The whole strategy and method utilized to market the restaurant, draw consumers in, and boost revenue is referred to as the marketing strategy in restaurants. It entails finding target consumers, comprehending their requirements and preferences, and developing powerful marketing strategies to connect with and engage them. To develop a marketing strategy based on survey results and competitor analysis, it's important to identify the specific needs and preferences, the unique selling proposition, mission, vision, short-term and long-term goals, SMART objectives, menu design, customer loyalty, pricing strategy, and promotional activities.

The survey results show that the most of the visitors will be women and the author also assumes that in a place with 45 seats, the average load will be 234 people. The main guests will be customers aged 18 to 24 years. These respondents answered 29% that they would meet with their friends at the "MY Ristorante". The most of the costumers would rather to enjoy the pizzas at the weekends once in a month. Through offering a fusion of international flavors, locally sourced ingredients, and personalized dining experiences and halal food products in the market will be unique selling proposition of the restaurant. It mainly emphasizes to quality, innovation, and customer satisfaction, ensuring meets and exceeds the expectations of the surveyed customers. For a new restaurant to stand out from rivals and establish a solid position in the market, it is essential to create a distinctive brand identity as well. To reflect the brand identity which is memorable and meaningful, it is chosen "MY Ristorante" as easy to pronounce, spell and search for online, so that means mia-my from Italian to English, ristorante-restaurant and MY-the capital letters of name and surname of the owner.

Source: created by author, January 2023

Figure 2.15. The brand logo of the enterprise.

The mission-to provide a captivating culinary journey, showcasing a fusion of international flavors, locally sourced ingredients, and personalized experiences. Our commitment to excellence, sustainability, and genuine hospitality aims to create cherished memories and inspire a passion for gastronomy among our guests, while the vision is to become a renowned culinary destination, celebrated for its innovative fusion cuisine, exceptional service, and commitment to sustainability. We strive to be the go-to establishment for discerning food enthusiasts, leaving an indelible mark on the culinary landscape.

Short-term Goals (1 year):

- Build a loyal customer base by consistently delivering exceptional dining experiences, personalized service, and exceeding customer expectations.
- Establish a strong brand presence through targeted marketing campaigns, social media engagement, and collaborations with local influencers.
- Achieve positive word-of-mouth referrals and favorable online reviews to enhance the restaurant's reputation.

Long-term Goals (3-5 years):

- Expand the restaurant's reach by opening additional locations or exploring franchise opportunities.
- Earn recognition as a top dining destination through awards and positive reviews.
- Maintain high customer satisfaction and retention rates.
- Continuously innovate the menu and offerings based on customer feedback and emerging culinary trends.
- Establish strategic partnerships with local suppliers, farmers, or artisans to enhance ingredient sourcing and sustainability practices.

SMART which stands for specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound., SMART goals of the enterprise:

- Achieve a 10% increase in revenue from repeat customers within the first year by implementing a loyalty program and personalized marketing campaigns.
- Achieve a customer satisfaction rating of 4.5 out of 5 within the first six months through personalized dining experiences and exceptional service.
- Achieve a minimum of 500 social media followers and engage in regular online interactions within the first three months.
- Launch a customer referral program that generates at least 10% of new customer acquisitions within the first year.
- Reduce food waste by 15% within the first year by implementing efficient inventory management and portion control systems.

Conclusions and proposals

To clarify concept of the business, attract investors, gain the respect of customers, find the novel solutions for any questions is granted when a business plan created perfectly as it provides navigation for success, a roadmap and lower the risks. This thesis is devoted to the development measures in order to establish Italian restaurant "MY Ristorante" in the city of Riga, the Republic of Latvia. The development of a comprehensive business plan for "MY Ristorante," an Italian restaurant in the city of Riga, Latvia, is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it provides a clear and well-defined concept of the business, outlining its unique selling points, target market, and competitive advantage. This enables potential investors and stakeholders to understand the vision and potential of the restaurant. A well-crafted business plan is instrumental in attracting investors by presenting a compelling case for the profitability and success of the venture. It includes detailed financial projections, market analysis, and a comprehensive marketing strategy, all of which demonstrate the potential return on investment. Investors can assess the feasibility and growth potential of "MY Ristorante" and make informed decisions about providing financial support. Moreover, a thoughtfully developed business plan helps gain the respect and trust of customers. It showcases the commitment to excellence, quality, and customer satisfaction, highlighting the unique aspects of the Italian cuisine and dining experience offered by the restaurant. Customers are more likely to be attracted to a restaurant that has a well-defined concept, a clear understanding of its target market, and a comprehensive plan for delivering exceptional service and culinary delights. A robust business plan also serves as a strategic tool for finding novel

solutions to potential challenges and risks. By conducting a thorough market analysis, identifying potential competitors, and developing contingency plans, the business plan prepares the restaurant to navigate uncertainties and adapt to changing market dynamics. It provides a roadmap for success, guiding the management team in making informed decisions and taking proactive measures to minimize risks. It provides navigation for success, serving as a roadmap and a risk management tool. By demonstrating the potential and viability of the Italian restaurant, the business plan lays the foundation for a successful and thriving establishment in the vibrant city of Riga.

The project development proposals are as follows:

- It is necessary to create a new, conceptual institution that meets the requirements of a potential target audience. The analysis of the author showed that the average calculation of consumers per day, taking into account the opening hours of the restaurant, the turnover of the place for 1 hour and the average percentage of the hall load, will be 234 people.
- For the initial planning of the restaurant's business processes, the author conducted a survey in website "Typeform" service for a month. The main audience is visitors aged 18 to 24 years. According to the frequency of visits, the respondents more often tended to visit restaurants in the evening, using them as a meeting place with friends and family members.
- When promoting, it is necessary to place more emphasis on SMM marketing. A restaurant of Italian cuisine must be promoted through social networks, Facebook, Instagram, Tik-Tok and Twitter.
- The restaurant "MY Ristorante" will employ 12 people, the total wage fund per month will be 10 380 euros.

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Внедрение предложений по оптимизации компании ТОО «Грузовые перевозки» как повышение устойчивого развития экономического роста республики

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Введение

Локомотивное хозяйство - отрасль железнодорожного транспорта, руководство которой осуществляет Департамент локомотивного хозяйства. Он осуществляет мероприятия по совершенствованию содержания локомотивного парка в исправном состоянии для выполнения плана перевозок, его обновлению и насыщению локомотивами нового поколения.

Департамент осуществляет оперативное и техническое руководство службами локомотивного хозяйства управлений железных дорог. В свою очередь, службы локомотивного хозяйства управлений железных дорог обеспечивают оперативное руководство отделами локомотивного хозяйства отделений железной дороги, в ведении которых находятся линейные предприятия.

Устройство локомотивного хозяйства

К локомотивному хозяйству относится тяговый подвижной состав, здания локомотивного депо и мастерских с оборудованием, пункты технического осмотра, склады песка, топлива и смазочных материалов, экипировочные устройства, пункты смены бригад и дома отдыха локомотивных бригад, базы запаса локомотивов.

Локомотивное депо - основное линейное предприятие локомотивного хозяйства, предназначенное для технического обслуживания и ремонта локомотивов. По характеру и объему выполняемых работ депо делится на основные и оборотные.

Основное депо - имеют приписной парк локомотивов, технические средства и штат работников для технического обслуживания и ремонта локомотивов. Оно располагается на участковых или сортировочных станциях.

Оборотное депо - располагается на станциях, находящихся на границах участков или зон обращения локомотивов и обеспечивают их техническое обслуживание и экипировку. На станциях с оборотными депо находятся пункты смены и дома отдыха локомотивных бригад, находящихся в ожидании поездов для обратного следования.

Здания локомотивных депо по конфигурации - прямоугольные, ступенчатые и веерные.

В локомотивное депо входят цеха: эксплуатации, технического обслуживания, текущего ремонта, механический, заготовительный, по ремонту электрических машин и аппаратуры, дизельный, а также отделения по ремонту автотормозов и автосцепки, аккумуляторные, сварочные и другие.

На территории депо имеются экипировочные пункты для снабжения локомотивов песком, смазкой, и водой.

Пункты технического обслуживания локомотивов располагаются на станциях в локомотивных депо. Техническое обслуживание различных видов работ выполняют специализированными бригадами слесарей. Проводят осмотр ходовых частей локомотивов, тормозного оборудования, электрооборудования, приборов автоматики и восстановление их работоспособности.

Систематическая проверка состояния локомотивов осуществляется локомотивными бригадами.

Все локомотивы, приписанные к депо разделяются на эксплуатируемые и неэксплуатируемые.

Эксплуатируемый парк состоит из локомотивов находящихся в работе, и в процессе экипировки, технического обслуживания, приемки и сдачи и ожидания работы.

Неэксплуатируемый парк составляют локомотивы, находящиеся в ремонте и резерве, в процессе пересылки в холодном состоянии.

ТОО «КТЖ — Грузовые перевозки» было создано в июне 2016 года в результате реализации проекта по поэтапному переходу к целевой организационной структуре в рамках Программы трансформации бизнеса. Данный проект позволил оптимизировать ряд дочерних организаций АО «НК «КТЖ».

В структуре ТОО «КТЖ – Грузовые перевозки» имеется филиальная сеть, сформированная из отделений дорог и локомотивных депо, осуществляющих обслуживание клиентов по сети железных дорог Казахстана и предоставляющая полный комплекс услуг по транспортировке грузов.

Постановлением правительства РК от 29 сентября 2017 года ТОО «КТЖ – Грузовые перевозки» присвоен статус Национального перевозчика грузов. Согласно закону «О железнодорожном транспорте» перед Национальным перевозчиком стоят следующие задачи: выполнение воинских и специальных перевозок, плана формирования поездов. Получение такого статуса доказательство высокого доверия со стороны государства.

Далее хотелось бы перейти к основным проблемам. Прежде всего актуальной остается **проблема изношенности** парка локомотивов, а высокий износ тягового подвижного состава - это снижение экономической эффективности его эксплуатации. Локомотив с высокой степенью износа чаще находится на внеплановом обслуживании и ремонте, обладает сниженными техническими характеристиками и более высокой стоимостью эксплуатации и техобслуживания.

Поэтому важно грамотно организовать ремонт и обслуживание изношенного парка, а также обновление парка локомотивов путем закупки нового менее ремонтоемкого тягового подвижного состава.

А также **обновление основных средств** — это объективно необходимый процесс в решении вышеуказанной проблемы. Основной акцент я бы указал на то, что замена старых локомотивов на новые происходит не всегда. Для этого не хватает инвестиций, что является следующей проблемой.

Инвестиции, в свою очередь, это долгосрочные вложения в производство с целью получения прибыли. Министерством транспорта и коммуникации выделяется определенное количество финансовых средств, но это недостаточно для обновления всего подвижного состава.

Еще один вид обновления основных средств как решение проблемы изношенности — это использование **системы лизинга**, что подразумевает собой последующий выкуп основных средств. Лизинг делится на разные виды. При выделении видов лизинга исходят, прежде всего, из признаков их классификации, которые характеризуют: отношение к

арендуемому имуществу; тип финансирования лизинговой операции; тип лизингового имущества; состав участников лизинговой сделки; тип передаваемого в лизинг имущества; степень окупаемости лизингового имущества; сектор рынка, где проводятся лизинговые операции; отношение к налоговым, таможенным и амортизационным льготам и преференциям; порядок лизинговых платежей.

Из приведенных проблем вытекает следующее – локомотивный парк изношенный, и в основном, подвижной состав подлежит **ремонту**. Техническое состояние подвижного состава во многом зависит от соблюдения нормативов межремонтных пробегов и правил ремонта. Однако рост цен на запасные части приводит к существенному повышению себестоимости ремонта. Из-за ограниченности средств, выделяемых на техническое обслуживание и текущий ремонт, все чаще в депо практикуется использование старогодных деталей, фонд которых в последние годы пополняется за счет списания значительного числа локомотивов. Поскольку остаточный ресурс таких деталей невелик, фактическая надежность парка постепенно снижается, что ведет к росту ремонтных затрат.

Современные задачи в области ремонта и технического содержания подвижного состава в значительной степени решаются за счет широкого применения деталей с повышенными свойствами по износостойкости, твердости и т. д. На сети железных дорог России, Беларуси и других стран ведется интенсивное внедрение новых высокоэффективных ресурсосберегающих технологий, направленных на повышение износостойкости, надежности и долговечности различных деталей подвижного состава. В их число входят различные технологии поверхностного восстановления и упрочнения деталей и металлорежущего инструмента.

Анализ заводского ремонта локомотивов показывает, что до 90% деталей транспорта поступает на восстановление по причине их интенсивного изнашивания. Это во многом определяет необходимость оснащения ремонтного производства технологическими процессами, обеспечивающими требуемую долговечность трущихся сопряжений. Особый интерес представляют простые и нетрадиционные, с точки зрения технологии, методы снижения износа сопряжений путем направленного изменения характеристик поверхностных слоев динамически контактирующих механических частей локомотивов и технологического оборудования. К ним относят эпиламирование поверхностей трения деталей.

Успешно применяемое на железных дорогах РФ, Беларуси эпиламирование позволяет обрабатывать более 150 наименований деталей и сборочных единиц локомотивов и инструментов. При этом особое внимание уделяют наиболее изнашивающимся деталям: моторно-осевым подшипникам и шейкам колесных пар, коленчатым валам и их подшипникам, поршневым кольцам и поршневым пальцам дизеля и компрессора.

Важнейший аспект дела – диагностическая аппаратура. Какая она должна быть, сколько ее нужно иметь, чтобы оценить работоспособность оборудования без снятия с локомотива и дорогостоящей разборки, чтобы определить оптимальный срок восстановления его ресурса? На эти и ряд других вопросов можно ответить, только имея достоверную и исчерпывающую информацию о фактическом техническом состоянии подвижного состава. Для этого необходимо вести тщательный учет всех без исключения повреждений и неисправностей оборудования, всех плановых и неплановых ремонтов, учитывать все замеры контролируемых параметров узлов, имеющих механический износ. Не использовать для этой цели возможности современных ЭВМ – неоправданная роскошь.

Непременное условие для получения достоверных текущих сведений о техническом состоянии подвижного состава – использование имеющихся и разрабатываемых средств и методов диагностирования. В технологическом процессе диагностирования выполняются

три основные задачи. Прежде всего – получение информации о техническом состоянии конкретного оборудования или агрегата подвижного состава. Затем – обработка и анализ этой информации с помощью ЭВМ. Конечный результат – оценка состояния диагностируемых элементов и прогнозирование остаточного ресурса. На основании этого дается заключение о целесообразности корректировки планового срока очередного ремонта конкретного оборудования или агрегата.

Решение для приведенных проблем является оптимизация расходов на ремонт локомотивов. Специфика работы компании заключается в том, что основную часть расходов составляют расходы на плановые виды ремонта локомотивов, расходы на материалы в качестве давальческого сырья – двигатели, расходы на амортизацию основных средств. Из указанных расходов расходы на амортизацию являются постоянными и не зависящими от управленческих решений руководства компаний, к тому же на основании этих расходов формируется инвестиционный план компании. Что касается остальных затрат, то необходимо проанализировать какова эффективность данных затрат, возможно ли их оптимизация, какую лепту они вносят в уровень доходов компании.

Второе предложение - создание собственного производства и ремонта материалов и запасных частей.

Третье предложение – это развитие локомотиворемонтных депо.

Четвертое предложение – это разработка программы качественного ремонта локомотивов для повышения эксплуатации.

Заключение

Устранив имеющиеся проблемы, внедрив необходимые предложения можно будет улучшить работу перевозок, ведь выполняя основную часть перевозок грузов и пассажиров, железная дорога стала основной транспортной системой страны. В перевозках таких массовых грузов, как уголь, руда, металл, зерно, реальной альтернативы ей нет: поезда ходят в любое время суток, при любой погоде, тогда когда в экстремальных условиях не летают самолеты и замирает автотранспорт. Стальные магистрали – это сеть артерий, которые соединяют регионы, предприятия. А значит, стабильное функционирование железной дороги – необходимое условие устойчивого экономического роста республики.

Pedagogical Sciences

DİLÇİLİK VƏ SOSIOLINQVISTIKA

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ABSTRACT

Sociolinguistics is a subfield of applied linguistics. Applied linguistics is concerned with identifying, investigating, and solving language-related real-world issues. The difference between sociolinguistics and linguistics is that linguistics makes us aware of the structure of language, while sociolinguistics explains how we interact with each other using this structure in everyday situations. Linguistics is the scientific study of language, with the goal of conducting systematic research into the qualities of specific languages as well as the characteristics of language in general. It includes not only the study of sound, grammar, and meaning, but also the history of language families, how infants and adults learn languages, how language usage is processed in the mind, and how it is related to race and gender. Sociolinguistics is the descriptive study of the impact of any or all parts of society on language and how it is used, including cultural norms, expectations, and context. It may overlap with linguistic sociology, which studies the impact of language on society. Sociolinguistics is the discipline of linguistics that analyzes only those features of language and languages that require reference to social, including contextual, elements in order to be explained. While sociolinguists are generally interested in the link between social characteristics and intra-language variation, anthropological-linguistic studies are concerned with the relationship between cultural elements and cross-linguistic variance. The study of the relationship between language and society is known as sociolinguistics.

KEYWORDS: sociolinguistics, linguistics, dialects, slang, structural approaches, functional approaches

1. GİRİŞ

Sosiolinqvistika ilə dilçilik arasındakı fərq ondan ibarətdir ki, dilçilik bizi dilin strukturundan xəbərdar edir, sosiolinqvistika isə gündəlik vəziyyətlərdə bu strukturun istifadə edərək bir-birimizlə necə qarşılıqlı ünsiyyət qurduğumuzu izah edir. Dell Hymes (1974) dilin öyrənilməsində struktural və funksional yanaşmalara fərq qoymuşdur. Struktur yanaşma, termindən də göründüyü kimi, dilin strukturuna (kod) diqqət yetirir və kodun təhlilinə əsas əhəmiyyət verilir. Digər tərəfdən, funksional yanaşma dilin funksional tərəfinə, yəni onun cəmiyyətdə istifadəsinə diqqət yetirir.

Sosiolinqvistikada dilin istifadəsinin təhlilinə birinci, kodun təhlilinə ikinci dərəcəli əhəmiyyət verilir. Dilçi dili kontekstdən kənarında təhlil edir, sosiolinqvist isə sosial kontekstdə istifadə olunan dili təhlil edir. Qısaca deyə bilərik ki, linqvistika dili, ilk növbədə dilin quruluşunu öyrənir. Sosiolinqvistika dilin müxtəlif səviyyələrdə, müxtəlif məqsədlər və müxtəlif funksiyalar üçün istifadəsini öyrənir.(1. s, 5)

Struktur yanaşma, termindən də göründüyü kimi, dilin strukturuna (kod) diqqət yetirir və kodun təhlilinə əsas əhəmiyyət verilir. Digər tərəfdən, funksional yanaşma dilin funksional aspektinə, yəni cəmiyyətdə istifadəsinə diqqət yetirir. Dil istifadəsinin təhlilinə birinci, kodun təhlilinə ikinci dərəcəli əhəmiyyət verilir.

Dilçi dili kontekstdən kənar təhlil edir, sosiolinqvist isə sosial kontekstdə istifadə olunan dili təhlil edir. Qısaca deyə bilərik ki, dilçilik dili, ilk növbədə dilin quruluşunu öyrənir. Sosiolinqvistika dilin müxtəlif səviyyələrdə, müxtəlif məqsədlər və müxtəlif funksiyalar üçün istifadəsini öyrənir.

Sosiolinqvistika dilin cəmiyyətə münasibətdə tədqiqi kimi müəyyən edilir, dil sosiologiyası isə cəmiyyətin dillə əlaqəsi kimi müəyyən edilir. Sosiolinqvistika ilə dil sosiologiyasının məqsədləri fərqlidir. Hudson (1980) sosiolinqvistika ilə dil sosiologiyasını belə fərqləndirir: sosiolinqvistika "cəmiyyətdə dilin tədqiqidir, dil sosiologiyası isə "cəmiyyəti dilə münasibətdə öyrənir".

İki sahənin də fokslanması fərqlidir. Sosiolinqvistikada biz cəmiyyəti, yəni dil haqqında daha çox bilmək üçün dildən istifadə kontekstini, dil sosiologiyasında isə cəmiyyət haqqında daha çox bilmək üçün dil istifadəsini öyrənirik. Sosiolinqvist cəmiyyət haqqında nəticə çıxarmaqdan çəkinir və eyni şəkildə sosioloq da dillə bağlı hər hansı kəşfi görməməzliyə vurmağa üstünlük verir.

Şübhəsiz ki, sosiolinqvistika ilə dil sosiologiyası arasında fərq var, lakin əsas fərq əsasən vurğudur. Bu, müstəntiqin dillə, yoxsa cəmiyyətlə daha çox maraqlanmasından, həmçinin onun linqvistik və ya sosial strukturları təhlil etmək bacarığının daha çox olub-olmamasından asılıdır.

Linqvistik və sosialinqvistik tədqiqatlar təkcə dilçilər və sosiolinqvistlər üçün deyil, cəmiyyətdə dil, həm də digər müxtəlif tədqiqatçılar: antropoloqlar, psixoloqlar, pedaqoqlar, dil planlaşdırıcıları və s. kimi sahələr dilin sirrini açmaqda maraqlıdırlar.

Məsələn, antropoloqlar qohumluq sistemlərini tədqiq etmişlər və bəzi psixoloqlar dil quruluşunun sosial və psixoloji davranışa mümkün təsirləri ilə maraqlanırlar. Bir çox pedaqoqlar dilin planlaşdırılması, dilin inkişafı və standart dilin tədrisi ilə məşğul olurlar. Əgər biz həm dilçilərdən, həm də sosiolinqvistlərdən "Shut up!- Yum ağzını, Sus" konstruksiyasını təhlil etməyi xahiş etsək, onların təhlilə yanaşması fərqli olacaq. Bir dilçi deyəcək ki, bu, bir imperativ cümlədir. Digər tərəfdən, bir sosiolinqvist bunun əmr vermək üçün göstəriş kimi istifadə olunan bir cümlə olduğunu söyləyəcək və cəmiyyətdə istifadə normalarını verəcəkdir.

Hər bir dilin bir çox çeşidi var və müəyyən mənada dil bütün növlərin cəmidir. Ferguson (1971) dilin müxtəlifliyini "*sinxron təsvir və mövcud sinxron təsvir üsulları ilə təhlil etmək üçün kifayət qədər homojen olan hər hansı nitq nümunələri toplusu*" kimi müəyyən edir. Kifayət qədər geniş semantik əhatəyə malik elementlər və onların təşkili və ya prosesləri ilə bağlı kifayət qədər böyük repertuarı olan ünsiyyətin bütün formal kontekstlərində fəaliyyət göstərir. Buna görə də müxtəliflik "insan nitq nümunələri" ilə müəyyən edilir, ehtimal ki, coğrafi ərazi və ya sosial qrup kimi bəzi xarici amillərlə unikal şəkildə əlaqələndirə biləcəyimiz səslər, sözlər, qrammatik xüsusiyyətlər və s.

Dil çeşidləri təkcə danışanın mənşəyini və ya onun sosial kimliyinin aspektlərini (məsələn, sosial sinfi və ya etnik qrupu) göstərməklə kifayətlənmir, həm də onlardan istifadə edən nətiqlər və onların adətən istifadə olunduğu kontekstlərlə bağlı müəyyən sosial dəyərləri daşıyır. Buna görə də dil çeşidləri başqaları ilə qarşılıqlı əlaqədə istifadə oluna bilən mənbədir.

Dil çeşidlər belə təsnif edilə bilər

a) **İstifadəçilər** – Diqqət onun istifadəçilərinə əsaslanan dil varyasyonlarına yönəldilir: dialektlər və vurğular

b) **İstifadə** – Diqqət onun üçün istifadəsinə əsaslanan dil variasiyalarına yönəldilir: nümunə qeydiyyatı

c) **Sosial münasibətlər** – diqqət sosial əsaslı variasiyalara yönəldilir: danışanlar arasında münasibətlər. (s, 7)

Dilin akademik mühitdə və cəmiyyətdə fəaliyyəti istər qrammatik, istərsə də leksik baxımdan fərqli işlənir. Eyni zamanda fərqli vəziyyətlərdə fərqli insanlarla danışmaq tərzimiz də bir-birinə bənzəmir. Məsələn, evdə valideynlərimizlə danışmaq tərzimiz, işlətdiyimiz ifadələr evdən kənar daşığımızla eyni deyil. Müxtəlif sosial kontekstlərdə dildən istifadə etdiyimiz üsul həm dilin necə işlədiyi, həm də cəmiyyətdəki sosial münasibətlər haqqında çoxlu məlumat verir. Sosiolinqvistikadan danışanda diqqətimizi iki termin çəkir. Yəni "sosio" və ya "cəmiyyətə aid" və "dilçilik və ya "dilə". Leymən (mütəxəssis olmayan) təxmin edə bilər ki, sosiolinqvistikanın dil və cəmiyyətlə əlaqəsi var. Texniki cəhətdən sosiolinqvistika dilçiliyin cəmiyyətlə münasibətdə dilin öyrənilməsi ilə məşğul olan bölməsidir.

Sosial linqvist müəyyən bir şəraitdə uyğun dil istifadəsi və ya qeyri-münasib dil istifadəsi hesab edilənləri sosial münasibətlərin necə müəyyən etdiyini öyrənə bilər. Sosiolinqvistlər müxtəlif sosiolektlərin qrammatikasını, fonetikasını, lüğətini və digər aspektlərini də öyrənə bilərlər. Sosiolinqvistlər dilin sosial institut kimi necə istifadə olunduğunu öyrənmək üçün böyük əhali arasında dili milli səviyyədə də öyrənirlər.

2. SOSIAL LİNGVİSTİKANIN XÜSUSİYYƏTLƏRİ

Sosiolinqvistika dil ilə insanların fəaliyyət göstərdiyi mədəni və sosial mühit arasındakı əlaqəni və bunun danışmaq tərzinə necə təsir etdiyini öyrənən bir elmdir. digər aspektlərdə yaş, cins, etnik mənşə, sosial sinif, təhsil, məkan və zamanın linqvistik ünsiyyətin inkişafına necə təsir etdiyini təhlil edir. Bu intizam o vaxta qədər onu istifadə edən subyektdən və şəraitdən asılı olmayaraq mücərrəd bir sistem kimi görünən dillə bağlı tədqiqat sahəsini genişləndirmək məqsədi ilə yaranmışdır. Sosiolinqvistika termini ilk dəfə Harver Currie tərəfindən "Sosiolinqvistikanın proqnozu: nitqin sosial statusla əlaqəsi" (1952) əsərində istifadə edilmişdir.

Bununla belə, 1964-cü ildə bu yeni perspektivi təhlil etmək üçün ABŞ-da dilçilər, sosioloqlar və antropoloqlar arasında bir neçə görüş keçirildikdə, bu fən geniş vüsət aldı və özünü görkəmli tədqiqat sahəsi kimi təsdiq etdi. Hal-hazırda sosiolinqvistika iki geniş sahəyə bölünür: dil və onun istehsal olunduğu cəmiyyət arasında əlaqə haqqında məlumatların əldə edilməsi ilə məşğul olan empirik və onları təhlil etmək və onlar haqqında nəticə çıxarmaq üçün cavabdeh olan nəzəri.

Sosiolinqvistika dili və onun yarandığı sosial və mədəni kontekstlə əlaqəsini öyrənən bir elmdir. (3)

Bunun üçün o, müəyyən bir cəmiyyət daxilində real istifadə vəziyyətlərini araşdırır, fərdlərin şifahi şəkildə necə qarşılıqlı əlaqədə olduğunu və müəyyən kodları və idiomatik qaydaları paylaşdığını təhlil edir.

Bütün cəmiyyətlərin spesifik danışmaq təzi var ki, bu da öz növbəsində həmsöhbətlərin yaşından, cinsindən, hazırlıq səviyyəsindən və sosial təbəqəsindən asılı olaraq dəyişir.

Digər tərəfdən, sözlər və ünsiyyət üsulları da dialoqun getdiyi yer və kontekstdən asılı olaraq dəyişir.

Bu amilləri və onların dili şərtləndirdiyi və söz seçiminə təsir göstərdiyi üsul sosiolinqvistika tərəfindən öyrənilir.

Sosiolinqvistika dili istifadə edən şəxsdən asılı olmayaraq, mücərrəd bir sistem kimi deyil, sosial və mədəni hadisə kimi təhlil etməklə xarakterizə olunur. Bunun üçün o, dilləri və onların baş verdiyi kontekstdə, real həyat vəziyyətlərində danışmaq tərzini öyrənir və diqqətini şəraitə yönəldir. Beləliklə, bu fənnin oxşar tədqiqat metodologiyalarını paylaşdığı sosial elmlər, xüsusilə antropologiya və sosiologiya ilə əlaqə nöqtələri var. Birinci və ikinci dillərin öyrənilməsini asanlaşdırmaq üçün sosial linqvistik biliklərdən istifadə edilmişdir, çünki sosial kontekst bu

prosesdə əsas elementdir. Məsələn, insan uşaqla danışdığı kimi böyüklərlə də danışır. O, həmçinin danışdığı mövzudan və ya dostlarınızla küçədə olduğunuzdan və ya iş yerində müştəriyə xidmət etdiyinizdən asılı olaraq dili dəyişir.

Hər bir dil çoxlu dialektlərin toplusudur. Dialekt regional ola bilən variasiyalarla bağlıdır, yəni istifadəçilərin yaşadığı yerə, bölgəyə və ya əraziyə görə. Dəyişiklik həm də sosial ola bilər, yəni istifadəçilərin sosial statusuna və ya sinfinə görə. Dialekt eyni zamanda müəyyən bir yerdə, bölgədə və ya ərazidə yaşayan, say baxımından nisbi olan bir qrup istifadəçidən gələn dil dəyişikliyinə də aiddir (Chaer & Augustina, 1995:83).

Bir ləhcənin istifadəçiləri onları eyni dialektə malik insanlar kimi qeyd edən müəyyən xüsusiyyətlərə malikdir. Məsələn, Şəki dialektindən istifadə edən insanların Bakı ləhcəsinə sahib olanlardan (əsasən İçərişəhərdə danışılır) fərqli olan özünəməxsus xüsusiyyətləri var. Lakin onlar bir-birləri ilə yaxşı ünsiyyət qura bilirlər, çünki bu ləhcələr eyni dilin növləridir.

Regional dialekt regiona görə ölkənin bir hissəsində danışılır. Məsələn, Yorkşir və Şotlandiyada danışılan ingilis dili regional dialektlərdir. Eynilə, Azərbaycanda Qərb dialekti regional. Regional dialektlər yaxın qonşularında daha az, uzaq qonşularda isə daha böyük fərqlər göstərir (Spolsky, 1998:29). Regional variasiya və ya regional dialektə beynəlxalq dünyada da rast gəlmək olar. Variasiya tələffüzdə, lüğətdə və hətta qrammatik fərqlərdə özünü göstərə bilər (Holmes, 2001:124). Tələffüz və lüğət fərqləri yəqin ki, insanların ingilis dilinin müxtəlif dialektləri arasında bildiyi ən asan fərqlərdir. Tələffüz fərqlərini vurğuda ayrıca müzakirə edəcəyik. Burada söz ehtiyatı və qrammatik fərqlərə diqqət yetirəcəyik. (5)

Dünyada danışılan ingilis dilinin müxtəlif növləri var. İngiltərə İngilis dili, Amerika İngilis, Kanada İngilis dili, Avstraliya İngilis dili. Lüğət fərqlərinin nümunələri avstraliyalılar, İngiltərə və Yeni Zelandiyalılar tərəfindən istifadə edilən terimlə tapıla bilər. Avstraliyalılar *sole parents- tək valideynlər* terminindən istifadə edirlər, İngiltərədə yaşayan insanlar *single parents- tək valideynlərdən* istifadə edirlər və Yeni Zelandiyalılar onlara *solo parents-tək valideynlər* deyirlər. Eynilə, İngilis dilinin müxtəlif növlərində olan bəzi qrammatik fərqlər var.

Məsələn, amerikalılar "*do you have-sən var?*" sözünü, Britaniya ingilisləri "*have you got-sən var?*", amerikalılar "*gotten-feli sifət*" sözünü, İngiltərədəki insanların çoxu "*got*", bir çox amerikalılar "*smelled- qoxuladı*" sözünü, əksər britaniyalılar isə ingilis dilində danışanların çoxu "*smelt-iyədi*" və amerikalılar "*did you eat?-yemisan?*" ingilislər isə "*have you eaten? -yemisan?*" deyirlər.

Sosial dialektə həm də sosiolekt deyilir və müəyyən sosial təbəqəyə mənsub bir qrup insan tərəfindən danışılır. məsələn, Londonda yuxarı, orta və aşağı təbəqənin danışdığı ingilis dili sosial dialektlərdir.

Sosiolektlər coğrafiya ilə deyil, sosial amillərlə müəyyən edilən dialektlərdir. Sosiolektlər çox vaxt cəmiyyət daxilində sosial-iqtisadi sinif və din kimi sosial bölünmələr səbəbindən inkişaf edir. Məsələn, Nyu-York şəhərində **four**-dördüncü sözdə olduğu kimi, **r** hərfini hecanın sonunda gələndə tələffüz etmə ehtimalı sosial-iqtisadi sinifdən asılı olaraq dəyişir. Ümumiyyətlə, yekun **r**-nin tələffüzü yüksək sosial-iqtisadi siniflərin nümayəndələri ilə əlaqələndirilir.

Bir dildə fərqli vurğulardan danışarkən, bir dildə danışanlar arasında tələffüz fərqlərini nəzərdə tuturuq. Vurğulardakı fərqlər ya danışanların yaşadıkları coğrafi bölgəyə görə, ya da sosial siniflərinə görə baş verən dəyişikliklərdir. Məsələn, İngiltərənin cənubunda təhsilli natiqlər tərəfindən danışılan Received Pronunciation (RP) və Londonda təhsilsiz natiqlər tərəfindən istifadə edilən Cockney ingilis dilinin vurğularıdır. Amerikalının tələffüz etdiyi *god-tanrı* sözü ingilis dilində danışan britaniyalının tələffüz etdiyi *guard-mühafizəçi* kimi səslənir və *latter-sonuncu* sözü bir çox qeyri-amerikan ingiliscə danışanlara *ladder-nərdivan* kimi səslənir.

Reyestr termini leksikonda variasiya ilə xarakterizə olunan peşəyə əsaslanan növlərə aiddir. Müxtəlif peşələrlə əlaqəli dilin mütəxəssis istifadəsidir. Ola bilsin ki, həkimə getdiyimiz zaman gündəlik söhbətimizdə istifadə edə bilməyəcəyimiz bəzi sözlərlə rastlaşdığımızı müşahidə

etmişiniz. Məsələn, Nəbz dərəcəsi, Arterial təzyiq, stetoskop, resept. Eynilə hüquq reyestrini, reklam reyestrini, təhsil reyestrini və digər peşələri düşünə bilərik. Dilin, xüsusən də lüğətin bu mütəxəssis istifadəsi eyni sözün ümumi dildə və ya sadə bir insan tərəfindən istifadə edilməsindən fərqlidir. Məsələn, bacı sözü ümumi məişət dilində (*bacı-sister – bacı-qardaş- sibling*) və tibb dünyasında (*bacı-sister –tibb bacısı- nurse*) fərqli məna kəsb edir. Eynilə, anbara gələn *mouse - siçan* kompüterinizə qoşulmuş *siçan -mouse* ilə eyni deyil.

Təcrübə icması sosiolinqvistikaya sosiallaşma, səriştə və şəxsiyyət arasındakı əlaqəni araşdırmaq imkanı verir. Şəxsiyyət çox mürəkkəb bir quruluş olduğundan, dilin sosiallaşmasının öyrənilməsi praktik fəaliyyətin (gündəlik fəaliyyətlərin) mikro-qarşılıqlı səviyyəsini yoxlamaq üçün bir vasitədir. (6. 59) Dilin öyrənilməsi ailədən çox təsirlənir, lakin bu, məktəb, idman komandaları və ya din kimi daha geniş yerli mühit tərəfindən dəstəklənir. Nitq icmaları daha geniş təcrübə icması daxilində mövcud ola bilər

3. NƏTİCƏ

Sosiolinqvistika tətbiqi dilçiliyin alt sahəsidir. Sosiolinqvistik tədqiqatlara gəldikdə, hər birinin öz metodologiyası və tədqiqat obyektini olan üç əsas sahəsi var. Bunlar şəhər variasiyası və ya kəmiyyəti, dil sosiologiyası və ünsiyyət etnoqrafiyasıdır.

Tətbiqi dilçilik dillə əlaqəli real dünya problemlərinin müəyyən edilməsi, tədqiqi və həlli ilə məşğul olur. Sosiolinqvistika ilə dilçilik arasındakı fərq ondan ibarətdir ki, dilçilik bizi dilin strukturundan xəbərdar edir, sosiolinqvistika isə gündəlik vəziyyətlərdə bu strukturun istifadə edərək bir-birimizlə necə qarşılıqlı əlaqədə olduğumuzu izah edir. Dilçilik xüsusi dillərin keyfiyyətlərini, eləcə də ümumiyyətlə dilin xüsusiyyətlərini sisteməlik şəkildə araşdırmaq məqsədi daşıyan dilin elmi tədqiqidir. O, təkcə səs, qrammatika və mənanın öyrənilməsini deyil, həm də dil ailələrinin tarixini, körpələrin və böyüklərin dilləri necə öyrəndiyini, dil istifadəsinin şüurda necə işləndiyini və bunun irq və cinslə necə əlaqəli olduğunu ehtiva edir. Sosiolinqvistika cəmiyyətin hər hansı və ya bütün hissəsinin dilə təsirini və onun necə istifadə edildiyini, o cümlədən mədəni normalar, gözləntilər və kontekstlə bağlı təsviri tədqiqatdır. O, dilin cəmiyyətə təsirini öyrənən linqvistik sosiologiya ilə üst-üstə düşə bilər. Sosiolinqvistika dilçiliyin yalnız izah edilməsi üçün sosial, o cümlədən kontekst elementlərinə istinad tələb edən dilin və dillərin xüsusiyyətlərini təhlil edən bir elm sahəsidir. Sosiolinqvistlər ümumiyyətlə sosial xüsusiyyətlər və dildaxili variasiya arasındakı əlaqə ilə maraqlansalar da, antropoloji-linqvistik tədqiqatlar mədəni elementlər və dillərarası variasiya arasındakı əlaqə ilə məşğul olur. Dil və cəmiyyət arasındakı əlaqənin öyrənilməsi sosiolinqvistika kimi tanınır. Sosiolinqvistika yeni dillərin öyrənilməsini asanlaşdırmaq üçün də istifadə olunur. Dil variantları eyni anlayışa istinad etmək üçün bir dildə mövcud olan müxtəlif formalara istinad edir. Bu mənada, sosiolinqvistika müəyyən qrupların və ya insanların nə üçün başqa bir söz əvəzinə müəyyən bir sözü istifadə etməyi seçdiyini və hansı şəraitdə ondan istifadə etdiyini öyrənir. Dörd növ variant var: coğrafi və ya diatopik, kontekstual və ya diafatik, sosial-mədəni və ya diastratik, tarixi və ya diaxronik.

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THE PROBLEM OF PREPARING PHYSICS TEACHERS TO ORGANIZE RESEARCH ACTIVITIES OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN KAZAKHSTAN

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the research topic lies in the problem of preparing physics teachers for the organization of research activities of schoolchildren, the need to develop the research abilities of future physics teachers as an important factor in their professional development. The object of the research is the research abilities of physics teachers. The subject of the study was the problem of preparing future teachers of physics for the organization of research activities of schoolchildren. The study was carried out in three stages.

Keywords: research competencies, physics teachers, skills, students

Introduction

The development of research skills among schoolchildren is one of the urgent problems of our time. It is carried out by teachers in the course of systematic work both in the classroom and in extracurricular forms of work- electives, circle work, project activities and individual lessons for schoolchildren. Here the role of the university lies not only in the problem of preparing future teachers of physics for organizing research activities with schoolchildren, but also in developing theoretical and methodological developments, creating an effective permanent teaching and research team, whose task is to form a new teacher capable of developing an effective research learning process.

Literature review

At the first stage, a literary analysis was carried out on the topic of the study. The research materials were legal acts, monographs, scientific articles and other scientific publications on the

research topic. Theoretical research methods are defined: analysis of pedagogical, methodical literature, normative legal acts and practice of forming research abilities.

The state educational standard of higher education requires the preparation of a bachelor of physics for research activities at school. The fulfillment of this task requires the involvement of students in research activities, the psychological features of which are reflected in the works of A.B. Brushlinsky, J.I.C. Vygotsky, V.A. Krutetsky, Yu.N. Kulyutkina, Ya.A. Ponomareva, S.Yu.T. Rubinstein, J.I.M. Friedman and others.

A.B. Usovoy, A.A. Bobrov, L.D. Shabashova, O.P. Bazhora, L.B. Gasparova, N.I. Mokritskaya, E.I. Barchuk, A.N. Kulev, S.F. Borisov and other scientists have proposed methods for the formation of research skills in the framework of a laboratory workshop.

Ya. Mamaeva, Yu.V. Leonov, L.T. Prishchepoy, Yu.V. Bekhovych, L.A. Bekhovych, A.A. Levin, T.G. Vaganova, E.A. Semenyuk and other researchers in the framework of the workshop studied the increase in cognitive activity and the development of students' creative abilities.

The use of information technology in laboratory work is considered in the studies of V.V. Larionova, G.V. Erofeeva, A.E. Eizenzon, S.B. Rozhkova, I.V. Aleksandrova, S.A. Shatokhina, E.V. Trofimova, A.M. Agaltsova, A.N. Morozova, M.B. Shapochkina, Yu.B. Pankrashkin and others.

Materials and methods

At the second stage, teachers of Pavlodar Pedagogical University held traditional meetings with graduates, current teachers of physics in Pavlodar and Pavlodar region.

During the meeting, the problems of teachers, issues of teaching and studying physics were discussed. Educators throughout this time asked questions and shared their ideas. The participants of the meeting voiced their proposals for the development of research skills among students, spoke about the need for advanced training courses, about the fact that the university physics teacher training program does not provide proper preparation of student teachers for teaching physics. Sometimes graduates lacked the relevant knowledge, skills and competencies to organize and conduct research work with schoolchildren. At the diagnostic stage, the level of formation of skills in conducting and organizing research work, as well as the level of motivation to conduct research work among 52 teachers was established. We proposed to prepare and launch a questionnaire for physics teachers to identify acquired research competencies after graduation. The main questions of the questionnaire were: do you know what research minimum a physics teacher should have; did you receive methodological materials during the training, according to which children should be taught research work; Do you use goal setting, testing, and hypothesis formulation in your teaching? Do you use design and creative methods in teaching? whether students have analytical skills and the ability to draw conclusions; how often do you conduct research with students; what prevents you from doing research work at school.

Results and discussion

The results of the assessment of the practice of developing the research skills of teachers indicate that the training of the majority of practicing teachers in the field of conducting and organizing the educational and research work of students is insufficient. This is understandable, because scientific work is not a necessary element of a teacher's professional activity.

At the next stage, a model for training future teachers was developed to form students' research skills. When developing the model, we proceeded from the fact that the formation of research activity seems to be a controlled and directed process that begins within the walls of the university under the guidance of experienced teachers. At the university, future teachers should acquire knowledge and skills that they can use in their teaching activities. It should be noted that the requirements for the level of training of future teachers are determined by the standard of higher education, qualification requirements, as well as changes in the school education system.

The proposed model for the formation of the readiness of future physics teachers for research activities is a set of interrelated and interacting structural components: methodological, meaningful, criteria-evaluative. The main goal - the external system-forming factor of this model is the formation of certain components of the readiness of future teachers to teach physics: motivational, meaningful, creative, reflective.

Conclusion

Thus, we have established that the problem of preparing physics teachers for research work remains relevant and needs to be addressed as soon as possible. This is due to the fact that modern physical education at school should be built in such a way that students are interested in research work, which makes it possible to teach them to understand new things, form skills and make independent decisions, primarily based on the results. research and then in practice. These requirements are also imposed on pedagogical universities, which should update the quality of training of teaching staff with an emphasis on a competency-based approach.

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Application of 5 E lesson model in the teaching of "Medicinal plants" subject of class VI

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Keywords: 5E lesson model, medicinal plants, stages of the lesson, biology, lesson example.

Teaching students to obtain knowledge independently is one of the main goals of today's education system. In this context, priority is given to course models that will reveal students' research interests. The 5E model is one of the modern teaching models based on constructivism. Constructivism is a model which claims that knowledge may be actively established by students.

The 5 E lesson model, based on a constructive approach, allows the application of independently obtained knowledge in the teaching of biology. The 5E learning model requires prior knowledge of the subject, openness to new ideas, and comparison of prior and post-knowledge. In this lesson model, the student goes through the process of discovering knowledge via exploration, experimentation, and learning. The teacher acts as a mediator who encourages and supports.

The 5E model has been used as a teaching method since the end of 1980. The 5E lesson model guides students on how to learn, encourages active learning, and supports the development of various skills. The 5E lesson model consists of 5 consecutive stages.

Let's take an example of a lesson prepared due to the 5E model. The first stage is the Engage stage. At this stage, students are asked questions using a familiar situation and invited to discuss. The aim is to connect students' prior knowledge with the learning outcomes of the lesson, to arouse interest in the topic and direct them to research.

A fragment from the film "Dade Gorgud" is shown to arouse interest in the subject. At this stage, students brainstorm and answer the following questions.

- Why did Dade Gorgud recommend the mountain flower?
- Do you think all mountain flowers have healing properties?
- Which herbs can be ointments?

In the second stage, Explore, students participate in activities, discuss results, and are prepared to move from specific results to a more general understanding.

Activity: Look at the plants shown in the picture.

Step 1: Can you name the medicinal plants (herbs) in the picture?

Step 2: Why do we call these herbs "medicinal" plants?

In the third Explain stage of the lesson, students learn the correct information and any misconceptions are clarified. Explained:

- Wild medicinal plants and their therapeutic importance;
- Cultivated medicinal plants and their therapeutic importance;
- Toxic medicinal plants and their harmful effects.

The teacher provides additional information about the medicinal plants of *Origanum* and *Eguisetum* (wild horsetail). The teacher informs the students that *Eguisetum* is widely used in folk medicine. This plant grows on the edges of fields, in moist soils. Horsetail has a positive effect on rheumatism. It accelerates the regeneration of damaged skin. It purifies the blood from toxic substances. It is a diuretic. The load accumulated in the body removes water from the body. In addition, *Origanum* herb is widely used in medicine. Tea made from this herb has an antiseptic

effect and is used as a gargle for sore throats. Brewing tea from dried Origanum relieves inflammation and spasm.

In the fourth stage of the lesson, Deepening (Elaborate) stage, new examples and samples are presented and the scope of the concept applied is expanded. New information is developed through tasks.

- Note the similarities and differences between wild and cultivated herbs in the Venn diagram.

- Place the following plants in the box correctly and provide information about them.

The fifth and final stage is the Evaluate stage. Evaluation criteria: explanation, differentiation. The 3-2-1 method is used in reflection.

At this stage, the level of students' mastery of the content is measured via the questions under the heading "Check what you have learned" in the textbook.

- Which parts of the plants are used for treatment?
- What are the harms of toxic medicinal plants?

Homework: Prepare herbarium of medicinal plants and provide information about them.

The application of the 5E model in biology teaching reveals the creative potential of students, forms the skills of formulating a problem, observing, analyzing, drawing conclusions and determining ways to solve the problem, and communicating the results with friends.

Абай Құнанбаевтың өлеңдеріндегі метафораның қызметі және оның аудармадағы көрінісі

Сексембаева Әлия Асылжанқызы

Педагогика ғылымдарының магистрі, Қазақстан Республикасы, Алматы қаласы,
Азаматтық Авиация Академиясы

Аннотация

Бұл мақала арқылы бүгінгі таңда аударма қазақ тіліне әлем әдебиетінің ең шоқтықты шығармаларын төгілте түсіру арқылы мемлекеттік тіліміздің мәртебесін асыруға ықпал жасай алатындығының айғағы. Қазақ поэзия аудармасының мұндай кемелдікке келу кезеңдерін теориялық тұрғыдан тұжырымдай талдау оның келешектегі көркемдік көкжиегін кеңейту жолдарын қарастыруға септесетін болады. Бүгінгі қоғам талабына сай елімізде туындап жатқан әлеуметтік – экономикалық өзгерістер мен жариялықтар білім беру саясатына жаңа көзқарас қалыптастыруды қажет етеді.

Көркем туынды да халықтың тарихи жүріп өткен жолдары, өмір белестері, елдік – ерлік дәстүрлері, тұрмыс – салты, психологиясы жинақталған, табиғаты кескінделген, адамгершілік ұғым түсінігі көрініс табады. Осындай талғамы биік оқушы жүрегіне жол табатын шығармалар қатарына Абай туындылары жатады. Сөз өз мағынасында емес, ауыстыру, алмастырып айту мағынасында қолданылады.

Түйін сөздер: метафора, метонимия, синекдоха, кейіптеу, символ

1. Кіріспе

Тілімізде өз мағынасында қолданатын сөздермен қатар, ауыспалы мағынасында қолданылатын сөздер де аз емес. Олар әсіресе көркем әдебиетте көбірек кездеседі. Көркем тілдің басқа түрлерінен ауыстыру мағынасында қолданылатын сөздердің негізгі ерекшелігі сөз астарлығында.

Абайдың поэтикалық тілдерінің өз мағынасында, ауыстыру мағынасында қолданатын жеке образдарын жасауда, адамның ой-сезіміне әсер етуде сөйлемдегі сөз байланыстарының мәні қандай, соған тоқталамыз. Жазушы, ақындар шығармаларын қара сөз, не ғылыми еңбектердегі сөз, сөйлем құрылыстарының түрлерінен басқаша құрады. Жазушы ақындар қандай өмір құбылысын суреттесе де, ең алдымен сезім дүниесіне әсер ету тілегін алға қояды.

Метафора. Ауыстыру мағынасында қолданылатын сөздер – қазақ өлеңдерінде де басқа әдебиеттердегі поэтик тілдермен негізі бір. Метафора, метонимия, синекдоха, кейіптеу, символ - бәрі жөнінде де осыны айтуға болады. Бірақ мазмұны жағында өзгешелік болмаса да, қазақ өлеңдеріндегі метафораларды орыс тіліндегі метафоралармен салыстырғанда, жасалуы жағынан өзінше кейбір ерекшеліктері де жоқ емес. Қазақ поэзия аудармасының арғы-бергідегі жүріп өткен жолын, бел-белестерін бажайлау, ізденістері мен іркілістерін саралау – ұлттың көркемдік ойының бүгінгі биігін бағамдаудың, алда алар асуларын белгілеудің бір жолы. Бұл жолға талдау жасау арқылы тәржіменің халқымыз тарихында қандайлық қомақты орын алғанын ғана емес, сонымен бірге келешек замандарда атқарар рөлінің де бөлекше болатынын көрсете аламыз.

1.1 Метафора және олардың аударылу ерекшеліктері

Метафора. Құрылымдық сипаттаманы образды дүние мен заттық дүние арасындағы мағыналық қатынасты есепке ала отырып аудару. Ауыстыру мағынасында қолданылатын сөздер - қазақ өлеңдерінде де басқа әдебиеттердегі поэтик тілдермен негізі бір. Метафора, метонимия, синекдоха, кейіптеу, символ бәрі жөнінде де осыны айтуға болады.

Жалпы алғанда, метафора - сыртқы, не ішкі бір ұқсастығына қарап, бір нәрсені екінші нәрсеге балау. Екі нәрсенің арасына тепе-теңдік белгісін қою десек, қазақ өлеңдерін де солай етіп шығару үшін кейде бір нәрсені екінші нәрсеге тікелей болса да, кейде жалғау арқылы, кейде көмекші етістіктер арқылы жасалатындығын көреміз.

Метафораның қызметі арқылы тілдің лексикалық және фразеологиялық қабаты, жалпы сөздік құрамы, бір ұғым аясы кеңі түседі. Сөздің метафоралануы арқылы сөз саны өспегенімен, мағына аясы көбейеді. Метафора көптеген тіл қабаттарының шығу көзі. Фразеологизмдер, мақал-мәтелдер, қанатты сөздер метафораға негізделіп жасалады.

Метафоралар, яғни ауыс мағыналы не әсірелеу мәнінде алынатын сөздер көбіне-көп көркем әдебиет стилінде қолданылғанмен, ара-тұра өзге стиль түрлерінде де кездеседі. Әдеби шығармалардағы метафора мен публицистикалық, саяси еңбектердегі метафора стильдік қызметі жағынан өз ара бірдей болып келе бермейді. Себебі, көркем әдебиет стилінде жалпы халықтық сипаттағы метафоралармен қоса, контекстікте метафора қолданылады. Публицистикалық стильде негізінен жалпы халықтық сипаттағы метафора жиі пайдаланады, Ал публицистикалық стильден кон-текстік метафора оқта-текте ғана ұшырасады.

Метафора сондай-ақ ресми кеңсе стилінде де қолданылады. Мұнда да негізінен сол жалпы халықтық сипаттағы метафоралар жұмсалады. Бірақ стиль түрлерінің ішінде метафора жалпы көркем әдебиет және публицистикалық стильдерден жиі байқалады. Ал басқаларға қарағанда ғылыми, ресми-кеңсе стильдерінде біршама аздау кездеседі. Мысалы, ресми-кеңсе стилінде мына тәрізді метафоралар қолданылады:

Метафораның (ауыс мағыналы не әсірелеу мағынасындағы сөз-дің) ен, көп қолданылатын жері — публицистикалық стиль мен әсіресе көркем әдебиет стилі. Сөздің метафоралық мағынасы шешендік сарындағы өсиет өлеңдерден, мақал-мәтелден, айтыс жырла-рынан, қиссалардан, жұмбақ пен жаңылтпаштардан, ауыз әдебиетінің өзге де үлгілерінен кездеседі. Бірақ осылардың ішінде өте-мөте көркем әдебиет стилінде жиі және әр тарап түрде келіп отырады.

«Құлагер, әкең - тұлпар, шешең - сұңқар,

Соғып ең дөненіңде сегіз арқар».

(Ақан сері)

«Арыстан еді Исатай».

(Махамбет)

Бұл үзінділерде «Құлагердің әкесін - тұлпар, шешесін - сұңқар», «Исатай арыстан» деп, «тұлпарға», «арыстанға» тікелей балап және екі нәрсенің арасына тепе-теңдік белгісін қояды (Исатай да арыстан, арыстан да арыстан). Аристотель теңеу мен метафора туралы айта келіп, мынадай мысалдар келтіреді. «Лев (-Ахилл) ринулся - и Ахилл ринулся, как лев» дейді. Мұның алдыңғысы - метафора, соңғысы – теңеу.

2. Зерттеудің мақсаты

Сөз өз мағынасында емес, ауыстыру, алмастырып айту мағынасында қолданылады. Әсірелеуде өмір құбылысы, қимыл, іс-әрекет, көрсетпек нәрсе қаншама үлкейтіліп айтылғанмен де, сөз өз мағынасында қолданылады. Зат, іс-амал, құбылыстар не өте үлкейтіледі, не өте кішірейтіледі. Бірақ өзінің бұрынғы мағынасынан ауыстырылмайды. Әсірелеу де, литота да өмір құбылысын суреттеудегі көркем тілдердің негізгі бір түрі есебінде бұрынғы және соңғы әдебиетімізден де орын алады.

Аударма – лингвистика заңдылықтарына арқа сүйеу арқылы тіларалық коммуникация міндеттерін шешетін сөз өнерінің өзгеше түрі. Көркем аударманың жемісі ретінде зерттеу қарастыратын поэзиялық тәржіме – алдымен әдебиеттану нысаны. Қойылған мақсатқа жету үшін төмендегідей міндеттер белгіленді:

- өлең тәржімесінің өзіндік ерекшеліктерін таныту;
- метафора және оның түрлерін белгілеу;
- метафораның өлеңде қолдану тәсілдерін талдау;
- аударманың төл әдебиетке ықпалын анықтау;
- аударманың әдіс-тәсілдерін сипаттау;

1. Абай туралы зерттеу еңбектеріне сүйене отырып, оның өскен ортасы, педагогикалық көзқарасы туралы сипаттап жазу.

2. Абайдың өлеңдер арқылы әдіс-тәсілдерін көрсету.

3. Деректерді жинау және талдау

Әлем әдебиетіндегі атақты ақындардың әйгілі шығармалары туған тілімізге тәржімеленіп, сөз өнеріміздің қоржынына қосылды. Соңғы бір ғасырға жуық уақыт аясында бұл жұмыс мемлекеттік деңгейде атқарылып, жүйелі, мақсатты сипат алды. Өлең аудармасына қазақ жырындағы таланттардың бәрі дерлік тартылып, аударма арқылы ұлттық поэзиямыздың көркемдік құралдары анағұрлым молыға түсті. Тарих табыстырған, тағдыр тоғыстырған орыс халқының төл поэзиясынан аударма жасау кең құлаш жайды. Орыс тілі арқылы сол тілге аударылған әлем поэзиясының күні кешеге дейін бір елдің құрамында өмір сүрген, қазір де алуан-алуан ықпалдастық жіптерімен жалғасып жатқан мемлекеттердің өлең-жырларының таңдаулылары тәржімеленді.

Жұмыста қолданылатын әдістемелер негізі. Зерттеуде негізгі тәсіл ретінде аудармалардың мәтінін түпнұсқамен салыстыра талдау тәсілі қолданылған. Абай туралы әдеби - сын зерттеу, философиялық, филологиялық, тарих, педагогикалық еңбектерді оқу, талдау, жүйелеу. Сөйтіп Абайдың поэтик тілдердің басқа түрлері жөнінде қазақ әдебиет тіліне қосқан жаңалықтарын жекелеп көрсетсек, кейіптеу Абайдың жазба әдебиетімізге бүтіндей қосқан жаңалығы деп айтуға болады. Өйткені ескі ауыз әдебиетінде өмір құбылысын суреттеуде поэтик тілдің негізгі бір түрі саналып, XVIII-XIX ғасырдың әдебиетінде де қолданылмай, не аз кездесетін кейіптеуді жаңа дәуір, жаңа ой-санаға сәйкес жаңаланған түрде қайта тіріліп, поэтик тілдердің өмір құбылысын суреттеуде санаулы құралының бірі етуі - қазақтың әдебиет тілін жасауда, сөз жоқ, ұлы еңбек.

Сонымен қатар Абайдың кейіптеуді қолдану жолдары әр алуан. Олардың әрқайсысында үлкен шеберлік, місекерліктер бар. Олардың әрқайсысы жеке талдауды керек етеді. Әйтсе де сол табиғатты жанды етіп суреттеудің сезім дүниесіне қандай әсер етуі жайлы «Мен көрдім ұзын қайың құлағанын» деген өлеңінен бір үзінді келтірейік:

«Мен көрдім ұзын қайың құлағанын,
Бас ұрып қара жерге сұлағанын.
Жапырағы сарғайып, өлімсіреп,
Байғұстың кім тыңдайды жылағанын.
Мен көрдім ойнап жүрген қызыл киік,
Кеудесіне мылтықтың оғы тиіп,
Қалжырап, қансыраған, қабақ түскен,
Кімге батар ол байғұс тартқан күйік.
Мен көрдім сынық қанат көбелекті,
О да білер өмірді іздемекті,
Күншуақта жатады қалт-қалт етіп,
Одан ғыбрат алар жан бір бөлек-ті».

(Абай, II том, 113-бет)

Табиғат құбылысын, жан-жануарларды кейіптеу арқылы суреттеп, не терең ой, не терең сезімдерді беруге болатындықтың бұл үзінді айқын үлгісі бола алады. Абайдан кейінгі қазақ әдебиетінде кейіптеудің поэтик тілден үлкен орын алуы да Абайдың әсері деуге болады.

4. Қорытынды

Абай – қазақ ұлтының ұлт боп өмір сүргендігінің және ұлт ретінде өмір сүруге хұқы барлығының кепілі. Себебі, дүниежүзілік ауқымға сай қазақтың ұлттық санасын оятқан және оны қалыптастырған адам – Абай. Абайды Абай еткен, асыл сөзімен өлең етіп ұйытып, жүрегіне жыр болып байланған қасиеті - өмірден әділет, мейірім, сенім, адалдық іздеу барысында тапқан танымдық олжалары, санасын сарғайтып барып көзін ашқан тұжырым тоғыстары өлең арқылы өріліп жатыр. Абай өлеңдерінің тақырыбы жан-жақты әлеуметтік аясы кең. Өлеңдері халықты өнерге, білімге, ғылымға шақырады, әрі жанға жайлы, жүрекке жылы тиетін махаббат өлеңдері болып келеді. Сондықтан Абай өлеңдері XIX ғасырдағы «қазақ қоғамының айнасы» деп те аталады. Жоғарыда атап өткендей, көркем мәтін өзі дүниеге келген дәуірдің құндылығы болып табылады.

Әр кезеңдерде және әр түрлі мәдениетте аударма туралы әр түрлі түсініктер орын алады. Сондықтан да «барлық заманға сай» аударма да өте аз. Дегенмен, көркем аударма тек қана лексикалық және синтаксистік сәйкестікпен ғана емес, тілге қатысты көркемдік байланыстар арқылы аударылуы керек.

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Literature

AZƏRBAYCAN-FRANSA ƏDƏBİ ƏLAQƏLƏRİ

Əsmayə Bəxtiyar qızı Əkbərova

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ABSTRACT

Azerbaijan-France cultural, scientific, artistic creative relations, which have more than three hundred years of history, have led both peoples to get to know each other more closely and become closer. The role of French literati is great in the field of collecting and translating materials related to the classical literature and folklore of Azerbaijan, which has rich creativity and traditions. French researchers paid a lot of attention to rich oral and written folk treasure of Azerbaijan, art monuments such as “Avesta”, “Kitabi Dada-Gorgud”, “Koroglu”, “Nizam, Khagani, Nasimi Fuzuli, Khatai, M.F.Akhundov and other prominent. They tried to study and translate the writers. The “Koroglu” epic was translated by A.Breliev and George Sand in Paris in 1853 and published in the form of monographs in “Aziatik” magazine. One of the translations reads: In the “Koroglu” epic, it is not about miracles created by a simple peasant, but about a hero who came out of the people, burned for the people, managed to lead the people behind him, and fought for justice. The hero around whom representatives of different nations gather and become brothers. The attributes of the legendary hero are “Egyptian sword” and “Griat”.

Keywords: folk creativity, creative relations, mutual understanding, intercultural communication, classical literature, folklore materials, national treasure, representative, numerous services, bright example, publicist, artistic wordsmith.

1. GIRIŞ

Millətlərarası mədəni-humanitar əlaqələr həmin millətlərin bir-birinə yaxınlaşmasına səbəb olmuş, qarşılıqlı anlaşmanın və mədəniyyətlərarası ünsiyyətin yaranmasına səbəb olmuşdur. Üç yüz ildən çox tarixə malik olan Azərbaycan - Fransa mədəni əlaqələri hər iki xalqın bir-birlərini daha yaxından tanımasına və yaxınlaşmasına imkan yaratmışdır. Tarixən Şərqlə Qərb arasında “qızıl körpü” rolunu oynaması Azərbaycanımızı dünyada mədəni miras baxımından ən dəyərli ölkələrdən biri olaraq tanıtmışdır. Bu isə beynəlxalq mədəni əlaqələrin yaranmasında və genişlənməsində əhəmiyyətli təsirə malikdir. Mütərəqqi düşüncəli ziyalılarımız daim Azərbaycan mədəniyyətini dünyaya tanımaq sahəsində geniş təbliğat işləri həyata keçirmişlər. Azərbaycan mədəniyyəti tarixin bütün dövrlərində dünya sivilizasiyasının qabaqcıl dövlətlərinin, o cümlədən Qərbin mədəniyyət beşiyi hesab olunan Fransanın diqqət mərkəzində olmuşdur. Nizami Gəncəvinin hələ XIV əsrdən (1362-1366) qeydə alınmış “Xəmsə”sinin əlyazması Parisdə milli xalq kitabxanasında saxlanılır.

Hələ XIX əsrin sonu-XX əsrin əvvəllərində Avropada təhsil alan Azərbaycan gəncləri, ziyalıları Fransa mədəniyyəti, incəsənəti ilə dərinlən maraqlanırdılar. Avropanın mədəni nailiyyəti kimi bu dəyərlərin Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinə inteqrasiyası üçün çalışırdılar. Fransanın mədəniyyət və incəsənət tarixinin qabaqcıl ziyalıları da Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinə biganə qalmamış, Azərbaycanın tarixi ənənələri, təbiəti, incəsənəti, dəyərli mütəfəkkirlərinin tanış olmuşlar. Lap qədim zamanlardan xalqlar arasında ədəbi-bədii yaradıcılıq əlaqələri həmin xalqların mənəvi cəhətdən yaxınlaşmasına səbəb olmuş, qarşılıqlı anlaşmanın və mədəniyyətlərarası ünsiyyətin yaranmasına təkan vermişdir.

Gözəl deyilmişdir: “Ədəbi dostluq- xalqlar dostluğudur”.

Üç yüz ildən çox tarixə malik olan Azərbaycan Fransa mədəni, elmi-bədii yaradıcılıq əlaqələri hər iki xalqın bir- birlərini daha yaxından tanımasına və yaxınlaşmasına səbəb olmuşdur. Zəngin yaradıcılığa və adətlərə malik olan Azərbaycan klassik ədəbiyyatı və folkloruna aid materialların toplanması və tərcüməsi sahəsində Fransa ədəbiyyatçılarının rolu böyükdür.

Fransız tədqiqatçıları zəngin Azərbaycan şifahi və yazılı xalq xəzinəsinə çox böyük diqqət yetirmiş, “Avesta”, “Kitabi Dədə Qorqud”, “Koroğlu” kimi sənət abidələrini, Nizami, Xaqani, Nəsimi, Füzuli, Xətai, M.F.Axundov və başqa görkəmli ədəbiyyatçıları tədqiq və tərcümə etməyə səy göstərmişlər.

“Koroğlu” eposu 1853-cü ildə Parisdə A.Brelye və Jorj Saand tərəfindən tərcümə olunmuş, monoqrafiyalar şəklində “Aziatik” jurnalında çap edilmişdir. Tərcümələrdən birində deyilir: “Koroğlu” eposunda sadə bir kəndlinin yaratdığı möcüzələrdən yox, xalq içindən çıxan, xalq üçün yanan, xalqı öz ardi ilə aparmağı bacaran, haqq-ədalət uğrunda mübariz bir el qəhrəmanından danışılır. O qəhrəman ki, onun ətrafında müxtəlif millətlərin nümayəndələri toplaşır, qardaşlaşır. Əfsanəvi qəhrəmanın atributları isə “Misri qılınc” və “Qıratdır”.

“Dədə Qorqud” əsərinin tətbiqi haqqında isə K.Planolun apardığı tədqiqatlar, tərcümələr, əldə edilmiş variantlar düzgün və dəqiq hesab oluna bilər. “Aziatik” jurnalında yazılır ki, 300-dən çox variantı olan bu sənət əsərinin əlyazmasının düzgün variantı Vatikan muzeyində saxlanılır. “Avesta”nın ilk tərcüməçisi XVIII əsrin II yarısında, 1771-ci ildə Fransız alimi Anketil de Perron olmuşdur. Onun tərcümsəi ədəbiyyat sahəsində böyük əks-səda doğurmuş, Fransa Azərbaycan ədəbi əlaqələrinin əsasının qoyulmasında müstəsna rol oynamışdır. 1873-cü ildən 1953-cü ilə qədər “Avesta”nın tərcüməsi ardıcıl olaraq “Aziatik” jurnalında Paris Luvenski Universitetinin professoru M.S. Xarlez tərəfindən həyata keçirilmiş və 1872-1880-ci illər arasında 13 məqalə ilə çıxış etmişdir. Get-gedə avestaçıların- xüsusilə, tərcüməçilərin sayı artmışdır. Onlar öz məqalələri ilə sübut edirdilər ki, Azərbaycanın şifahi və yazılı ədəbiyyatı ilə yaxından maraqlanır və öyrənməyə çalışırlar.

Əlbəttə, Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatına bu qədər maraq göstərən Fransa ədəbiyyatçılarını yazılı ədəbiyyat maraqlandırmaya bilməzdi. Hələ, XIV əsrdən (1362-1366) qeydə alınmış N.Gəncəvinin “Xəmsə”si Parisdə milli xalq kitabxanasında saxlanılır. Xəmsəni ilk dəfə Fransız dilinə tərcümə edən Nizamşunas alim Klerambol olmuşdur. (1741). “İsgəndərnamə” ni isə P.Şarmua tərcümə etmişdir. Nizami irsinin öyrənilməsində Edman və Şarmuanın xidmətləri daha böyükdür.

XIX əsr ədəbiyyatının görkəmli nümayəndəsi M.F.Axundzadənin 1850-1855-ci illərdə yaratdığı ölməz altı komediyasının tərcüməsi bu iki xalqın əlaqələrinin daha dərin olduğunu göstərir. “Mösyö Jordan və Dərviş Məstəli şah” komediyası Fransaya, fransız ədəbiyyatına, karol Lui Flippin devrilməsinə, Fransa inqilabına dərin hörmətin təcəssümüdür. Böyük realist, ustad M.F.Axundov tərəfindən qələmə alınmış Mösyö Jordan mürəkkəb xarakterli; həm müsbət, həm də mənfi cəhətləri olan bir surətdir. Qarabağın florasını öyrənməyə gələn M.Jordanı Hatəm xan ağa çox dəbdəbə ilə qarşılayır. Qonaqpərvər ağa uzaq Parisdən gələn alim Jordanı ailə üzvü kimi qəbul edir. Əsərin gedişi boyu Fransa, Paris diqqət mərkəzində olur. Şahbaz bəy fransız dilini öyrənməyə səy edir, Fransaya alim-Jordanla getmək istəyir. Hatəmxan ağa bu plana əvvəlcə razı olmasa da, qardaşı oğlunun Avropaya səfərinin ona şöhrət gətirəcəyi üçün razılaşıır. Baxmayaraq ki, əsər Fransa inqilabından iki il sonra yazılıb, ancaq dahi Azərbaycan dramaturqu məharətlə hadisələri əlaqələndirib.

M.F.Axundzadənin oğlu Rəşid bəy Axundov 1874-1878-ci illərdə Brüssel Universitetində oxuyurdu və fransız dilini gözəl bildiyindən atasının məsləhəti ilə “Mösyö Jordan” əsərini fransız dilinə, “Balaca Parislinin həyatı” əsərini Azərbaycan dilinə tərcümə edir.

Məmməd Arif yazırdı: “Fransız tədqiqatçıları M.F.Axundzadəni rus xalqının Qoqolu, Fransanın Molyeri adlandırır, hətta, fəlsəfi fikirlərinə görə onu dahi fransız filosofu Volterlə Dünya ədəbiyyatı xəzinəsinə dərin töhfələr vermiş, həm də səyyah kimi tanınmış məşhur fransız yazıçısı

Aleksandr Dümanın Azərbaycan haqqında xoş xatirələri böyük maraqla qarşılır. “Molla İbrahimxəlil kimyagər” komediyası “Kimyagər” adı altında 1886-cı ildə Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı tarixində çoxsaylı xidmətlərindən olan fransız tədqiqatçılardan Barbye de Meynar tərəfindən, “Hacı Qara” komediyası isə, 1904-cü ildə Lüsüən Büv tərəfindən fransız dilinə tərcümə edilmiş və “Aziatik” jurnalında dərc olunmuşdur.

YUNESKO-nun qərarı ilə 1967-ci ildə M.F.Axundzadənin bütün komediyaları toplu halında orijinaldan Lui Bazən tərəfindən tərcümə edilib çap olunmuşdur. Əsərlərinin tam tərcümə edilərək nəşr edilməsi Fransa-Azərbaycan ədəbi əlaqələrinin parlaq nümunəsi sayılır.

Artıq Fransada M.F.Axundzadəni tək dramaturq kimi yox, filosof, şair, ədəbi tənqidçi, publisit, ədəbi və bədii söz ustası kimi tanıyırdılar. Dünya ədəbiyyatı xəzinəsinə dərin töhfələr vermiş, həm də səyyah kimi tanınmış məşhur fransız yazıçısı Aleksandr Dümanın Azərbaycan haqqında xoş xatirələri böyük maraqla qarşılır. Əlaqələrin qədim taixinə daha parlaq bir misal olaraq Aleksandr Dümanın 1958-ci ildə Qafqaza səyahəti zamanı yazdığı xatirələri çox böyük əhəmiyyət daşıyır. Onun “Qafqaz xatirələri” adlı əsəri ilk dəfə Tiflisdə çap olunmuşdur. O, bu səyahətə Parisli rəssam Moyneni də özü ilə aparmışdır. A.Düma bu əsərində də XIX əsrdə Qafqazın ayrı-ayrı yazıçıları, siyasi və hərbi xadimləri, adət-ənənələri haqqında etnik məlumatlar vermiş, bazarlar məscidlər, ibadətgahlar və s. başlıqlarla verilmiş yazılarında XIX əsr Azərbaycan xalqının həyat tərzini ustalıqla qələmə almışdır. Əsərdə Quba şəhərinin və onun ətrafının təkrarolunmaz gözəllikləri təsvir edilmiş, yerli əhalinin əkinçiliklə, xalçaçılıqla məşğul olmaları haqqında məlumatlar verilmişdir. Qubanın meyvə bağları, çayları onu heyratə gətirmiş, Bakı, Xəzərin sahilləri onu valeh etmişdir. O yazırdı: “Xəzər elə bir ilahi gözəlliyə malik idi ki, heç bir taixçi və yazıçı olduğu kimi onu təsvir edə bilməzdi. Mən özümə “Xəzər” adlı bir dost qazandım. Biz bir ay bir yerdə olduq, onun tufanları, fırtınaları haqqında eşitmişdim, ancaq o, mənə xoş təbəssümünü göstərdi. Məndən qabaq Xəzərə Marlinski heyran olmuşdu. Xəzər ondan ötrü sönməyən alov idi, o da mənim kimi Xəzərdən ayərlnməyənə heyfsilənmiş və doluxsunmuşdu”. Bu sətirlər Xəzərin gözəlliyini əks etdirən ilk qələm nümunəsidir və ona görə bizə çox xoşdur ki, bu sözlər Qərbin ən məşhur incəsənət xadimləri, dünya ədəbiyyatının karifeyləri tərəfindən yazılmışdır.

A.Düma Bakıda M.Piqulevskinin iqamətgahında görüşdüyü bir azərbaycanlı ailəni belə təsvir edir: “Səbirsizliklə gözlədiyimiz, hörmətlə qəbul olduğumuz bir məclisdə iki Azərbaycanlı xanımı və 35 yaşında qəddqamətli, alışıb yanan gözləri, qarqara saqqalı, inci kimi ağ dişləri olan, başında quzu dərisindən gözəl papaq, uzun qara çərkəzi çuxa geyən, alovlu bir gənci bizə təqdim etdilər. Xanımlardan biri Qaarabağın axırncı xanı Mehdiquluxanın qızı, o biri isə, Xasay xan İsmiyevin xanımı idi. Hər iki qadın milli geyimdə və çadrada idilər. Xasay xanın geyimini belinə bağlanmış qızıl kəmə, fil sümüyü və qızılla işlənmiş xəncər daha çox gözəlləşdirirdi. O, təmiz fransızca danışırdı. Gənc xanımın yanında bir oğlan, bir də qız uşağı vardı. Oğlanın da belindən nəfis bir xəncər asılmışdı. Lap mat qalmışdım, əsl, iti xəncər idi. Xasay xanla söhbətimdən məlum oldu ki, o, Peterburqda təhsil almış və mənim dostum Marnye ilə yaxın dost olmuşdur. O, məndən xahiş etdi ki, dostumuza onun salamını çatdırım.

A. Dümanın əsərini oxuyan, bu epizodla və adı çəkilmiş şəkillərlə tanış olan hər bir ziyalı söhbətin şairə Xurşudbanu Natavan və onun ailəsindən getdiyini həmin dəqiqə anlar. A.Düma və onun dostu Moyneni Nuxa (Şəki), onun füsunkar gözəlliyi, təbii sərvətləri, üzük qaşı kimi onu əhatə edən dağları valeh etmişdi. A.Dümanın təklifi ilə Moyneni bu şəhərə iki sənət əsəri həsr etmişdi. Həmin əsərlərdən biri uzun illər Qafqazın ən məşhur adamlarından biri olan A.S.Baryatinski tərəfindən qorunub saxlanmış, o biri isə Dümanın Paris malikanəsindəki yataq otağının bəzəyi olmuşdur. A.Düma Nuxada (Şəki) da, çoxlu dostlar qazanmışdı. Ayrı-larkən mayor Məhəmməd xan qılıncı və tapancasını, Knyaz Tarkanov isə ona tufəng və xalça hədiyyə etmiş və Dümadan xahiş etmişdi ki, onlara imkan olsa “Devim” tapancası göndərsin.

“Xurşudbanu Natavan bizim diqqətimizi cəlb etdi, bizi heyran qoydu. Ya Qərbdə, ya da Şərqdə belə dərin zəkaya malik şairə ola bilməz. O, Azərbaycanın seçilib sayılan qadınlarından və şaiələrindəndir. İncə zövqü, kövrək qəlbi, xeyirxah niyyətləri, şair təbiəti ilə xalqın sevimlisi olmağa layiqdir”. A.Düma yazır: “Ey Nuxadan keçən səyyahlar, açıq havada dayanıb mütləq cızbız yeyin, belə təsadüfə əldən verməyin, mütləq yeyin! Tayı-bərabəri olmayan əzəmətli Qafqaz dağlarının qoynuna sığınmış Nuxaya ağaclar arasında baxa-baxa yeyin! Belə ləzzəti siz də dadın ” .Mənə belə gəlir ki, Nuxadan gözəl yer ola bilməz”. Yazıçı Qafqazı bəşəriyyətin beşiyi adlandırır. Qafqaz, xüsusən də Azərbaycan, onun təbiəti və insanları yazığının ürəyində dərin iz salır. “Nə olaydı mənə bu yerə bir də gəlmək qismət olaydı” - deyir.

“Qafqaza səyahət” kitabında xalqımızın təbii sərvətləri, tarixi abidələri haqqında maraqlı məlumatlar verən yazıçı, eyni zamanda azərbaycanlıların həssas, mehriban, zəkalı, qayğıkeş, qonaqpərvər, sözübütöv, mərd, işgüzar, yaraşlıq, gözəl olduqlarından xüsusi bəhs edir. Dümanın Azərbaycan haqqında müsbət fikirlərinin formalaşmasında Xan qızı Natəvanın rolu danılmazdır. Dümaya görə “Elə xalqların adamları var ki, öz əli ilə imza qoyduğu, möhür vurduğu sənəddən belə boyun qaçırır. Azərbaycanlılarda isə kişi sözü var. Onlarla bir şey barədə sövdələşəndə sənəd, imza, möhür tələb etmək lazım deyil. Azərbaycanlılar verdiyi sözdən heç vaxt dönməz”. Azərbaycan dilinin əhəmiyyətindən söz açdıqda isə o demişdir: "Avropada fransız dili necə əhəmiyyətlidirsə, Qafqazda da Azərbaycan dili o cür əhəmiyyətlidir".

Dünya şöhrətli digər bir fransız yazıçısı Jül Vernin "Klodius Bombarnak" kitabında müəllif qəhrəmanın diliylə Azərbaycanın təbii mənzərəsinə heyran qaldığını, aşiq olduğunu söyləmişdir.

2. AZƏRBAYCAN-FRANSA ƏDƏBİ ƏLAQƏLƏRİ İNKİŞAFI TARİXİ

Azərbaycan-Fransa mədəni əlaqələrinin təşəkkülündə M.A.Şahtaxtinski, C.Hacıbəyov və Ə.Topçubaşovun xidmətləri xüsusi qeyd edilməlidir. Təhsilini Fransada alan Şahtaxtinski, C. Hacıbəyov Azərbaycan tarixi və mədəniyyəti ilə bağlı kitablarını məhz fransız dilində çap etdirmişlər. 1911-ci ildə "Kaspi" qəzetində "Azərbaycan günləri" adlı məqaləsini dərc etdirən C.Hacıbəyov sonradan onu ayrıca kitab şəklində fransız dilində Parisdə nəşr etdirmişdir.

1918-ci ildə Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyətinin yaradılması ilə Azərbaycan-Fransa münasibətləri rəsmi status qazanır. Azərbaycan nümayəndə heyətinin Fransaya ilk səfəri 1919-cu ildə Paris şəhərində keçirilən Paris Sülh Konfransı zamanı baş tutur. Paris Sülh Konfransında əldə edilən diplomatik uğurun nəticəsi olaraq 1920-ci ilin əvvəllərində Bakıda Fransanın nümayəndəliyi açılır. Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyətinin maliyyə yardımı ilə 100 nəfərə yaxın tələbə Avropa ölkələrinə təhsil almağa göndərilir ki, onlardan 42 nəfəri Fransanın müxtəlif şəhərlərində təhsil almışdılar. Fransa-Azərbaycan ədəbi əlaqələri tarixində dəyərli faktlar çoxdur.

1925-ci ildə Parisdə fransız dilində "Arşın mal alan" komediyası tamaşaya qoyuldu. Komediyanı fransız dilinə Ceyhun Hacıbəyli tərcümə etmişdi. Parisdə "Azərbaycan" adlı jurnalın nəşr edilməsi də mühüm mədəni hadisələrdən biri idi. Jurnal "Müsəvat" partiyasının nəşri kimi 1926-cı ilin oktyabrından çapa başlamışdı.

1925-ci ilin 4 iyununda Parisdə təhsil alan azərbaycanlı tələbələrin səyi nəticəsində şəhərin Femia Teatrı səhnəsində də fransız dilində "Arşın mal alan" komediyası təkrar tamaşaya qoyuldu. Parisdə İren xanım kimi tanınan Ümmül Banunun Fransa-Azərbaycan mədəni əlaqələrinin formalaşmasında xüsusi rolu olmuşdur. Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti hökumətinin ticarət naziri Mirzə Əsədullayevin qızı Ümmül Banu hələ 19 yaşında ikən (1924-cü ildə) Fransaya getmişdi. Fransızca yazan müəllif xalqı, doğma mədəniyyəti haqqında avropalıları məlumatlandırır. Onun "Qafqaz günləri", "Yad Fransa", "Paris günləri" əsərləri fransızlara çox yaxşı məlumdur. “Les Fleurs de l’Azerbaïdjan” (Azərbaycan çiçəkləri), yəni “Azərbaycanın şairə qadınları” adlı məqalə “Müsəlman aləmi” adlı (Revue du Monde Müsülman) jurnalında çap olunmuşdur. Bu məqalədə IX-X əsrdə Qafqazda yaşayan Ağabəyim ağa, Aşiq Pəri, Gövhər ağa, Fatma xanım Kəminə,

Xurşudbanu Natavan kimi şairələr haqqında məlumatlar verilir: "Fatma xanım Kəminə çox talantlı, uzaqgörən, ağıllı parlaq bir Azərbaycan şairəsidir. Onun XIX əsr Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatında öz layiqli yeri var".

Azərbaycanda V.Hüqo, J.Vern, A.Düma, Mopassan, Molyer və başqa fransız yazıçı və şairələrinin əsərləri istər orijinaldan, istərsə də, tərcümədən oxucularımız tərəfindən sevilə-sevilə oxunur. Fransa mədəni əlaqələri sahəsində yazıçılarla görüş, mübadilə formalarına daha çox üstünlük verilirdi. Məşhur fransız yazıçısı Anri Barbüsün 1927-ci ildə Azərbaycana gəlişi Azərbaycan-Fransa mədəni əlaqələrinin yeni kontekstdən inkişafında mühüm rol oynadı. Bakı haqqında təəssüratlarını görkəmli yazıçı özünün "Neft ölkəsində" adlı məqaləsində bu şəkildə ifadə etmişdir: "Əgər məndən sovet hakimiyyətinin həyata keçirdiyi, yaratdığı ən təəccüblü, heyranedicilik işləri haqda soruşsalar, onda mən belə cavab verərdim: Bakıya baxın!". Fransanın ictimai xadimi Andre Malro da Fransanın mədəniyyət işləri üzrə dövlət naziri kimi Azərbaycan - Fransa arasında mədəni əməkdaşlığın hökumətlərarası və dövlətlərarası səviyyədə inkişafına mühüm töhfələr vermişdi.

Əhmədiyyə Cəbraylov, Mirzəxan Məmmədov, Hüseyn Rza Məmmədov və bunlardan başqa 30-a yaxın həmyerlimizlə fransız əsgərləri arasındakı hərbi işgüzar münasibətlər II Dünya müharibəsindən sonra hər iki ölkənin siyasi, iqtisadi, eləcə də mədəni əlaqələrinin davam etdirilməsinə çox böyük təsir göstərmişdir. II Dünya müharibəsindən sonra Fransada Azərbaycan, onun qədim mədəniyyətinin öyrənilməsinə maraq gücləndi. Elə bu illər Fransanın "Vedi Kartlisa" adlı jurnalında Azərbaycan ensiklopediyasının nəşri haqqında məlumat yayılmışdı.

3. NƏTİCƏ

Tarixi faktlar Azərbaycan-Fransa mədəni əlaqə elementlərinin qədim olduğunu sübut etsə də, bu əlaqələrin dinamik inkişafı yeni tarixi dövrdə baş tutmuşdur. Fransa Azərbaycanın müstəqilliyini tanıyan ikinci dövlətdir (31 dekabr 1991-ci il) və öz səfirliyini Bakıda 1992-ci ildə açmışdır. İkitərəfli əlaqələr çoxsaylı səfərlərlə zəngindir. Mərhum Prezidentimiz Heydər Əliyev və Prezident İlham Əliyev prezident kimi ilk ikitərəfli səfərlərini məhz Parisə etmişdir. Azərbaycan Fransanın Cənubi Qafqazda əsas ticarət tərəfdaşdır. Fransa ilə ticarət dövriyyəimiz iki milyard dollara yaxınlaşır.

Fransanın Azərbaycandakı səfiri Zaxari Qross ilə Azərbaycanda Fransa İnstitutunun direktoru Moris Rufin dekabrın 16-da Dövlət Tərcümə Mərkəzində olublar. Görüş zamanı iki ölkə arasında ədəbi əlaqələr, perspektiv layihələr ətrafında fikir mübadiləsi aparılıb. Bu il fransız dilinə çevrilərək Strasburqda nəşr edilmiş "Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı antologiyası", həmçinin Jan Anuy, Şarl Bodler, Pol Verlen, Andre Morua, Alber Kamyu, Fransua Moriak, Artur Rembo kimi tanınmış fransız yazıçı və şairlərinin əsərlərinin müxtəlif illərdə Azərbaycan dilində nəşri ilə bağlı məlumat verilib. Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatının Fransada tanınması və yayımı, eləcə də Fransa ədəbiyyatı ilə Azərbaycan oxucusunun tanış edilməsi istiqamətində nəzərdə tutulan layihələr müzakirə edilib. Görüşün sonunda səfirə Dövlət Tərcümə Mərkəzinin son nəşrlərindən olan A.Moruanın "Vəsiyyətnamə" kitabı hədiyyə edilib.

Fransa Azərbaycan əlaqələrindən danışmaq, onun tədqiqatçılarını diqqətlə izləmək və oxumaqla əmin oluruq ki, hər iki xalqın ədəbiyyatı çox zəngin tarixə və görkəmli şəxsiyyətlərə malikdir.

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ŞƏKI-ZAQATALA REGIONU FOLKLORUNDA ÖLÜM VƏ QORXU MOTİVLƏRİ VƏ OBRAZLARI

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ABSTRACT

The major theme of Azerbaijani fairy tales frequently revolves around magic, which is a subset of folklore. Black magic is defined as magic that does harm to others. White magic can be used to access divine power or acquire lofty understanding. Grey magic is all other forms of magic. Witches cast spells that fall under the category of grey magic. Grey magic is the spell employed to achieve success in your profession, love life, and at work. It is not sinful if used in a safe environment and without causing harm to others. Numerous tales and stories from Azerbaijani folklore that feature horrific and soulful themes involved in this study. Ancient faiths provided the foundation for a number of beliefs, customs, and proverbs that have evolved into what they are today. There was a widespread belief in magic and sorcery throughout Azerbaijan in the middle ages. Magic was based on the widely held belief that there existed unseen, supernatural forces that had the ability to influence human events, both positively and badly. Magic required making an effort to use these abilities for one's own gain. The official theology and what was practiced by the majority of people differed significantly, notwithstanding the mosques' efforts to refute magical practices. Early modern commoners saw an intriguing interplay between magic and religion, and occasionally they would seek out specific spiritual and magical healers who had expertise in a wide range of helpful magical services. The Sheki-Zaqatala region of ancient Azerbaijan appears to have been a hotbed of sorcery practice and belief and it was prominent in the Azerbaijani cultures of antiquity. The region is also well-known for its anti-witchcraft ritual history.

Keywords: magic, spiritual and magical healers, supernatural forces, belief, magical images

1. GİRİŞ

Sehr bir çox növ rituallarda, qədim xalq təbabəti düsturlarında və pis əlamətlərə qarşı durmaq üçün istifadə olunurdu. Müdafiə və ya qanuni magiya spesifik reallıqları dəyişdirmək üçün nəzərdə tutulmuş sehrlər və ritual təcrübələr idi. Şəki-zaqatala regionunda yaşayan qədim azərbaycanlılar inanırdılar ki, sehr, əfsun və cadu cinlərə, ruhlara və pis sehrbazlara qarşı yeganə etibarlı müdafiədir. Zülm etdikləri insanların ruhlarından qorunmaq üçün, onları sakitləşdirmək ümidi ilə ritual keçirir və evdə plov bişirir, ölünün adına düz salır və bir qaba çəkib kənara qoyurdular ki, ruh onu yeyib sakitləşsin və evdən getsin. Əgər bu da uğursuz olarsa, onlar bəzən mərhumun əşyalarını torpağa basdırırdılar, tanrılardan ruh onlardan uzaqlaşdırması və onu insanı rahat buraxmağa məcbur etməsi üçün dualar edirdilər.

Bölgədə yaşayan qədim azərbaycanlılar onları lənətləyə biləcək pis sehrbazlardan qorunmaq üçün əfsunlardan istifadə edirdilər. Lənətlərin gizli şəkildə səsləndirilir, sehrbazlığa qarşı müdafiə isə adamın qarşısında aparılırdı. Sehrbazı cəzalandırmaq üçün cadudan əziyyət çəkən şəxs

sehrbazın surətini yaradıb gecə onu mühakimə edər, sonra həmin şəxs onu yandırır və bununla da sehrbazın onların üzərindəki hakimiyətini qırılmasına inanırdılar.

Xurafat bütün zamanlarda insanların məişətinə güclü təsir edən bir vasitədir. O, bizim ən böyük qorxu və istəklərimizə toxunur və bizim məntiqi düşüncəmizi asanlıqla məğlub edir. Onlar qədim zamanlardan sivilizasiyamızın əsasında olmuş və mədəniyyətimizdə dərin kök salmışdır. Bu müdrüklük və maarifçilik əsrində belə, bir çoxumuz şüuraltımızın ən dərin qatlarında pıçıldayan beynimizdəki məntiqsiz səsə qulaq asmaya bilmirik. *“Bir çimdik duzu çiyinizdən atın”*. *“Nərdivanın altından keçmə”*. *Evdə fit çalma”*. *“Cümə ayının 13-dür - çox diqqətli olun”*. *“Qara pişiyin yolunuzu keçməsinə imkan verməyin”*. *“Qara hörümçəyi öldürün!”*

Yerli əhali bilmədən etdikləri günahlardan təmizləmək üçün sehrli ayınlar yerinə yetirirdilər. Belə rituallardan biri Sırr daş vasitəsi ilə həyata keçirilirdi. Bu mərasimdə bütün əməllərini sırr daşına nəql edir və günahı özündən atmaq üçün sabun, soğan və digər müxtəlif əşyalara üzərinə köçürürdü. Sonra həmin şəxs arındığına inanırdı. Bütün sevgi sehləri bir insanın başqa bir insana aşiq olmasına, sönmüş sevgini bərpa etməsinə səbəb olduğuna inanılırdı. Bunun üçün müqəddəs hesab edilən ağacın yarpağına sevdii insanın və özünün adını yazır və onu gizli yerə qoyurdular. Niyyəti baş tutduqdan sonra həmin yarpağı yandırır və külünü gül dibinə atırdılar. (1)

Araxnofobiya dünyada ən çox yayılmış qorxular siyahısına başçılıq edir. Hörümçəkdən qorxu ehtimalınız o qədər yaygındır ki, əgər mövhumatçısınızsa, yəqin ki, hörümçəyi öldürməyin uğursuzluq olduğunu bilirsiniz. Qorxunuza baxmayaraq, onu tutmağa və evinizdən təhlükəsiz şəkildə çıxarmağa çalışacaqsız. Onlar haqqında bütün canlılardan daha çox xurafat müşahidə olunur. Biz insanlar həmişə qorxularımızla üz-üzə gəlməyə həvəsli oluruq və hörümçəyə uğurlar simvolu kimi baxmaq bizi məhz bunu etməyə məcbur edir.

Şəki-Zaqatala Regionundan qələmə alınan folklor örnəklərində xurafat və əfsanəvi cadugərlik konsepsiyası ilə ilahiyyat arasında oxşar cəhətlər vardır. Magiya qədim zamanlarda Küpəgirən qarılar tərəfindən yerinə yetirilirdi. Onlar təbiətən çox oxşardırlar. Dünyada böyük dəyişikliklərin vaxtı çatanda peyğəmbərlik peyda olmuş və insanlar inanmışlar ki, həyatlarında olan bizi əzab və çətinliklərdən qurtaracaq, yeni, təmiz və günahsız dünya yaranacaq.

XV əsrdə cadugərin nə və kim ola biləcəyi anlayışı dəyişməyə başladı. Cadugər süpürgə ilə şənbə günlərinə uçan şeytani təriqətin üzvü idi, kənarda qalan, çirkin və ya eybəcər və davranış və ya görünüşdə itaətsiz aşağı səviyyəli bir insanın, çox güman ki, qadın. Nəzəriyyədə hər kəs cadugər ola bilərdi, amma praktikada ən çox günahlandırılan kəndli qadınlar idi, onlar təhsili, sosial vəziyyəti və ya pul sərvəti az olan ən həssas qadınlar idi.

İbn Sinanın “Əl qanun” kitabı var ki, bu gün Avropa institutlarında ondan akademik vəsait kimi istifadə olunur. Həmin kitabda tibbdən bəhs olunsa da, onun 30 faizi cadu və tilsimlərin insan səhhətinə təsirlərindən qeyd olunur. Bu məsələ bir növ insanlara psixoloji təsir vasitəsidir.

XX əsrdə xalq arasında cadukün kimi tanınan cadugər populyar mədəniyyətdə təmsil olunurdu, lakin böyük dəyişikliklər baş vermişdi. Onlar ailə dağdır, insanın canına cin daraşdırır, xəstələndirir, evin aurasını pisləşdirirdi.

XXI əsrdə də cəmiyyət ibtidai inanclar sistemini inkar etmir, lakin onu dogmaya çevirmək düzgün deyil. Müasir dünyada falçılar sosial şəbəkələr vasitəsilə insanların falına baxır, bərəkət duası, sevgi, qovuşma və ayrılıq kimi məsələlərə dair cadu hazırladıqlarını bildirirlər. Müasir dövrün cadugərləri gördükləri işin qarşılığında pulu da kart vasitəsilə alırlar. Bəzi insanlar baxıcı-cadugərlərin bu yolla onları aldatdıqlarını, pullarını, qiymətli əşyalarını əllərindən aldıqlarını deyirlər. Bəziləri isə müqəddəs kitablarda belə cadunun və cadugərliyin olmasını əsas gətirərək caduya və onun təsirinə inanırlar. Maraqlıdır ki, cadugərlərə orta əsrlərin nə inkvizisiyası dərs oldu, nə də onlara nifrət edən insanlarda mərhəmət yaratdı. Cəmiyyətdə onları sevməyən, onların əməllərindən bezən və qorxan bir çox insanlar hələ də belə pis əməlli insanlara cəza verilməsində maraqlıdır. Lakin heç bir dinə boyun əyməyən, cəzalardan qorxmayan bu “ölməyən” sənət bəlkə də texniki tərəqqi dövrünə məhəl qoymadan öz qanunları ilə işləyən yeganə sənətdir.

Şəhər və kəndlərdə “sehrli şam”lar satılan mağazalar fəaliyyət göstərir. İddia olunur ki, həmin şamlar müxtəlif arzuların həyata keçməsində rol oynayır və yaxud “göz dəyməsi”nin qarşısını alır, evə edilən cadu və sehri təmizləyir. Şamların qiyməti adi şamların qiymətindən dəfələrlə bahadır. Əsasən İsrail və Rusiyadan gətirildiyi iddia olunan şamlar 35-40 manata satılır.

İnsanlar qəbiristanlıqlarda, evin baxçasından, yataq otağından, paltar dolabından, hamam otağından sehirli sözlər yazılmış cadular tapırlar. Cadugərlər tərəfindən ərəb dilində müxtəlif adlar yazılmış və "qurd yağı" töküldüyü iddia edilən əşyalar kiminsə bəxtini, taleyini bağlamaq və ya ona pislik etmək məqsədi ilə torpağa basdırılır.

Bəzən cadu ilə duaları qarışdırırlar. İnsanlara zərər vermək üçün "qurd yağı", heyvan dərisi, qıfıl, insanın baş tükü, dırnağı, şəkli, paltarı və ya digər vasitələrdən istifadə olunur. Onların üzərinə sehirli ovsunlar yazılır. Keçmiş zamanlarda insanlar qızıl sərvətlərini torpaqda gizlədir, üstünə dualar yazılırdı ki, xəzinəni cinlər qorusun. Bu səbəbdən də xəzinəni tapan insanlar peşman olurdu, çünki cinlər onlara zərər verir və qızılı götürən adam dəli olurdu. Ona görə də belə bir ritual həyata keçirirdilər: xəzinə tapan insan ondan bir ovuc götürüb başının üstündə tullamalındı ki, ona sədəmə toxunmasın.

Bəzi cadukünlər Ölüm cadusu ilə də məşğul olur ki, guya tibb də onun qarşısında çox acizdir və həkimlər belə xəstənin dərini tapa bilmirlər. Ölüm cadularının çoxu qəbiristanlıqda təmizlənir. İnsanlar caduları üzə çıxarmaq üçün bilicilərin yanına gedirlər. Bilicilər, cadugərlərdən fərqli olaraq, xeyrixah hesab olunurlar. Onlar insanın özündə axan su ilə onları təmizləyirlər Hətta bu günə qədər kiçik kəndlərdən tutmuş şəhərlərə kimi evdə saxsı qab qırılırsa, cadugərləri günahlandırır və sevinirlər ki, cadu qırıldı. Heç bir dinə tabe olmayan, cəzadan qorxmayan bu “ölməz” sənət bəlkə də yeganə peşədir ki, texniki tərəqqi çağına məhəl qoymayaraq öz qanunları ilə işləyir. Cəmiyyət isə düşünür ki, bu insanlar cəhənnəm odunda yanacaqlar.

Cadugərlər müxtəlif metod və vasitələrdən istifadə etməklə güclərini müsbət yönə də sərf edir, mənfi yönə də. Cadugərlər çox vaxt ikinci yola üstünlük verirlər, çünki sərvəti pislik etməklə daha sürətlə qazanırlar. Beləliklə, öz gücləri vasitəsilə enerji daşıyıcısı olan müxtəlif əşyalardan, bitki və heyvan mənşəli ləvazimatlardan, əlaqəyə girdikləri mənfi enerji dalğalarından yararlanaraq, ovuna təsir edirlər. Bir sözlə artıq öz ruhlarını şeytana sataraq, onun nökrinə çevrilirlər. Bəzən hətta səhvlərini sonradan başa düşüb, tövbə etsələr də, şeytan onları rahat buraxmır, müxtəlif yollarla insanlara pisliyini davam etdirmələrini tələb edir.

Dünyada ağ və qara magiya kimi tanınan cadugərlikdə, qara magiya pisniyyətli insanların əməllərindən yaranmış simvolik qara buluda bənzədilir. Həmin bulud insanın ətrafındakı rəngbərəng auraya çirkab kimi yapışmış qalır. Getdikcə həmin çirkablar artır, qalınlaşır və insanın həyatında problemlər, əngəllər, maneələr yaranır. Yəni şəffaf rəngbərəng aura vasitəsilə insana ötürülən müsbət maddi-mənəvi enerjilər qara buluda ilişir və insana çata bilmir. Beləliklə də insanın dolanışığında, planlarında, həyatında, mənəviyyatında və sair ciddi əngəllər meydana çıxır.

Ağ magiya ilə məşğul olan insanlar isə müxtəlif dualar və ayinlər vasitəsilə həmin aurayı təmizləyir, qara buludu dağıdır və insanın yollarını açırlar. Bu baxımdan ağ magiyanı haradasa xoşniyyətli cadugərlik kimi qeyd edə bilərik. Hər ikisinin də metodları, yararlandığı vasitələr eyni olur, amma məqdəs fərqlidir. Kəmiyyət və say baxımından qara, keyfiyyət və güc baxımından ağ magiya üstündür.

Bu gün qara magiya daha fəal və güclüdür. Get-gedə insanlar mənfiyə meyillənirlər, bu sahədə məktəblər yaradılır, elm öyrədilir, bir sözlə şeytanlaşma gedir. Lakin Allahın lütfündən hər bir ölkədə, toplumda güclü müsbət auraya və energetikaya malik insanlar olur. Bəzən onlar özləri belə daşıdıqları ali missiyadan xəbərsiz olurlar. Amma məhz onların təsirindəndir ki, qara magiya bəşəriyyəti tamamilə məhv edə bilmir. Yəni istər ayrı-ayrı toplumlar, istərsə də ümumi dünya hansısa sütunların - seçilmiş insanların mövcudluğuna xatir bəlalardan hifz olunur. (1)

Şəki-Zaqatala bölgəsində bir-çox falçı-gadugərlər indi də mövcuddur və onlar müxtəlif vasitələrdən istifadə etmək insanlara cadu edir, tilsimdən çıxarır, tilsimə salır, əşyalardan və otlardan istifadə edərək insanlara sehr-cadu edirlər.

Cadugərlərin gücü həqiqətən mövcud olduğu qəbul edilən fəvqəltəbii qüvvələr kütləsindən yalnız biri idi. Dünyanın bu anlayışını nəzərə alaraq, sehrli sayıla biləcək təcrübələr gündəlik həyatda çox yayılmışdı. İnsanlar sehrli prosedurlardan - çox vaxt valideynləri tərəfindən onlara öyrədilmiş - çoxsaylı məqsədlər üçün istifadə edirdilər. Onlar əlamətlərə və əlamətlərə inanırdılar. Sehrli elementləri əhatə edən ənənəvi mərasimlər və ayinlər də mal-qaranın və əkinlərin qorunması və rifahı üçün istifadə olunurdu (5, 194). Bədbəxtlikdən yan keçmək, xəstəlikləri sağaltmaq və ya pis cadugərlikdən qorunmaq üçün onlar müxtəlif sehrlərdən istifadə edirdilər. və cazibələr. Hər bir xəstəlik üçün sehrli bir həll mövcud idi, belə ki, sehr gündəlik həyatın əksər aspektlərində işləyirdi və "xüsusi ehtiyac olduğu hallarda [insanlar] bu sənətlərdə xüsusi bacarıq və ya biliyə malik olan şəfaçılara, hiyləgər xalqa və ya peşəkar falçılara müraciət edə bilirdi."

2. ŞƏKI-ZAQATAL BÖLGƏSİNİN FOLKLORUNDA FƏVQƏLTƏBII GÜCLƏR VƏ KABUS OBRAZLARI

Biz ətrafımızdakı dəyişikliklərin təsirini görürük. Havanın, suyun çirklənməsi, yerdə dəfn edilmiş zəhərli tullantılar, dəniz nüvə radiasiyasının sızmaları, tropik meşələrin dağıntısı, qoruyucu ozon qatının azalması, fəvqəladə və dəhşətli təbiət hadisələri və ilaxir. Bizim hər birimiz bilir ki, bu belə davam edə bilməz, lakin bilmirik ki, bu çirklənmə axını necə saxlayaq. Halbuki, qədim inanclar və təlimatlar yer, bitki və heyvanlar aləmi arasındakı balans müvəffəqiyyətlə saxlaya bilmişdir.

Sehrli, sirli və çox güman ki, mifik sehrbazlara bir çox nağıllarda arst gəlirik ki, onlar inanc, ovsun, ağızbağlama, xəstəlikqaytarma, təbiət hadisələrinə (yağış yağdırma, günü çağırma, bədnəzərdən qorunma) təsir gücünə malikdirlər.

Nağıllarda cadugərlər cadu ilə məşğul olan, sehrli gücə malik şifahi formulalardan istifadə edən və ruhları kömək və ya dəyişiklik üçün çağıran insanlar idi. Onlar ritual zamanı ruhani təsire malik olduğuna inanılan sözləri bərkədən deyir və ya səslər çıxarırdılar. İnsanlar düşünürdü ki, cadugərlərin əksəriyyəti İblisin işini görən büt-pərəstlərdir. Ancaq onların bəzisi xəstələrə sadəcə təbii otlar və vasitələrlə müalicə edərək sağaltmağa çalışan və ya peşə seçimi səhv başa düşülən "müdrək qadınlar" idi.

Azərbaycan mədəniyyətində **Küpəgirən Qarı**, şəri, qaranlığı, xaosu və münaqişəni təmsil edir. Onlar insan həyatı üçün istifadə etdikləri təhlükəli sehri xeyirxah və ya düzgün hesab edərək əxlaq hissini pozmuş kimi görünürlər. "Göyçək Fatma" nağılında cadugərin siması "Fatma evə girib gördü ki, burada bir heybətli qarı oturub, alt dodağı yer süpürür, üst dodağı göy. Qarı qabağına bir qurbağa qoyub onu sığallayır." (8) təsvir edilir. Cadugər Fatmanın cavablarından razı qaldığı üçün onu mükafatlandırır. "Gedərsən, qabağına bir ağ su, bir qara su və sonra bir qırmızı su çıxacaq. Ağ suda çimərsən, qara su ilə saçını yuyarsan, qırmızı sudan yanaqlarına sürtərsən. Bir də qarı öz tükündən verdi və dedi ki, mən sənə lazım olsam, yandırarsan, yanında hazır olaram." (8)

Cadugərin ən bariz xüsusiyyəti sehr etmək bacarığı idi, sehrli hərəkəti həyata keçirmək üçün müəyyən vasitələrdən istifadə etməklə söz "sehr" ifadələr işlədirdi və ilan, qurbağa, pişik, bayquş onun əmrlərini yerinə yetirən əsgərləridi. (4. 297). Sehr bir sıra sözlərdən, düsturdan və ya ayədən, ritual hərəkətdən və ya bunların hər hansı birləşməsindən ibarət olurdu. Erkən Azərbaycan ənənəsində cadugərlər yalnız qadınlara aid olmasa da, stereotip idi. Cadu lənət olduğu üçün müəyyən vaxtdan sonra onu etdirənlərin özünə bir gün qayıdacaq. Cadunu təmizləmə ritualı əslində onu etdirənə geri qaytarmağa xidmət edir.

Qara pişik cadugərin əsgəri kimi mistik heyvan hesab edilir və baş verə biləcək hər hansı xoşagəlməz hadisələr barədə öncədən xəbərdarlığın simvoludur. Xalq təfəkküründə sınınmış bu amil qara pişiyi az qala düşmən elan edib, insanlar onu öldürməyə çalışırlar. İnanclara görə Qara pişik mənfi enerjini başqalarında daha tez duyur. Qara pişik hansısa bir məkanda olursa, deməli orada mənfi enerji zonası var həmin zonada daimi məskən salmaq, yataq otağı yaratmaq məsləhət görülmür. Belə ki, inanclarda deyilir ki, Yer kürəsi gözlə görülməyən şaquli və üfiqi xəttlərin yaratdığı qəfəslə örtülüb. Həmin xətlərin kəsişdiyi nöqtələrdə insanların yuva salması, ev tikməsi, uzun müddət qalması düzgün deyil və gələcəkdə orada mövcud olan mənfi enerjiden doğan ciddi fəsadlar meydana çıxır. Qara pişiklərdə duyum qabiliyyəti digər növlərə nisbətən daha güclü olduğundan, onlar həmin kəsişmə nöqtələrinin daşdığı ağırlığı hiss edirlər və orada məskən salmaqla, insanlara işarə vermiş olurlar. Bu məsələ sırf elmi anlayışdır və inkişaf etmiş ölkələrdə həmin kəsişmə nöqtələrini ciddi araşdırır və çox həssas yanaşırlar.

Şəki-Zaqatala bölgəsində bayquş da cadugərin əsgəridir və onun ulaması qaçılmaz ölüm əlaməti kimi qəbul edilirdi, ölümü qabaqcadan xəbər verməsi kimi qəbul edilmişdir. Lakin Şəki-Zaqata bölgəsində başqa bir mövhumata inanırlar ki, bəzi aktivitələr evinizin qapısına ölü bayquşu mismarlamaqla ölümün qarşısını almaq olar, ki, bu da pislikdən çəkindirər. Bayquşun “ayağını kəsmək” üçün siniyə (məcməiyə) su, çörək, duz qoyaraq ucadan deyirlər: *Bay quşu, Baylar quşu, Al payını, Uzaqlaş Bay quşu* (6. 65)

Hörümçək həm kəskin intellektinə görə heyranlıq, həm də ürpertici qəribəliyi və yırtıcı davranışına qarşı ikrah hissi yaradan valehedici bir qaynaq olmuşdur. Azərbaycan mifologiyasında və teologiyasında hörümçək simvolizminin nümunələri mövcuddur. Dəfələrlə zəhmətkeşlik, səbir, hiyləgərlik, fitnə-fəsad və bədxahlıqla əlaqələndirilmişdir ki, bunların hamısı nəsil-dən-nəslə ötürülən şifahi ənənələrə, nağıllara və xalq yaradıcılığına töhfə vermiş və bu gün bizə tanış olan bir çox xurafatların əsasına çevrilmişdir.

Yaşlı, tənha və çox çirkin simalı qadınlar xalq inanclarının və nağıllarını əsas sakinləridirlər. Ən məşhur nümunə **Kabusağıcı** qadındır. (3. 283) O, qarabasma şəklində uşaqların və böyüklərin gözünə görünür. Nağılda kabus qadın hündürboylu, arıq və qəddar baxışlıdır. Saçları pırtlaşlıq və səliqəsiz şəkildə üz-gözünə dağılır və baxışları təhlükə saçır. Həmişə evin küncələrindən çıxır və başını sürətli hərəkətlə aşağı-yuxarı hərəkət etdirməklə rəqs edir. Rəqs zamanı insana arxasını çevirir və qorxudan dili tutulan adam danışmaq istərkən çevrilib qəzəblə baxar və əllərini dodaqlarının üzərinə qoyub susmağı tələb edər. Kabusağıcı yalnız bədən dilində danışardı, işarələrlə insanları qandırır. Sevmədiyi ailə mehriban ailə idi, spesifik ailələrə sıx bağlı idi və bəzən onlara arzu edilməyən sürprizlər edirdi. Əgər ailə onun hündürdən ağlamağını, və ya çığırmağını eşitsə idi, demək həmin gecə ailənin hər hansı bir üzvü öləcəkmiş. İnsanlar ondan bərk qorxur, qorunmaq üçün müxtəlif vasitələrə əl atırdılar; ev dəyişdirir, evin küncələrindən dualar və simvolik qoruyucu əşyalar: maral buynuzu, keçi buynuzu, heyvan dərisi asırdılar. Belə əşyaların bir ucu iti olurdu.

Azərbaycanın bütün bölgələrində, yeni doğum etmiş qadınlara görünən, onların qorxmasına, xəstə olmasına, hətta ölmələrinə səbəb olan **Alanası, Alarvad** adlandırılan ölüm mələyi var ki, o da bəzi qaynaqlarda sarışın qız kimi təsvir edilir. Lakin Şəki –Zaqatala bölgəsində yaşayan bir çox qadın onun xarici görkəmini təsvir edərək onu hündürboylu, uzun ağı saçları bütün bədənini yayılmış, çılpaq və iri sinəsi göbəyinə qədər uzanan çirkin qadın kimi təsvir edir. Əsasən hamilə qadınlara musallat olan Alarvadı onların gözünə görünür, gecələr yuxusuna girib həyatə çağırır. bu haqda görkəmli folklorşünas M. Seyidova da öz araşdırmalarında ətraflı yazmışdır. (4, s.183) Kabusun xarici görkəmi bölgə əhvalatlarında qorxulu və çirkin təsvir edilsə də, Seyidovun araşdırmasına görə “Alarvadı-uca, yüksək arvad, Günəşdir.” “həyatın, kainatın yaradıcısı, eləcə də labüd ölümün başlanğıcıdır.” (4, s. 184). Bölgə folklorunda evlərdə ürək formasında tünd göyə çalanan rəngli daşı divardan asaraq onun evə girməsinin qarşısını aldıklarına inanırdılar. Alarvadı yeni doğum etmiş qadınlara müsəllət olar, ciyərinə söküb yeyir qadının ölümünə səbəb olar.

Qadınlar bu varlıqdan qorunmaq üçün yastıqlarına, baş örtülərinin, paltarlarının bir yerinə iynə və ya sancaq sancardılar. Yeni doğum etmiş qadının yatağının ətrafına yundən hörülən iplik, qifil asılırdı.

Keçisaqqal, Haçasaqqal, Qırmızısaqqal, Mavi saqqal (3. 286) uşaq nağıllarının super gücləridir. Onlar Azərbaycan folklorunda evlərin çardağında yaşayır, gecələr evə girir, səs-küy yaradır və uşaqları qorxuzurdu.

Çincinə (3. 286) adlı qadın gecələr peyda olur, əcaib hərəkətləri ilə insanı qorxuzur, evin küncülərində rəqs edir və öz çirkin sifəti ilə uşaqları qorxuzur ki, nəticədə azyaşlı uşaqlarda qorxudan müxtəlif psixoloji problemlər yaradır.

Tüklübaş (3. 286) "Tüklübaşın nağılı" əhvalatında isə bütün varlığı yalnız bir tüklü başdan ibarət və gözləri qıpqırmızı olan, qəhqəhə ilə gülən vahiməli varlığın insanları qorxuzması təsvir edilir. Bu bəd-heybətli yaşayış məskəni qəbiristanlıqdır və cildən-cildə girməyi bacarırlar.

Bölgədə **Vurğun** adlandırılan bədxah cin Türk, Anadolu və Altay xalq mədəniyyətində Urgun, Orğun və ya Vurğun kimi məşhurdur. O, oddan yaradılmışdır. Tək-tənha olaraq əsasən, zoğal, əncir, fındıq ağaclarının altında və su kənarında yaşayan gözə görünməz cin insanı pis əməlinə görə vurur, hətta öldürür. Bu ağacların altında gecə vaxtı yatmaq, iş görmək, paltar yumaq, zibil atmaq, budaqlarını qırmaq təhlükəli hesab edilir. Çünki qəzəbli Vurğun mütəlak həmin şəxsə xəsarət yetirirdi. Bölgədə ən geniş yayılan qarğışlardan biri də "səni vuğun vursun", "vurğuna rast gələsən" ifadələridir.

Bütün pis ruhlar kimi, qaranlıqdan sonra hərəkətə keçir. İnsanı qaranlıq yerdə və ya sudan keçərkən vurur. (4) Bu cin hücumuna tutulan şəxs bir müddət ölü kimi yatır. Yaxud uzun müddət kar və lal gəzir, yaxud ölür. Vuruşmaq da adlandırılan bu xəstəlik çox təhlükəlidir. Bədəni qarqara qaralır və ya qara şillə peyda olur. Əvvəllər xəstəni Vurğun ocağına aparardılar ki, sağalsın. Bəzən qadın cildində gözə görünürlər. Bəzən qadın cildinə girir. Xalq inancında "Vurğunun güclü gəlsin!" ən ağır lənətlərdən biri hesab olunur.

Korkol adlı qorxulu qadın cildində kabus ruhəmicisi gecə insanlar yatarkən gəlib onların ruhunu əmib gedirlərmiş. Hətta onu gözləri ilə gördüklərini iddia edən insanlar var.

Ərazidə yaşayan folklorunda **xortdanla** bağlı müxtəlif əfsanələr mövcuddur. Xortdan ölmüş insanın yenidən, eybəcər ruh şəklində dirilməsidir. O, insanları qorxuzur, onların ölümünə səbəb olur. Hətta "Xortdan-xortdan" uşaq oyunu əhali arasında son 20 ilə qədər geniş yayılmışdır. Xortdan Ümumtürk mifologiyasında məzardan çıxan ölüdür və həddindən çox arıq, çirkin və qorxulu xarici görkəmi var. Xortdanın cinsiyyəti olmasa da hər iki cinsin cildində görünür. Bəzi Hordtan müəyyən şəhərlərə sahib olan canlı insanlar ola bilər. Xortdanın bəzi xüsusiyyətləri bunlardır: onun heyvana çevrilmə qabiliyyəti, gözəgörünməzliyi və qan impulsu ilə qurbanların qanı ilə qidalanmasıdır. Ancaq qaranlıqda görünür, ən çox da qəbiristanlıqlarda yaşayır. Günəşdən qorxduğu üçün gündüzlər qəbrinə girir və gecələr çıxaraq özünə qida axtarır. O yalnız insanların deyil, heyvanların da qanını içir. Şəki-Zaqatala bölgəsində "Xortdan" uşaq oyunu çox məşhurdur: uşaqlardan biri Xortdan olur və onu yarpaqların arasında dəfn edirlər. Digər uşaqlar onun ətrafında oxuya-oxuya əl çalıb fırlanırlar: "*xortdan baba dursana, durub bizi tutsana, əgər tuta bilməsən, qəbirində yatsana*". Xortdan qəfildən yarpaqların arasında çıxıb uşaqların üzərinə qaçır və ilk tutduğu adam xortdan olaraq yarpaqların arasında sanki dəfn edilir. Beləcə oyun davam edir. Bu oyun əslində təlimat xarakteri daşıyır və uşaqların xortdandan qorxmamasını təbliğ edir. Çünki kiçikyaşlı uşaqları qorxuzmaq üçün xortdan adından hələ də kənd yerlərində istifadə edilir.

Məlum olduğu kimi qədim tarixə və mədəniyyətə malik olan və gündəlik həyatında möhkəm ənənələrə söykənən azərbaycanlı mentalitetində özünü dərkətmə, özünə hörmət, özünükünə yaşatmaq amilləri vardır. Tarix qədər qədim Şəki əhalisinin əsrlər boyu dünyagörüşündə və məişətində milli ənənələrə münasibət xüsusi mühafizəkarlıq qorunur.

3. NƏTİCƏ

Azərbaycanın Şəki-Zaqatala regionundan qələmə alınan folklor örnəklərinin əsas mövzusu tez-tez folklorun böyük bir qrupu olan sehr ətrafında cərəyan edir. Qara sehr başqalarına zərər verən sehr kimi, ağ sehr ilahi gücə çatmaq və ya yüksək anlayış əldə etmək üçün istifadə edilən sehr kimi, boz sehr magiyanın bütün digər formalarıdır. Cadugərlər boz sehr kateqoriyasına daxil olan sehrlər edirlər. Boz sehr fərdin peşəsində, sevgi həyatında və işində uğur qazanmaq üçün istifadə edilən sehrdir və təhlükəsiz bir mühitdə və başqalarına zərər vermədən istifadə edilərsə, günah deyildir. Şəki-Zaqatala region folklorundan dəhşətli və ruhlandırıcı mövzuları özündə əks etdirən çoxsaylı nağıl və hekayələr bu tədqiqatda iştirak edir. Qədim inanclar bir sıra əfsun, sehr, adət-ənənələrin və atalar sözlərinin əsasını qoyub, indiki hallarına çevrilib. Orta əsrlərdə bütün Azərbaycanda sehr və cadugərliyə inanc geniş yayılmışdı. Sehr insan hadisələrinə həm müsbət, həm də pis təsir etmək qabiliyyətinə malik görünməyən, fəvqəltəbii qüvvələrin mövcud olduğuna dair geniş yayılmış inama əsaslanırdı. Sehr, bu qabiliyyətlərdən öz mənfəəti üçün istifadə etmək üçün səy göstərməyi tələb edirdi. Məscidlərin sehrli təcrübələri təkzib etmək səylərinə baxmayaraq, rəsmi ilahiyyət və insanların əksəriyyəti tərəfindən tətbiq edilənlər əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə fərqlənirdi. erkən müasir adi insanlar sehr və din arasında maraqlı qarşılıqlı əlaqəni görürdülər və bəzən onlar müxtəlif faydalı sehrli xidmətlərdə təcrübəyə malik olan xüsusi ruhani və sehrli müalicəçiləri axtarırdılar. Qədim Azərbaycanın Şəki-Zaqatala bölgəsi, görünür, cadugərlik və inanc ocağı olmuş və qədim Azərbaycan mədəniyyətlərində görkəmli yer tutmuşdur. Bölgə həm də cadu əleyhinə ritual tarixi ilə məşhurdur.

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Philological Sciences

Newspapers, tabloids and broadsheets

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Key words: newspapers, image led newspapers, text led newspapers, tabloids, red tops, middle market dailies, broadsheets, newspaper headlines.

Abstract: A newspaper is a printed publication which contains news and content of general and special interest. Newspapers consist of folded sheets that show current news, correspondence, advertisements, and news articles. Newspapers are important sources of precious information in our daily life. The first newspaper was published in Germany by Johann Corolus in 17th century. Nowadays hundred of newspapers are published every day. The newspapers in United Kingdom are divided into two categories: Image led newspapers and text led newspapers. Image led newspapers include tabloids, but text led newspapers include broadsheets. Tabloids are smaller in size than broadsheets and they focus on less “serious” content, especially celebrities, sports, and sensational stories. Broadsheets are standard, full sized newspapers that take serious look at major news stories. Tabloids are popular newspapers and can be subdivided into two groups: 'red tops' and 'middle market' dailies. These newspapers are called 'red tops' because they have red mastheads. The masthead is the large font title at the top of a newspaper front page containing the newspaper's title. The 'red tops' report on politics and international news but tend to include more celebrity gossips and scandals. 'Red tops' write short stories using simple language and they have more pictures than other newspapers. The description 'middle market' refers to the target readership of these newspapers, which is somewhere between the 'red tops' and the 'broadsheets'. Broadsheets are 'quality' newspapers, they have a higher news content than the 'red tops' and broadsheets cost more to buy and have a lower circulation. The style of writing differs from tabloids with longer sentences and paragraphs, and more articles offering in-depth analysis.

Before the age of TVs, Radio, and the internet, newspapers dominated the media. Today, they remain one of the most popular and accessible sources of information. But what is newspaper? A newspaper is a publication that contains news and content of general and special interest. The printed publication comprises folded sheets that display current news, correspondence, advertisements, and articles. This newspaper definition confirms that newspapers are important sources of valuable information in day-to-day life. In addition to this newspaper meaning, it is important to point out that typical newspapers report news and events that have occurred over the last 24 hours.

Generally, the purpose of a newspaper is to inform and efficiently convey current information to the target audience. Examples include The New York Times, The Washington Post, and The Wall Street Journal. Several factors, such as the target audience and topics covered, influenced the circulation and readership of newspapers. Nonetheless, with continued improvement in literacy levels, the circulation and readership of newspapers have increased globally, although their popularity is on a decline due to the advent of the internet.

For nearly 400 years, newspapers have been integral sources of information. Their history goes back to 59BC in the Roman Empire. Rome was not only a strategic city, but also the center of innovation. Historians attribute the emergence and development of inscribed news to the Roman

Acta Diurna (daily public records). The Romans carved updates about military campaigns, executions, competitions, and politics on metal or stone sheets. These carved updates were published on the public forum.

Nonetheless, the establishment of the printing press dates back to 17th century Europe. The first newspaper was published in Germany by Johann Carolus. Soon after, printed newspapers spread to France, the Netherlands, the UK, and Italy.

Initially, newspapers were costly and limited to the elite. However, over the years, the printing press underwent rapid transformations which exploded the printing of newspapers, subsequently reducing prices and making them available to the masses. By the 19th century, newspapers were available to the wider populations of Europe, America, Asia, and the Middle East. The emergence of advertising made newspapers even more popular, and print media expanded globally.

Technology has revolutionized many aspects of modern life, and newspapers are no exception. Recently, newspapers have acknowledged the vital role of technology and are now incorporating broadcast, mobile phone, and internet innovations. Technological development is changing the newspaper industry. For example, smartphones are changing how consumers perceive news and updates. Publishers now send instant information to readers through mobile applications and text messages. Technology has facilitated the growth of online newspapers, which, unlike print newspapers, publish news and updates in electronic documents. Online newspapers allow for quick dissemination of information. Notably, however, print newspapers remain significant because they enable more in-depth analysis and reporting. As such, traditional newspapers make an extended impact on the reader's mind.

Every day hundreds of different newspapers are published. The content and layout of each newspaper reflects its target readership. The newspapers in United Kingdom can be divided into two categories: Image led newspapers and text led newspapers. Image led newspapers include tabloids, however text led newspapers include broadsheets. Tabloids are smaller in size than standard newspapers and they focus on less “serious” content, especially celebrities, sports, and sensational stories. Broadsheets are standard, full sized newspapers that take serious look at major news stories.

Tabloids are popular newspapers and can be subdivided into two groups: 'red tops' and 'middle market' dailies. The 'red tops' are *The Sun*, *Daily Mirror* and *Daily Star* newspapers. These newspapers are called 'red tops' because they have red mastheads. The masthead is the large font title at the top of a newspaper front page containing the newspaper's title. The 'red tops' report on politics and international news but tend to include more celebrity gossips and scandals. 'Red tops' write short stories using simple language and they have more pictures than other newspapers. The 'middle market' dailies are the *Daily Mail* and the *Daily Express* newspapers. The description 'middle market' refers to the target readership of these newspapers, which is somewhere between the 'red tops' and the 'broadsheets'.

Broadsheets are 'quality' newspapers, the top broadsheets are *The Times*, *The Telegraph*, *The Guardian* newspapers. The broadsheets have a higher news content than the 'red tops' and broadsheets cost more to buy and have a lower circulation. The style of writing differs from tabloids with longer sentences and paragraphs, and more articles offering in-depth analysis.

There are a lot of differences between tabloids and broadsheets, so we can compare them easily. Firstly, tabloids contain the mixture of fact and emotion, but broadsheets contain more fact than emotion. Tabloids use shorter sentences, but broadsheets use longer sentences. In tabloids journalists use biased and emotional language, however in broadsheets they use unbiased, impartial and clear language. In tabloids stories are mixed together, but in broadsheets news stories are divided into clear sections. Tabloids use less complex, simple vocabulary, broadsheets

use difficult, complicated vocabulary. Tabloids focus on famous, popular people, their private lives and scandals but broadsheets concentrate on major national and international events. Furthermore, in tabloids and broadsheets the language is used differently. Tabloids use informal language but broadsheets use more formal language. Most of the time tabloids focus on external appearance but broadsheets describe personality of people and their position in society. In tabloids journalists use puns, alliteration, exaggeration for effect, but in broadsheets they use metaphors rather than puns, rhetorical questions as the important stylistic devices. Tabloids use colloquial language, slangs, short, snappy sentences, heightened language, however broadsheets use more complex sentences (separated by lots of commas, semi-colons etc.) Most of the time the names of brands and informal names appear in tabloids, but statistic figures appear in broadsheets. Frequent use of elision such as won't, don't occurs in tabloids. Broadsheets frequently include opinions, ideas of politicians with the commentaries by journalists.

Newspapers are published daily, semi-weekly (twice a week), triweekly (three times a week), weekly, biweekly (one every two weeks), monthly, quarterly etc. Newspaper language includes copy (articles, texts in newspapers written by journalists), the pictures used, the size and font of the text and how these elements are presented in the design layout. When writing copy, the journalist must establish the importance of the story in the first few sentences in order to hook the reader in and ensure they keep reading. To do this, they must capture the key points of the story using as few words as possible. Photographs in a newspaper are chosen by a picture editor and these choices play a crucial role in determining the look of a newspaper, especially the front page. The choice of photograph also plays a key role in influencing the reading of the story.

A great headline is essential for a successful newspaper as it attracts a potential buyer's attention and helps the newspaper stand out from its competitors. Tabloid headlines tend to be large and catchy and often use puns, rhyme, abbreviation, alliteration, even invented spellings. A broadsheet will use headlines which are longer and more serious. When all the copy (articles, texts in newspapers) is written and the pictures for the story have been chosen, the layout must be decided upon. A sub-editor is responsible for editing copy, looking at the grammar and style of the writing as well as the layout of a newspaper.

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Political Studies

Роль политических институтов в обеспечении экологической безопасности в Казахстане

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Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется роль политических институтов в обеспечении экологической безопасности Казахстана. Учитывая значительные экологические проблемы, стоящие перед страной, включая загрязнение воздуха и воды, обезлесение, опустынивание, деградацию почв, последствия ядерных испытаний и изменения климата, существует острая необходимость в эффективных институциональных действиях. В исследовании рассматривается достигнутый к настоящему времени прогресс в разработке, реализации и обеспечении соблюдения политики. Также выделены ограничения и потенциальные области, требующие улучшения с точки зрения участия общественности, правоприменения и интеграции политики. В работе рассматриваются перспективы развития этих институтов, включая укрепление законодательства, более полный учет экологических аспектов, расширение участия общественности и международного сотрудничества. Исследование позволяет сделать вывод о том, что политические институты Казахстана могут внести значительный вклад в обеспечение экологической безопасности путем постоянного развития и адаптации к изменяющимся вызовам.

Ключевые слова: Экологическая безопасность, политические институты, разработка политики, экологические вызовы, Казахстан, участие общественности, международное сотрудничество, законодательство, нормативно-правовое регулирование.

Заметная роль государственной экологической политики и экологической безопасности, как на национальном и региональном уровнях, так и на международной арене, приобрела ключевое значение в формировании всеобъемлющих политических рамок. Появление согласованной экологической политики является свидетельством сложной взаимосвязи и взаимозависимости, характеризующих современный глобальный ландшафт. Только благодаря согласованной реализации единой глобальной экологической политики мы сможем эффективно обеспечить экологическую безопасность и гарантировать выживание и процветание человечества.

Сравнительный политологический анализ факторов риска показывает, что как в казахстанском, так и в мировом сообществе, экологическая политика учитывает следующие аспекты: принципы устойчивости и политического баланса; принцип "загрязнитель платит", гарантирующий справедливую компенсацию убытков; принцип предосторожности при принятии любых решений, связанных с окружающей средой; бесспорное превалирование прав человека; и принцип общего политического участия.

В рамках экологической политики принцип платы за загрязнение интерпретируется как принцип, регулирующий отношения между различными государствами в контексте политического регулирования последствий глобальных экологических катастроф, которые

затрагивают интересы нескольких стран. Он также служит механизмом политического противодействия возникающим рискам, связанным с экологической политикой. В Европейском Союзе эти принципы получили наиболее широкую и сильную поддержку на высшем политическом уровне.

Принцип "баланса интересов" приводит в контексте межгосударственных экологических отношений, базируясь на нормах международного права, регулирующих деятельность государств в области экологической политики. В качестве иллюстрации можно рассмотреть разработку международных правовых режимов, направленных на регулирование использования ресурсов Мирового океана, учреждение экологических центров для изучения уникальных природных зон, а также разработку технологий для охраны природы. Особое значение приобретает техногенное сотрудничество, которое ставит вопрос о взаимосвязи природоохранных мероприятий с одновременным предоставлением дополнительных ресурсов для их реализации.

Международное сотрудничество способствует решению глобальных экологических проблем, которые имеют планетарный характер, а также проблем, связанных с разработкой технологий, направленных на эффективное использование ресурсов и энергии, внедрение принципов безотходного производства и рационального использования земельных ресурсов, и другие смежные аспекты.

Влияние политических институтов на экологическую безопасность невозможно переоценить. В условиях обострения глобального климатического кризиса Казахстан сталкивается с уникальными вызовами и возможностями, учитывая его огромные природные ресурсы, растущую экономику и центральное геополитическое положение.

Экологическая безопасность, определяемая как сохранение основных экологических процессов, биологического разнообразия и устойчивого использования природных ресурсов, сегодня важна как никогда. Казахстан, занимающий девятое место в мире по площади территории, обладает уникальной окружающей средой, характеризующейся обширными степями, горами, лесами и богатым биоразнообразием. Экономическая зависимость страны от природных ресурсов делает ее экологическую безопасность крайне важной.

Политические институты в Казахстане являются ключевыми субъектами в управлении и решении значительных экологических проблем страны. Они выполняют различные функции, включающие создание, реализацию и обеспечение соблюдения политики, направленной на сохранение окружающей среды и содействие устойчивой эксплуатации природных ресурсов.

С момента обретения независимости правительство Казахстана добилось заметных успехов в разработке политики, связанной с охраной окружающей среды. Политический ландшафт был постепенно ориентирован на решение экологических проблем, что принесло свои плоды в виде значительных политических инициатив.

Одним из таких примеров является программа партнерства "Зеленый мост", которая была предложена правительством Казахстана на Конференции ООН по устойчивому развитию (Рио+20) в 2012 году. Эта инновационная политическая инициатива направлена на продвижение "зеленой экономики" путем содействия обмену знаниями и технологиями между странами. Она является символом приверженности Казахстана устойчивому развитию и переходу к низкоуглеродной экономике. [1]

Более того, "Концепция перехода Республики Казахстан к зеленой экономике", представленная в 2013 году, является еще одной важной политической основой, которая подчеркивает приверженность Казахстана к сокращению выбросов углерода. В этом

перспективном политическом документе изложены основные стратегии и механизмы для содействия переходу к более устойчивой экономической модели, соответствующей мировым стандартам устойчивости. [2]

В Казахстане Министерство экологии, геологии и природных ресурсов занимает центральное место в реализации экологических стратегий. Этот важнейший орган является связующим звеном между политическими директивами высокого уровня и операциями на местах.

Министерство, через свои различные департаменты, способствует сотрудничеству для обеспечения достижения Казахстаном целей экологической устойчивости. Эти департаменты играют важнейшую роль, включая мониторинг изменений окружающей среды, обеспечение соблюдения нормативных актов, предоставление научных данных для разработки политики и реализацию проектов в соответствии с концепцией "зеленой" экономики страны.

Их работа охватывает широкий спектр задач, таких как координация инициатив по борьбе с обезлесением и деградацией земель, управление водными ресурсами и обеспечение сохранения биоразнообразия. Выполняя эти задачи, данные департаменты способствуют воплощению политики в конкретные действия, повышающие экологическую безопасность.

Помимо разработки и реализации политики, политические институты Казахстана выполняют важнейшую роль по мониторингу и регулированию деятельности, способствующей деградации окружающей среды.

Это достигается в основном посредством всеобъемлющего законодательства и надежных механизмов регулирования. Экологический кодекс Республики Казахстан, принятый в 2021 году, является основополагающим правовым документом, в котором изложены обязательства страны по охране окружающей среды, регулированию использования природных ресурсов и снижению загрязнения. [3]

Экологический кодекс дополняет комплексная система административных и уголовных наказаний, направленных на пресечение и наказание экологических нарушений. Эта комплексная система гарантирует, что физические лица, предприятия и организации соблюдают экологические нормы и несут ответственность за нарушения. Такие механизмы являются жизненно важными для общей эффективности экологической политики и вносят значительный вклад в обеспечение экологической безопасности в Казахстане.

Однако эффективность этих норм зависит от их строгого соблюдения и регулярного обновления с учетом меняющихся экологических проблем. Следовательно, роль политических институтов заключается в постоянном укреплении механизмов регулирования и совершенствовании стратегий правоприменения.

Следует отметить, что политические институты в Казахстане, благодаря их активному участию в разработке политики, стратегий внедрения и обеспечения соблюдения нормативных актов, играют незаменимую роль в обеспечении экологической безопасности. Несмотря на сохраняющиеся проблемы, их постоянная приверженность делу охраны окружающей среды может направить Казахстан в сторону устойчивого развития и повышения экологической безопасности.

Несмотря на значительные успехи, достигнутые политическими институтами Казахстана в укреплении экологической безопасности, сохраняются различные ограничения, которые снижают их общую эффективность. Эти ограничения имеют несколько форм и создают проблемы, которые требуют дальнейших действий и переоценки текущих стратегий.

Одним из основных ограничений является относительно низкий уровень участия общественности в решении экологических вопросов. В то время как разработка и реализация политики происходит в основном в рамках политических институтов, широкая

общественность часто остается пассивным наблюдателем, а не активным участником. Такой сценарий не является идеальным, поскольку участие общественности может дать ценные знания, повысить эффективность политики и воспитать чувство коллективной ответственности за состояние окружающей среды.

Более того, пробелы в правоприменении еще больше ограничивают эффективность политических институтов Казахстана. Хотя на бумаге существуют надежные нормативные акты, их реальное воздействие на окружающую среду часто снижается из-за непоследовательного исполнения. Это несоответствие может быть вызвано различными факторами, включая нехватку ресурсов, недостаточную подготовку, коррупцию или отсутствие политической воли. Независимо от причины, эти пробелы в правоприменении подрывают общую цель экологической безопасности и могут привести к дальнейшей деградации природных ресурсов.

Третье ограничение заключается в необходимости более тщательной интеграции экологических проблем во все сферы разработки политики. Хотя значительные усилия были направлены на реализацию "зеленых" политических инициатив, для достижения подлинной устойчивости экологические соображения должны пронизывать все аспекты разработки политики. Такой комплексный подход обеспечит, чтобы политика в различных секторах - от развития инфраструктуры до сельского хозяйства и энергетики - способствовала экологической безопасности.

Для устранения этих ограничений потенциальные средства защиты включают повышение прозрачности политических институтов, поощрение более активного участия граждан в решении экологических вопросов и создание более строгих механизмов правоприменения. Прозрачность может повысить доверие общества и способствовать конструктивному анализу экологической политики. Аналогичным образом, активно вовлекая граждан в процессы принятия решений и внедряя более жесткие механизмы правоприменения, политические институты могут повысить эффективность экологической политики и регулирования.

Перспективы развития политических институтов в области экологической безопасности в Казахстане связаны с более активным международным сотрудничеством. Поскольку экологические проблемы не ограничиваются национальными границами, международное сотрудничество имеет решающее значение для эффективного управления ресурсами и смягчения последствий изменения климата. Это требует от политических институтов более активного участия в многосторонних обсуждениях, соглашениях и инициативах.[4]

Одна из таких возможностей для международного сотрудничества заключается в развитии инициативы "Пояс и путь". Будучи важным участником, Казахстан имеет возможность использовать этот масштабный инфраструктурный проект для продвижения принципов устойчивого развития. Выступая за внедрение "зеленых" стандартов и практик при реализации проекта, Казахстан может не только повысить собственную экологическую безопасность, но и внести вклад в региональные и глобальные усилия по обеспечению устойчивости.

В перспективе развитие политических институтов Казахстана, особенно в сфере экологической безопасности, обладает значительным потенциалом. Учитывая актуальные экологические проблемы, стоящие перед страной, укрепление потенциала этих институтов и совершенствование их стратегического подхода становится все более важным.

Одна из ключевых перспектив развития политических институтов заключается в дальнейшем укреплении экологического законодательства и нормативно-правовой базы. Это включает в себя не только разработку новых, инновационных нормативных актов, но и последовательное совершенствование и адаптацию существующих законов и политики. По

мере усложнения и расширения масштабов экологических проблем законодательные меры должны динамично обновляться, чтобы обеспечить адекватное решение возникающих вопросов. Более того, создание более комплексных механизмов регулирования для обеспечения соблюдения существующих экологических законов может значительно повысить их эффективность. Это может включать ужесточение наказаний за экологические нарушения, совершенствование систем мониторинга и выделение достаточных ресурсов для правоприменительных органов. Эти меры могут стимулировать более строгое соблюдение экологических норм и способствовать формированию культуры подотчетности и ответственности по отношению к окружающей среде.

Еще одна многообещающая перспектива заключается в возможности более широкого учета экологических соображений во всех секторах разработки политики. Достижение подлинной устойчивости требует, чтобы экологические соображения пронизывали все аспекты управления, помимо тех, которые традиционно ассоциируются с природопользованием. В этом смысле политические институты могут способствовать внедрению подхода "учета экологических аспектов" во всех сферах политики, от экономического развития и городского планирования до развития инфраструктуры и социальной политики. Такой комплексный подход гарантирует, что вся политика и инициативы, предпринимаемые правительством, вносят положительный вклад в экологическую безопасность, тем самым способствуя более устойчивому будущему.[5]

Политические институты также могут выиграть от более активного взаимодействия с гражданским обществом в процессах принятия экологических решений. Содействие участию общественности в этих процессах может обеспечить учет более широкого круга точек зрения, тем самым повышая общее качество и приемлемость экологической политики. Способствуя формированию культуры активной гражданской позиции и вовлечению общественности в решение экологических вопросов, политические институты могут создать более прочный общественный консенсус по вопросам охраны окружающей среды и устойчивого развития. Такая широкая поддержка может повысить эффективность экологической политики и стимулировать добровольное соблюдение экологических норм.

Наконец, учитывая трансграничный характер многих экологических проблем, у политических институтов Казахстана есть значительный потенциал для активизации усилий по международному сотрудничеству. Это может включать в себя расширение участия в международных экологических договорах, активное участие в глобальных экологических форумах и сотрудничество с соседними странами в решении общих экологических проблем. Укрепляя свое международное сотрудничество, политические институты могут гарантировать, что экологическая политика Казахстана соответствует лучшей мировой практике, способствует достижению глобальных экологических целей и эффективно решает общие экологические проблемы.

В заключение следует отметить, что будущее развитие политических институтов в сфере экологической безопасности Казахстана открывает значительные перспективы. Укрепляя законодательную базу, интегрируя экологические соображения во все сектора, привлекая общественность и развивая международное сотрудничество, эти институты могут сыграть ключевую роль в формировании устойчивого и экологически безопасного будущего Казахстана.

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Biological Sciences

Biology of birds in a residential area

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Keywords: residential area (seliteb region), biotope, anthropogenic factors, natural landscape, urban ecosystem

A number of ethological and ecological indicators of bird biology in the natural landscape of the residential area differ. For example, birds that nest in low trees and bushes in forests and shrubs (*Streptopelia*, Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*), True thrush, *Chloris*, etc.) nest in inaccessible tall trees in the field. Even the Bunting, which nests in the grass in its natural environment, builds a nest on a low bush in a watery field. In some countries, crow species living in the suburbs build their nests in low trees and on rocks in natural areas, while in cities they are known to nest on the roofs of high buildings or in the inaccessible heights of tall trees.

The chronology of breeding birds in the Seliteb region changes. Here the breeding numbers of many bird species increase during the season. We assume that it is because the birds in the residential area have an additional food base. While the field pigeon in the natural biotope (rocky) doesn't breed more than 2 times, breeds 4 times in the residential area. The roof sparrow breeds twice a year in the natural biotope (bushes), and up to 5 times after moving to the field. *Streptopelia* breeds only once a year in the natural biotope (shrub), and twice a year in the field.

Birds adopting the residential area show a change in food ration, and in some cases even in the food nature. Grain-eating birds move from wild plant seeds to cultivated plant grains. Eating crab berries and fruits in the natural biotope, birds begin to feed on berries and fruits of cultivated plants in the field.

Moving from the forest to the city in Western Europe (Berlin), Eurasian jay (*Garrulus glandarius*) and True thrush destroy the nests of peaceful birds, that is, eat their babies. In London, the food ration of Greyish eagle-owl is peaceful birds, but in the forest is small mammals. Crow and raven prey on small vertebrates and invertebrates in natural landscapes around some cities, while in the city they prefer to feed on fruits and berries of a number of cultivated plants.

The daily activity of birds using the residential area also changes. For example, during the winter, seagulls and crows feed on food scraps found in landfills in Great Baku. To spend the night, seagulls fly to the Caspian Islands (30-40 km), and crows to the reeds of Shabran port (50-60 km). They spend a lot of time traveling long distances. Therefore, they fly to the place of feeding at dusk in the morning, and to the place at midnight. So they are busy looking for food all day. Known that the feeding of these birds in the form of a colony is an adaptation to use time efficiently.

The transition sequence of the bird species to the residential area (synthropization) is also interesting. In modern times, residential areas have expanded intensively, compressing natural landscapes and disrupting their integrity. The response of animals to anthropogenic transformation of natural landscapes is positive and negative. In negative cases, the zoological species or its specific population leaves the region, and in positive cases, it reproduces further in the changed habitat.

The synanthropization of zoological species is a historical process parallel to human evolution. However, the history of studying this process scientifically is not more than 60 years. Literature information on the synanthropization of animals, including birds, in Azerbaijan is given in detail in

Chapter I of the dissertation (thesis). However, since the theoretical foundations of the problem were adequately explained, we tried to provide wide space to this area.

Generally, the literature on the fauna of the anthropogenic landscape contains sufficient information that helps to clarify the mechanism and sequence of the synanthropization process.

From the collected literature, observed that the process of synanthropization begins and develops when human society changes the environment. The beginning of the zoological species' assimilation of the anthropogenic transformation of the natural landscape can be regarded as a preparatory period for its synanthropy. The use of forest birds in the garden and the meadow birds in the field are the first adaptations for their future synanthropic status.

The synanthropization of birds varies from region to region, either qualitatively (number of species) or quantitatively (number of individuals). The general indication is that no new species are formed as a result of synanthropization process. Even the zoological species cut off completely the connection with their natural biotopes began to live in the neighborhood with humans after they were formed under the general influence of a certain geographical area, not in the residential area. Therefore, synanthropic species retain the features of the basic stereotype acquired during their formation in natural conditions. Although they are completely synanthropic, they are content to change their ethological and later some ecological indicators under the influence of anthropogenic factors.

There are two sources of synanthropization of fauna in a certain region: 1) remnants of the first natural landscape, 2) species from outside. The species in the first group live in the same region and simultaneously both in their natural biotopes and in the field (under human contact conditions). For example, the ruffed grouse - *Garlerida cristata*, the warbler - *Oenanthe isabellina*, etc. When there was no Great Baku, these birds lived in its place and are still adapting to new conditions. The second group, "arrivals", are species not found in the natural landscape around the city. They came to the field more or less from far away and adapted to the neighborhood with people. For example, turtle-dove - *Streptopelia senegalensis*, which is now synanthropic in Baku, and the collared turtle-dove - *Strep.*

Birds such as decaocto, barn swallow - *Hirundo rustica*, black thrush - *Turdus merula*, and house sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) - *Passer demeticus* were not in the place before the city, they came later. Some of these populations came from natural biotopes far from Baku and started to synanthropize here, and some came by synanthropizing in other regions. Intraspecies groups, including populations, are known to be open systems. Therefore, we may say undoubtedly that the genetic exchange between the synanthropic and the natural population of zoological species (if any) continues.

We assume that the most qualitatively complex of the anthropogenic biocenoses is included in the urban ecosystem. The biocenosis of the urban ecosystem unites different continents and natural regions pursuant to its systematic, biogeographic, and ecological origin. The high biodiversity in the residential area facilitates synanthropization. At night, insects gather in the bright light of a big city like Baku, attracting bats, and in turn, bats become the prey of owls. Thus, the reproduction of the food chain and the expansion of the food web in the city make bioenosis sustainable, and some of its components gradually become synanthropic in terms of time.

Legal Sciences

The COVID-19 pandemic as a challenge for personal data protection

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Abstract

The occurrence of any crisis serves as a testament to the significance of human rights for the state and sheds light on the willingness of state institutions to establish a fair balance between fundamental human rights and other legitimate interests.

The COVID-19 pandemic presented itself as a significant challenge not only to healthcare systems, but, but also for protection of human rights. The primary objective for all states during this period was the safeguarding of public health. However, the degree to which states compromised human rights in pursuit of this objective was contingent upon their level of democratic development and adherence to fundamental human rights principles.

Among the various rights jeopardized during the pandemic, personal data and privacy emerged as prominent concerns. During the COVID-19 pandemic, a particularly large amount of special category personal data related to health status was processed. Personal data was processed not only by state institutions, but also by private companies (for example, thermal screening data). The process of learning and working has moved to the online mode, which has led to the processing of a particularly large volume of data electronically. To impede the spread of the disease, numerous online applications were developed, entailing the processing of geo location data for millions of individuals.

Extraordinary situation and need of prompt response made complicated to strike a fair balance between human rights and public health interests. Additionally, the sustainability of state institutions, their competences, and the level of democracy within the country have played pivotal roles in establishing this equitable balance. Consequently, the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic can be perceived as a litmus test, assessing the preparedness of state institutions to navigate crisis scenarios and effectively discharge the responsibilities entrusted to them.

Keywords: Personal data, COVID-19 pandemic, public health

1. Introduction

The right to personal data protection has gained special relevance in the 21st century with the development of technology and the Internet era. Personal data protection law is a new and dynamically developing field. It is closely related to the right to privacy, which dates back to 1890. Lawyers from United States Samuel D. Warren and Louis Brandeis write an article "The Right to Privacy". In this article definition of privacy was concise and comprehensive - right to be left alone".¹ The international protection of the right to private life was implemented in 1948 by the

¹ Samuel D. Warren, Louis Brandeis, The Right to Privacy, Harvard Law Review, Vol. IV December 15, 1890 No. 5

Universal Declaration of Human Rights.² Currently the right to privacy recognized not only with international legal acts, but also with the constitutions of number of countries. The right to protection of personal data is not the same as the right to privacy. Personal data protection is a broader concept. Personal data protection ensures that one's personal data is protected from any unlawful access by unauthorized parties regardless of whether or not damage has occurred. The right to personal data was protected at the international level for the first time by the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data at 1981.³ The new and most progressive step in the field of personal data protection was the adoption of the GDPR in 2016.⁴

Right to personal data protection as well as right to privacy is not unrestricted right. Legislation sets up legal legitimate interests for the restriction of these right. Although international and national personal data protection regulations have improved significantly in recent years, the implementation of the norm in practice has revealed a number of challenges. One of the main challenges in the field of personal data protection was the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic has been problems not only in the field of healthcare care but also in terms of human rights protection. One of the main challenges was to find a fear balance between public health interests and human rights. Personal data were restricted for the purposes of public health.

The government has been given access to a range of personal data for disease control and prevention. For the same purpose, health data became known to the employers as well. For different application were also used information about Geo location. In some cases access to this data was justified for health protection purposes. However, in some cases there was an excessive compromise at the expense of limiting rights, which was caused on the one hand by the extraordinary and unexpected situation and on the other hand by inexperience in managing similar situations.

After pandemic is over and the problem has been eliminated, it is important to analyze the process well and identify the problems that characterize the protection of personal data in a crisis situation.

It is important to analyze how the state dealt with personal data protection in a crisis situation, how was established a balance between the right to personal data protection and the interests of health, how effectively the supervisory bodies performed their function. The results of the study of this issue will be useful to outline the main trends of personal data protection problems and to prevent problems in the future.

In the paper, personal data protection during the COVID-19 pandemic is discussed on the example of Georgia, and the main problems are presented against the background of practical examples.

2. Personal data in the field of health care and the legal grounds for their restriction

Personal data is any information connected to an identified or identifiable natural person (such as gender, personal number, email, age and etc.). However, there is a category of personal data that is protected by a higher standard, because of a closer connection with the basic human right - the right to privacy, and therefore illegal processing of this data may cause more harm to the

² Universal Declaration of Human Rights. 10 December, 1948 (<https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>)

³ Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data Strasbourg, 28.I.1981(<https://rm.coe.int/1680078b37>)

⁴ General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (<https://gdpr-info.eu/>)

data subject. Such data are called sensitive (special category) data and belong to them, such as data connected to a person's racial or ethnic origin, political views, religious or philosophical beliefs, membership of professional organizations, state of health, sexual life, criminal history, biometric and genetic data that allow to identify a natural person by the above features etc.

Data on the state of state of health belong to a special category of data according to both international⁵ and national legislation. Legal grounds for processing of sensitive data are limited and stricter sanctions have been imposed for violation of such data. During the processing of sensitive data following principles should be protected: Lawfulness, fairness and transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality. International acts also define legal basis when personal data related to health can be processed: processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services.⁶

In Georgia, the processing of personal data related to health care and the rights of patients are regulated by a number of laws, among them: "Law on personal data protection", "Law on Medical Practice", "Law on Patients Rights", "Law on Health Care", "Law on Public Health".

"Law on personal data protection" defines several legal basis for processing of personal data, among them: processing of the data related to previous convictions and state of health is necessary for labor obligations and labor relations, including making a decision regarding employment; data processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of a data subject or a third person and when the data subject is physically or legally unable to give his/her consent to data processing; the data are processed for public health protection, health care or protection of health of a natural person by an institution (employee), and if it is necessary to manage or operate the health care system.⁷

Georgian Law on medical practice defines circumstances when medical practitioner have the right to disclose personal data without consent of patient: if the non-disclosure of such information puts the health and/or life of a third person (whose identity is known) at risk, there is a reasonable doubt about the existence of a disease subject to mandatory registration, the disclosure of information is required by law enforcement bodies under a court decision.⁸

Lawfulness and fairness of personal data restrictions depends on several factors, including the democracy of the country and the strength and competence of the institutions. Any limitation of the right must be done in compliance with the principle of proportionality. The grounds for restricting the right should be established and controlled by a body with high legitimacy.

Need of quick decision-making during COVID 19 pandemic and the extraordinary situation threatened the protection and realization of many rights.

3. The covid pandemic, the state of emergency and its impact on human rights

Coronavirus was a reason of death of 6,895,112 people in 229 countries and territories.⁹ The first cases of novel coronavirus were detected in China in December 2019. The virus spreading rapidly to other countries across the world. This led WHO to declare a Public Health Emergency of

⁵ Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data Strasbourg, 28.I.1981, article 6.

⁶ General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679, article.10 (<https://gdpr-info.eu/>)

⁷ Law of Georgia on Personal Data Protection, article 6. (<https://matsne.gov.ge/en/document/view/1561437?publication=23>)

⁸ Georgian law on Medical Practice, 2001, article 48 (<https://matsne.gov.ge/en/document/view/15334?publication=17>)

⁹ 6,895,112 people have died so far from the coronavirus COVID-19 outbreak as of June 28, 2023 (<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/coronavirus-death-toll/>)

International Concern (PHEIC) on 30 January 2020, and to characterize the outbreak as a pandemic on 11 March 2020.

Georgia reported the first case of the novel coronavirus on February 26, 2020. The government of Georgia started imposing certain restrictions to tackle the pandemic. Initially, most of the restrictions were of recommendatory nature. They became obligatory only after the state of emergency was declared on 21 March 2020. The President's Decree established grounds for blanket derogation of rights, while the powers of determining the nature and scope of specific restrictions were delegated to the government. Moreover, regulation of certain issues fell within the competence of the ministries. As a result, the government was granted a broad discretion in terms of restricting the rights.¹⁰

In 2020, the Parliament endorsed the amendments to the Law of Georgia on Public Health, which made it possible to restrict some of the fundamental human rights without declaring a state of emergency, through quarantine measures. The rules and the scope of restrictions are determined by the government. This was a temporary Law which was in force until 2022. During the two years rules restricted of human rights in Georgia were issued without control of the Parliament.

More than two years have passed since the coronavirus pandemic. The mentioned period is enough to analyze the impact of the pandemic on human rights and, most importantly, to evaluate how the states coped with one of the main challenges of the 21st century.

Evaluating the general picture, we may note that the degree of democracy of the country determined the extent to which the states compromised with human rights and the extent to which they were able to establish a fair balance between basic human rights and public health interests.

The need to respond promptly to problems and rapidly changing conditions has led to the redistribution of power and functions between different branches of government. In those countries where parliamentary control was not properly implemented, the restriction of human rights took place in a larger dose.

During the pandemic, international organizations such as the Council of Europe and the United Nations (UN) have developed principles and guidelines for the protection of human rights during the COVID-19 pandemic for member states. On April 8, 2020, the Council of Europe (COE) published a guide for member states on Respecting democracy, rule of law and human rights in the framework of the COVID-19 sanitary crisis¹¹

In April 2020, the UN published the report COVID-19 and Human Rights: We are all in this together.¹²

The Venice Commission has focused on the special necessity of human rights protection. „The protection of life, health and ensuring safety of the population is an important public interest which, under the state of emergency, can warrant restriction or suspension of some of the rights and freedoms and changes in the distribution of roles among various branches of government at the expense of increasing the powers of the executive branch.“¹³

¹⁰ transparency International-Georgia, Parliamentary control related to the management of pandemic, Tbilisi 2022.(https://transparency.ge/sites/default/files/parliamentary_control.pdf)

¹¹ Respecting democracy, rule of law and human rights in the framework of the COVID-19 sanitary crisis A toolkit for member states, Information Documents SG/Inf(2020)11, Council of Europe.

¹²UN, COVID-19 and Human Rights: We are all in this together (<https://unsdg.un.org/resources/covid-19-and-human-rights-we-are-all-together>)

¹³ The European Commission for Democracy through Law (Venice Commission), Emergency Powers, 1995, CDL -STD(1995)012.

International organizations published a numerous recommendations and reports related to the human rights protection during coronavirus pandemic. Among them we should mention report of European Parliament about Human right protection standards.¹⁴

During the pandemic, personal data was restricted along with other rights. During the state of emergency, a number of basic rights, including the right to access information, were restricted by the decree of the President of Georgia and the ruling of the Government, and the access to personal data was also affected. Although the right to privacy was not limited by the presidential decree, the restriction of access to personal information and disclosure of personal information was considered by some lawyers as interference in privacy. Prevention of access to personal information or suspension of the timeframe for releasing personal information may interfere with the right to privacy.¹⁵ The suspension of access to public information was assessed negatively by civil society.¹⁶

Along with access to personal data, compliance with the principles and legal bases of personal data processing, as well as compliance with security rules and deadlines for personal data storage, was a significant problem.

4. Main challenges related to personal data during the covid pandemic in Georgia

During the COVID pandemic a lot of information were processed not only by state institutions and competent public authorities (e.g. public health authorities) but also by private companies in the employment context - safety at the workplace, or to the public interest, such as the control of diseases and other threats to health. For prevention of spread of disease and for creation a special applications location data of a numerous persons were processed.

The outbreak has also clearly indicated the ability of governments, health authorities and researchers to harvest this data efficiently and securely in order to reliably learn from it.¹⁷

During the Covid pandemic, the following main problems in terms of personal data protection were identified:

During the Covid pandemic, the amount of personal data processed has increased significantly and the risks of rights violations have increased accordingly. During the Covid pandemic, a large amount of special category data related to health was processed. These data were collected not only by public and medical institutions, but also by other private structures, which increased the risks of rights violations. At the time of their processing, in many cases, it was not determined in advance what impact the data processing could have on the right to privacy. Problems were also identified with regard to organizational and technical standards of personal data security. In many cases, more employees had access to personal information than was necessary. Data retention periods were also unclear.

In 2020, the State Inspectorate examined 24 personal data protection cases. The agency inspected 6 organizations and identified violations, including:

In the medical institutions and in the hotel quarantine areas where not registered all actions related to the personal data processing; several persons had access to electronic system of one

¹⁴ European Parliament, Upholding human rights in Europe during the pandemic, 2020 ([https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2020\)652085](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2020)652085))

¹⁵ Konstantine Korkelia, Legality and Proportionality of Human Rights Restrictions Imposed in Georgia in Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic, MPIL research series, NO 2021-23. P.15 (https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3922554)

¹⁶ Institute for Development of Freedom of Information (IDFI) Report on Rule of Law and Human Rights During the COVID-19 Crisis, , May 2020, 10. (https://idfi.ge/public/upload/Covid/rule_of_law_and_human_rights_during_covid_19.pdf)

¹⁷ Maria Christofidou, Nathan Lea , Pascal Coorevits, A Literature Review on the GDPR, COVID-19 and the Ethical Considerations of Data Protection During a Time of Crisis. National library of medicine. 2021 (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34479394/>)

of the medical institutions with the same user profile; Ministry of Internal Affairs registered information about infected persons, as well as persons who were in contact with them and/or were in self-isolation (name, surname, personal number, contact information, address, date of contact with the infected person, date of self-isolation and completion of self-isolation period and, if necessary, information on the transfer of a person to a fever clinic or quarantine) However, in this process, the Ministry did not record information on the date of collection, disclosure and/or deletion of personal data; National Center for Disease Control and Public Health, the preliminary passwords of users registered in the COVID-19 electronic test registration module were not changed; The lack of a two-level authentication mechanism posed a risk of privacy breach of information in the module; One of the medical institutions disclosed the results of COVID-19 testing to a third party; In several shopping malls, the customer temperature screening system did not record the operations performed in relation to the personal data and was not password-protected.¹⁸

In order to prevent the violation of personal data rights during the Covid pandemic, the Personal Data Protection Inspector of Georgia developed recommendations. Recommendations are important because they can be used in any critical situation. Among the recommendations, the following are particularly noteworthy: Data processors should assess the impact of data processing on human rights in order to pre-emptively eliminate expected risks; For data security, implement the necessary organizational and technical measures taking into account the categories of data, the volume of processed data, the purpose, form and means of processing, as well as the threats of infringement of the data subject's rights; introduce mechanisms that ensure the proper realization of the data subject's rights; Set a timeframe for data storage and delete them after achieving the purpose for which they were collected; Introduce an effective mechanism for monitoring the persons authorized to access the data and, in case of unlawful and/or non-official processing of the data, respond appropriately to the detected violations.¹⁹

Crises can't be used as an argument for less protection of human rights and among them personal data and privacy. In the extraordinary situation violation of human rights increase and more strong protection of rules and principles are required. During the pandemic data collection, use, sharing, storage, and other processing of health data should be limited to what is strictly necessary for the fight against the virus. Only in such way we can achieve purpose limitation and data minimization, two very important principles of data processing. Health information is very valuable information also for a commercial purposes. There is a high risk to use collected information for another purposes. A pandemic is no excuse to collect extensive and unnecessary data and to use this data for different purposes. Access to health data shall be limited to those who need information to conduct treatment, research, and otherwise address the crisis. The information should be stored securely, in a separate database. State need information for management of pandemic, but always this information should be depersonalized, although when personal data is used for historical and research purposes. Personal data without depersonalization can't be used without consent of data subject. When crises over data subjects should have information about data storage period and retention. Data processed in response to the crisis should be kept only for the duration of the crisis.

From past health crises, we have learned not to fall for quick fixes, but to uphold human rights to prevent further harms for the population.

Conclusion

¹⁸ Report on the activities of state inspector service, 2020. p.27 (<https://www.personaldata.ge/en/about-us>)

¹⁹ Ibid

During the Covid pandemic, the processing of personal data has significantly increased not only by state structures, but also by private companies. A large amount of data related to the state of health was being processed, including thermo-screening, information on infection. Geo-location data is also collected in the process of combating the covid pandemic, in order to identify and prevent contact persons of infected patients.

The situation was unusual and quite acute. On the one hand, people's lives and health were at stake, and on the other hand, rights, which were sometimes more restricted than necessary to protect the interest of health. Although the Covid pandemic was an acute problem for the whole world, the states had different approaches to deal with the problems. A different approach applied to both health care and human rights. Fragile democracies are more vulnerable to human rights in crisis situations.

In the article, the discussion of the problems related to personal data during the Covid pandemic, using the example of Georgia, showed the following problems: it was often not well analyzed to what extent it was necessary to limit personal data in the volume and intensity that was limited; Private and public structures were not ready to establish the right balance between health interests and personal data in crisis situations. The mentioned problems were caused by several reasons, including the lack of information about personal data protection on the part of both the data subject and the data processor, the lack of personnel knowledgeable about personal data issues in institutions and organizations, inexperience in critical situations, and the weakness of state institutions.

During a crisis situation, it is especially important to protect personal data, including data processing in compliance with principles and legal bases. The existence of a strong controlling institution is of particular importance. Even though the Covid pandemic is over, there are still risks that the vast amount of personal data collected during the pandemic could be misused. It is important for independent institutions to find out whether this data has been destroyed or for how long it has been stored and whether security measures have been followed during storage.

The problems and challenges in protecting personal data during the Covid pandemic should be analyzed and its results applied to future crises.

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State of Emergency and Legal Regulation of Crisis Management Caused by the Covid Pandemic

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Abstract

The study was carried out within the framework of the study “Problems of protection of human health and other rights under the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic and international legal guarantees” funded by the International University of Georgia - GIU.

In the course of the research, the legislative changes introduced at the national and international level during the Covid pandemic as well as their implementation process in the context of the protection of human rights and their implementation have been analyzed. Since the World Health Organization declared a global pandemic on March 11, 2020, countries around the world have mostly resorted to special measures to stop the spread of the Covid pandemic.

Though the pandemic has forced the European countries to apply for the various means and to carry out the different actions, it should be underlined that the majority of the European countries did not announce the state of emergency, and they coped with this great challenge based upon the legislation regulating ordinary (common) situation. It is a fact that the reason for declaring the state of emergency in Georgia was not the danger of internal uncontrolled spread of Coronavirus, but the threat of absence of the proper legal base in the country, which would have enabled the state to establish the restrictions / limitations of the human rights compliant to the epidemiological standing.

Within the framework of the research, the analysis will be made on the legal bases of the restrictions introduced by the state in the conditions of the pandemic, which will help in the future to establish the response mechanisms of the states to solve similar emergency situations in such a way as to exclude confusion, chaos and inconsistent actions in crisis conditions.

Key words: Covid Pandemic. Legal arrangement. State of emergency.

Introduction

The present research has been important and relevant after the fact that the whole world and among them, Georgia as well turned out to be facing non-precedential challenge. It should be noted that not a single country appeared ready to fight the crisis. Neither should Georgia have the experience of dealing with a pandemic of this scale.

The Covid pandemic has been a challenge for both the medical and the legal fields. Finding a balance between public health as a legitimate interest and basic human rights has not been easy. The Coronavirus has threatened democracies and non-democracies alike, but how the European states managed to do that largely depended on their level of democracy. Much of the human rights have been curtailed in the process of fighting the Covid pandemic. In order to respond quickly to the virus, the government has been given the power to restrict, and that is why effective control of the government's activities by the people's representative body, the Parliament and the Court has become particularly important. The Coronavirus has created many new and important

challenges in the agenda of the legislative and the judicial authorities of the countries of the world.

The state of emergency in its essence aims at positive expectations, which should ensure the protection of public safety and order. The scale caused by this pandemic is quite wide and almost no state was left on which it did not have a negative impact, and Georgia was not an exception. The Constitution of Georgia envisages the declaration of a state of emergency during both an epidemic and a pandemic, when the state authorities are deprived of the possibility of normal exercise of their constitutional powers.

The pandemic was truly unprecedented throughout the world, including the European countries. European states, and Georgia among them, more or less coped with the pandemic. From the point of view of comparison between Georgia and other European countries, it is worth noting that only 10 of the 27 European Union member states, while 10 of the 47 member states of the European Council declared the state of emergency, and Georgia was among them. Therefore, the majority of European countries did not declare a state of emergency and they dealt with the pandemic based on the legislation regulating the ordinary (common) situation. It should be noted that the announcement of the state of emergency in Georgia was not preconditioned by the danger of the non-controlled internal spread of the Coronavirus in the country, but was due to the lack of the proper legal basis in Georgia, with which the state could impose appropriate human rights restrictions.

Both the law of Georgia on public health as well as the law on social security in relation to this, and no other legal act fully defined the conditions for limiting human rights in the conditions of an epidemic. The existence of a proper legal base would have prevented the declaration of a state of emergency and the restriction of human rights in the conditions of the state of emergency.

The present study will allow us to promote better protection of fundamental human rights during the crisis situation in Georgia. During the pandemic, the government of Georgia limited the fundamental human rights guaranteed by the Constitution of Georgia. That is why it is important to assess the restrictions imposed in Georgia in terms of compliance with international and European standards of human rights, as well as due to the Constitution of Georgia.

General Part

Since December 31, 2019, the disease caused by the novel Coronavirus has spread rapidly around the world after the first cases of the virus were reported in the city of Wuhan, Hubei Province, People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as China). Since the early March 2020, the number of countries affected by the new Coronavirus has exceeded 190. On January 30, 2020, WHO announced the situation as an international public health emergency,²⁰ and on 11 March, assessed as the pandemic.

In order to deal with the pandemic, a state of emergency was declared in only 10 of the 27 EU member states (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Hungary, Luxembourg, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, and Spain). In 17 member states, constitutional emergency norms were found to be suitable for responding to the pandemic²¹. It should be noted here that the parliament declared a state of emergency in two countries - Bulgaria and Portugal, the government declared a state of emergency in seven countries - the Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Hungary, Luxembourg, Romania, Spain, and 5 states (France, Germany, Italy, Latvia and Slovakia) declared a state of emergency based on ordinary legislation.

²⁰ Public Health Emergency International Concern. 2020. <file:///C:/Users/nino.botchorishvili/Downloads/global-research-and-innovation-forum-towards-a-research-roadmap.pdf> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

²¹ States of emergency in response to the Coronavirus crisis, normative response and parliamentary oversight in EU Member States during the first wave of the pandemic. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/659385/EPRS_STU\(2020\)659385_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/659385/EPRS_STU(2020)659385_EN.pdf) (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

Seven member states (Croatia, Germany, Lithuania, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland and Slovenia) chose not to declare a state of emergency. The state of emergency was initially declared from March 11 to 19 and was lifted from May 13 to June 24, 2020. In some cases, such states of emergency were withdrawn after the first wave of the pandemic was under control, and then were replaced by lighter mechanisms. The minimum statutory duration of the state of emergency varies from 10 days (Luxembourg) to 90 days (Estonia, Finland, Slovakia), in the first stage emergency measures were introduced for a period of 10 days to about a month in all EU member states and then renewed at least once. However, there were states that did not set a deadline for the state of emergency, such as Croatia and Hungary, which was rejected by the Venice Commission. The Venice Commission recommends that declarations of states of emergency or restrictions that do not have a specific period of time, including the suspension of which depends on the overcoming of special circumstances, should not be considered legal unless the situation is regularly reviewed.”²²

The measures taken by EU member states to deal with the Covid pandemic differed significantly from each other. The constitutions of some Member States contain a provision for declaring a state of emergency, while others do not contain such provisions at all (e.g., Denmark) or contain provisions that do not include a mechanism for declaring a state of emergency for health protection (e.g., Italy). Some member states decided to declare a constitutional state of emergency to contain the pandemic (e.g., Bulgaria, Estonia, Latvia, Romania or Spain), while others decided not to apply for this option, even when their constitution allowed it. Instead, they have taken measures, for example, using customary laws, statutory regimes or special legislative powers granted to the executive government.

The measures taken by the states in the first stage of the spread of the Covid pandemic can be divided into four categories:

- I. Constitutional emergency;
- II. Normative regimes;
- III. Measures taken under special legislative authority; and
- IV. Measures taken almost exclusively by ordinary legislation.

Constitutional state of emergency refers to the state of emergency provided for by the constitution of the member state. Statutory regimes refer to those regimes which are provided for by statute rather than the constitution and which organically regulate emergency situations and powers vested in the relevant authorities. Special legislative powers refer to the constitutional powers granted to the executive to enact statutory acts with the same legislative force as primary laws in cases of emergency/exception and are subject to parliamentary oversight.

Despite the diversity of national legislation, a common feature of the legal response to the pandemic in member states has been a shift in the competences of both the legislative and executive branches of government. As in other countries of the world, member states of the European Union²³ the government has undertaken an important role in referring to the necessary measures to overcome the pandemic crisis, in some cases by transferring additional powers from the legislature to the executive.²⁴

In general, legislation based on declared states of emergency allowed governments to restrict basic rights. Some EU member states sent notifications to the Secretary General of the

²² Nakashidze, Malkhaz, 2021. Restriction of human freedom under the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic: European standards and Georgian legislation. Human rights protection and the covid-19 pandemic. A collection of articles. <https://tsu.ge/assets/media/files/76/II%20Genaral/HR%20Covid-19.pdf> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

²³ Ginsburg, Tom and Versteeg, Mila. 2020. The Bound Executive: Emergency Powers During The Pandemic, No 52, p. 22, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3608974 (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

²⁴ T. Ginsburg and M. Versteeg, op. cit, p. 4; E. Griglio, 'Parliamentary oversight under the COVID-19 emergency: striving against executive dominance', *The Theory and Practice of Legislation*, July 2020.

Council of Europe under Article 15 of the European Convention on Human Rights and to the Secretary General of the United Nations under Article 4 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.

According to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, member states have the right to limit a number of fundamental human rights during the declaration of a state of emergency, except for those rights that are prohibited by the international agreement itself. However, at the same time, international agreements establish formal and substantive guarantees, including that the state of emergency is not formally declared, that it is caused by special circumstances, and that the measures taken are necessary, temporary and subject to constant monitoring.

Under Article 15 of the European Convention on Human Rights, in times of war or other emergency threatening the existence of the nation, any High Contracting Party may take measures to derogate from its obligations under the Convention only to the extent strictly required by the gravity of the situation and provided that such measures are not incompatible with its other international legal obligations.²⁵

Under Article 4 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, during a state of emergency which threatens the life of the nation and which is officially declared, the States Parties to the present Covenant may deviate from their obligations under the Covenant to the extent required by the gravity of the situation, provided that these measures are incompatible will not be inconsistent with their other obligations under international law and will not include discrimination based on race, color, sex, language, religion or social origin²⁶.

The European Parliament also supported a similar approach during the Covid pandemic, stressing that all measures taken must be “strictly proportionate to the necessity of the situation, clearly linked. The current health crisis should be subject to time-limited and regular inspections”²⁷. Similarly, the Venice Commission indicated that the use of emergency powers can only be considered justified if they are necessary to overcome a particular situation, if they are proportionate and limited in time, and if they are subject to effective judicial and parliamentary control²⁸.

Out of the 47 states participating in the European Convention on Human Rights, only 10 states (Latvia, Romania, Estonia, Armenia, Moldova, Georgia, Albania, North Macedonia, Serbia, and San Marino) have sent a notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe.²⁹ And 20 states (Argentina, Armenia, Chile, Colombia, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El-Salvador, Ethiopia, Georgia, Guatemala, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Namibia, Palestine, Paraguay, Peru, Romania, Senegal, Thailand)³⁰ of 173 states - international participants in terms of the civil and the political rights sent the notification about the departure from the Covenant to the Secretary General of the United Nations Organization.

²⁵ European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights, 1950, European Council, Article 15, available at: https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/convention_kat (last seen on 05.07.2023)

²⁶ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966, United Nations, Art. 4, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/1398335?publication=0> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

²⁷ Resolution of 17 April 2020 on EU coordinated action to combat the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences, European Parliament, 2020/2616 (RSP), para. 46.

²⁸ Report on Respect for Democracy, Human Rights and the Rule of Law during States of Emergency, Venice Commission, CDL-AD (2020)014, 19 June 2020.

²⁹ Korkelia, Konstantine. 2021. Human rights protection and the covid-19 pandemic. A collection of articles. Tbilisi: pg. 81. <https://tsu.ge/assets/media/files/76/ILI%20Genaral/HR%20Covid-19.pdf> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁰ Korkelia, Konstantine. 2020-2021. Restrictions on human rights in Georgia during the Covid-19 pandemic: lessons learned and recommendations. pg. 44. https://georgia.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/LongVersion_GEO_WEB.pdf (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

On March 11, 2020, the new Coronavirus was declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization, taking into account its mass spread and the growing challenge facing the country, in order to respond appropriately to the pandemic declared by the World Health Organization, to normalize the situation, so that the state fulfills its constitutional obligation - to ensure the necessary in a democratic society Public safety and reduction of the expected threat to the life and health of the country's population, in accordance with Article 71, Clause 2 of the Constitution of Georgia and Article 2, Clause 1 of the Law of Georgia "On the State of Emergency", the Order of the President of Georgia No. 1 declared a state of emergency in Georgia³¹. By the same order, the period of validity of the state of emergency shall be determined until April 21, 2020. On April 21, 2020, the order of the President of Georgia No. 2 "On the declaration of a state of emergency in the entire territory of Georgia" by the order of the President of Georgia No. 1 of March 21, 2020, the period of validity of the state of emergency declared in the entire territory of Georgia should be extended until May 22, 2020³².

On March 21, 2020, the President of Georgia issued a decree on the measures to be taken in connection with the declaration of a state of emergency in the entire territory of Georgia, according to which the rights indicated in the Clauses 3 and 4 of the Article 71 of the Constitution of Georgia³³ and the Clauses 3 and 4 of the Article 2 of the Law of Georgia "On the State of Emergency", the Article 13 (Human Rights), the Article 14 (Freedom of Movement), the Article 15 (Rights to inviolability of private and family life, personal space and communication), the Article 18 (Rights to fair administrative proceedings, access to public information, informational self-determination and compensation for damages caused by the public authorities), the Article 19 (Right to property), the Article 21 (Freedom of assembly) and the Article 26 (Freedom of work, freedom of professional associations, right to strike and freedom of entrepreneurship) were restricted / limited³⁴. The restriction did not affect the Article 17 (rights to freedom of opinion, information, media and Internet). By decree, the government of Georgia was given the authority to manage the state of emergency and establish isolation and quarantine rules. It is a fact that the President of Georgia declared a state of emergency in order to limit the fundamental human rights guaranteed by the Constitution of Georgia with a decree, the need to limit which was caused by the threat of the spread of the Covid pandemic, where the basis for the restriction of human rights refers to preventive measures and is not guided by the Law of Georgia "On Public Health", The main task of which is the implementation of preventive measures³⁵. It should be noted that Georgia, like many other European states, was not ready to deal with the crisis situation caused by the pandemic, and the processes were conducted chaotically and inconsistently at the beginning of the pandemic. In some cases, the basis for this was an unorganized legal base, for example, the law of Georgia "On State of Emergency" turned out to be completely useless, because it does not take into account the goal of health protection at all³⁶. It should be noted here

³¹ On declaring a state of emergency in the entire territory of Georgia, Order of the President of Georgia N1, March 21, 2020. Available: <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4830390?publication=0> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³² On declaring a state of emergency in the entire territory of Georgia, Order of the President of Georgia N2, April 21, 2020. Available: <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4853172?publication=0> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³³ Constitution of Georgia, Agencies of the Parliament of Georgia, 31-33, 24/08/1995, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/30346?publication=36> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁴ Decree of the President of Georgia N1, March 21, 2020, on measures to be taken in connection with the declaration of a state of emergency in the entire territory of Georgia. Available: <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4830372?publication=0> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁵ Law of Georgia on Public Health, Parliament of Georgia, Georgian Legislative Herald 26, 12/07/2007, <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/21784?publication=39> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁶ Law of Georgia on state of emergency, Parliament of Georgia, 44, 11/11/1997 <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/33472?publication=7> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

that the Law of Georgia "On Public Health", the main principle of which is the provision of preventive measures to avoid health-related threats, the clear separation of competencies of state bodies in the field of public health and their close information coordination during the planning and implementation of health-related measures. In accordance with the Article 11 of the Law of Georgia "On Public Health", the decision on the use of isolation and quarantine measures is taken by the Public Health Service. The President of Georgia, when issuing the decree, ignored this provision of the law, because he transferred the authority to establish isolation and quarantine rules to the Government of Georgia. It appeared once again that the national legislation could not respond to the new challenge and the content of the law was regulated differently by decree.

It should be noted that the Constitution, as the supreme law, should clearly assign one or another function to each body of the state, it is also important to take into account the principle of separation of powers, clear separation of powers, supervision and mutual control.

At the same time, a state of emergency was declared in many states, and during a state of emergency, as a rule, the reins of management and decision-making passed more into the hands of the executive authorities. In the process of fighting against the Covid pandemic, human rights restriction measures were mainly written on the basis of orders issued by the executive authorities, government decrees, emergency regulations and other subordinate normative acts. If the state is not characterized by a high degree of democracy, its executive power is more inclined to manage the crisis situation without control. It is this desire, speed and even effective management that may sacrifice a high standard of human rights protection. Special care should be taken when delegating powers to the government by the parliament, as democratic values may be called into question.³⁷

On March 21, 2020, the Government of Georgia sent a notification to the Secretary General of the United Nations Organization in accordance with the Article 4 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, informing that, under the conditions of the declaration of a state of emergency, Georgia restricts the rights of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Articles 9, 12, 17 and the rights and freedoms provided for in the Article 21³⁸. In the message sent to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, the latter noted being concerned with the rights and freedoms stipulated defined with the Articles 5, 8 and 11 of the European Convention, as well as the Articles 1 and 2 of the Protocol 1 of the European Convention and by the Article 2 of the Protocol 4 of the Convention. After Georgia extended the state of emergency for another month, on April 22, 2020, the government additionally notified international organizations that during this period, it maintains the human rights restrictions imposed in the country.³⁹ The state of emergency declared in Georgia on May 22, 2020 was canceled, which should have been the basis for canceling the protection of human rights established by the decree of the President of Georgia under the state of emergency, but this did not happen. On May 22, 2020, the Parliament of Georgia approved the Law of Georgia "On Public Health" with amendments, the amendment to the law allowed the Government of Georgia to implement restrictive measures without a state of emergency. Accordingly, the Government of Georgia

³⁷ Nino Botchorishvili, Ilika Sajaia. 2022. Parliamentary control in the wake of the Covid pandemic (Comparative research) XXIV International Scientific and Practical Conference «Multidisciplinary academic notes. Science research and practice». P.187. <https://books.google.ge/books?id=9GI3EAAAQBAJ&printsec=frontcover#v=onepage&q&f=false> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁸ Notification to the Secretary General of the United Nations, 21 March 2020, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/CN/2020/CN.125.2020-Eng.pdf>, Notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, 23 March 2020, <https://rm.coe.int/16809cff20> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

³⁹ Additional communication to the Secretary-General of the United Nations, 22 April 2020, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/CN/2020/CN.142.2020-Eng.pdf>, Notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, 23 April 2020 <https://rm.coe.int/16809e3a36> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

notified the Secretary General of the United Nations and the Secretary General of the Council of Europe that it maintains the restrictions imposed during the state of emergency, based on the Law on Public Health and the Code of Criminal Procedure.⁴⁰ On July 15, 2020, the Government of Georgia also notified the relevant international organizations that the restrictions stipulated by the international pact and the European Convention will continue to apply until January 1, 2021.⁴¹ With the said notification, Georgia increased the list of rights it restricted in order to deal with the pandemic in the country, and this right was the Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights and the Article 14 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (right to a fair trial). On December 31, 2020, the government also sent a notification to the UN Secretary General stating that the imposed human rights restrictions would remain in effect until July 1, 2021. A similar notification was sent to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe on January 4, 2021.⁴² Georgia sent the last messages to the Secretary General of the United Nations and the Secretary General of the Council of Europe on January 02, 2023, informing them that the human rights restrictions imposed in Georgia due to the Covid pandemic have been terminated from January 01, 2022.⁴³

Conclusion

The analysis of the measures taken in the direction of the management of the Covid pandemic crisis in Georgia and the reports sent to international organizations highlights several problems, on which the following conclusions can be made and several recommendations can be made, namely:

I. It should be noted that during the state of emergency under the Article 71 of the Constitution of Georgia, it is not allowed to limit the right defined by the Article 31 of the Constitution of Georgia, therefore this right was not limited by the decree of the President of Georgia, However, after the cancellation of the state of emergency, during the restriction of the human rights preserved in the country based on the ordinary legislation, Georgia notified the restriction of the right to a fair trial in a notification sent to the UN and the Council of Europe. What needs to be regulated by national legislation, that is, if there is a need to limit the said right in order to protect public health, then the legislation of Georgia should take into account the said norm. The need to restrict the right itself and the notification period are also unclear, since the restriction of the right to a fair trial only affected the restriction established by the criminal law on the remote holding of the court session, which the President of Georgia still prepared with the decree issued on March 21, 2020, therefore it is unclear. Why didn't the government of Georgia notify the UN and the Council of Europe from the beginning that, along with other rights and freedoms, it restricts the rights provided for by the Article 14 of the International Covenant and the Article 6 of the European Convention.

II. Another issue that was highlighted during the research process is also important, namely, the European Convention and the International Pact envisage sending a message from the member

⁴⁰ Additional notification to the Secretary General of the United Nations, 23 May 2020, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/CN/2020/CN.183.2020-Eng.pdf>, Notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, 25 May 2020, <https://rm.coe.int/16809e757c> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

⁴¹ Additional notification to the Secretary General of the United Nations, 15 July 2020, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/CN/2020/CN.314.2020-Eng.pdf>, Notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe 16 July 2020, <https://rm.coe.int/16809efedd> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

⁴² Additional communication to the Secretary-General of the United Nations, 31 December 2020, <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/CN/2020/CN.580.2020-Eng.pdf>, Notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe 4 January 2021, <https://rm.coe.int/1680a0e8a0> (last seen on: 05.07.2023)

⁴³

states about the limitation of the rights protected by the Convention and the Pact, only in emergency situations. Accordingly, after the state of emergency was canceled in Georgia, Georgia had no right to maintain the restrictions on human rights imposed under the state of emergency, and international organizations had to be notified about the termination of the restrictions on human rights. It is a fact that after the cancellation of the state of emergency in Georgia, crisis processes were managed in accordance with the Law of Georgia on Public Health, i.e. with ordinary legislation, at which time the obligation to notify international organizations of restrictions on human rights no longer rests with member states, since the Article 15 of the European Convention and the Article 4 of the International Covenant, It does not establish at all the need to send a notification to the Secretary General of the United Nations and the Secretary General of the Council of Europe, if human rights are protected in an ordinary situation. Accordingly, all messages sent by the Government of Georgia after April 21, 2020 are baseless.

III. In terms of sending a notification to international organizations about the restriction of human rights under the state of emergency, it is worth noting another flaw in the international legislation, which was revealed during the research process, in particular, according to the Article 15 of the Law of Georgia on the State of Emergency “The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Georgia immediately informs the United Nations about the declaration and cancellation of the state of emergency Secretary General of the organization”. While Georgia has also undertaken the obligation to send a notification to the Secretary General of the Council of Europe on the restriction of the rights protected by the Convention during a state of emergency based on the Article 15 of the European Convention on Human Rights, which it does. Accordingly, it is better to specify the Article 15 of the Law of Georgia on the state of emergency and write the Secretary General of the Council of Europe together with the Secretary General of the United Nations.

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Agricultural Sciences

АГРОХИМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЕ ОРОШАЕМОЙ ПАШНИ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МИНЕРАЛЬНЫХ УДОБРЕНИЙ В СУХОСТЕПНОЙ ЗОНЕ ЗАПАДНОГО КАЗАХСТАНА

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Все современные агротехнологии возделывания сельскохозяйственных культур подразумевают высокий агрохимический фон каждого поля с оптимальным содержанием в почве необходимых элементов питания. Агрохимическое обследование почв и наличие агрохимических картограмм в каждом хозяйстве в настоящее время служит теоретической и практической основой эффективного, экономически обоснованного ведения орошаемого степного земледелия.

В связи с этим в июне 2023 года было проведено выборочное агрохимическое картирование территории хозяйства ТОО «Алем Агро Холдинг» (с. Кенсахара), расположенное в умеренно сухой степи Актюбинской области. Обследованный участок состоит из орошаемой пашни и включает шесть полей № 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. Почвенный покров представлен темно-каштановыми почвами, которые по родовому признаку являются карбонатными и солонцеватыми разностями. Представленный материал включает базовый и расширенный набор агрохимических параметров.

Таблица 1 – Содержание гумуса и подвижных элементов питания в пахотном слое

Гумус, %	рНсол	Содержание, мг/кг почвы			
		N-NO ₃	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	SO ₄
Поле 1, площадь 150,14 га, среднее из 33 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,0	7,0	6,0	40,6	457	8,7
низкое	нейтральная	низкое	повышенное	высокое	среднее
Поле 2, площадь 150,1 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
3,4	7,1	5,3	43,8	359	8,0
низкое	сл.щелочная	низкое	повышенное	повышенное	среднее
Поле 3, площадь 200,18 га, среднее из 42 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
2,0	7,1	4,5	53,8	308	5,2
оч.низкое	сл.щелочная	оч.низкое	высокое	повышенное	низкое
Поле 4, площадь 150,16 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
2,1	7,2	13,7	47,9	374	12,6
низкое	сл.щелочная	среднее	высокое	повышенное	высокое
Поле 5, площадь 60,54 га, среднее из 14 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
2,5	7,7	10,0	34,8	265	11,0
низкое	щелочная	низкое	повышенное	среднее	среднее
Поле 6, площадь 150,89 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
2,2	6,9	13,6	30,7	252	11,9
низкое	нейтральная	среднее	повышенное	среднее	среднее

Анализ агрохимических показателей позволяет сделать следующие выводы.

Орошаемые участки хозяйства характеризуются не высокой гумусированностью. На полях № 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 содержание гумуса в пахотном слое оценивается как низкое и составляет 2,1...3,4 %. На участке № 3 его величина опускается до очень низкой степени – 2,0 %. Учитывая, что оптимальное содержание гумуса для темно-каштановых почв Актюбинской области составляет 2,9 % и более, то этому требованию отвечают только два поля № 1 и 2,

соответственно 3,0 и 3,4 %. На других клетках (№ 3, 4, 5 и 6) этот показатель значительно ниже и составляет всего 2,0...2,5 %. Поэтому здесь наблюдается ухудшение всех агротехнологических свойств почвы – распыление структуры, образование почвенной корки, уплотнение, низкая водопроницаемость (фильтрация), испарение влаги, поверхностный сток, образование мелких западин, заполненных водой (вымочек) и др. В результате получаются недружные и не выравненные всходы растений, частые их выпадки, неравномерность созревания, низкая видовая урожайность. Поэтому, часть полей приходится культивировать (перепаживать) и пересевать другими культурами.

Для повышения содержания гумуса на таких полях необходим следующий комплекс агрохимических и агротехнических мероприятий: внесение полуперепревшего навоза, жидких навозных стоков КРС и свиней, птичий помет, соломы с близлежащих полей, минеральных удобрений для увеличения послеуборочных остатков, посев сидератов после ранозубираемых культур,

Реакция почвенной среды (рН_{сол}) на орошаемых участках варьирует от нейтральной рН 6,9...7,0 (поля № 1 и 6) до слабощелочной рН 7,1...7,2 (поля № 2, 3 и 4). Такое значение рН является благоприятным для возделывания многих овощных (капуста, морковь, лук), картофеля, зерновых и силосных культур. Выделяется поле № 5, где реакция почвенного раствора поднимается до щелочного уровня – 7,7 ед. Причиной подщелачивания почвы является ее карбонатность и солонцеватость, а также наличие солонцовых пятен. Однако и в этом случае не требуется проведение каких-то специальных мелиоративных мероприятий. Достаточно будет посева на этом поле устойчивых культур, таких как картофель, зерновые, кукуруза на силос, многолетние травы.

Содержание нитратного азота на орошаемых полях характеризуется некоторыми особенностями. Учитывая, что агрохимическое обследование и отбор почвенных образцов были проведены в середине июня, то часть азота уже была поглощена вегетирующими растениями. Поэтому обеспеченность азотом на поле № 3 очень низкая – 4,5 мг/кг, а на клетках № 1, 2, 5 низкая – 5,3...10,0 мг/кг. На клетках № 4 и 6 она возрастает до средней степени и составляет соответственно 13,7 и 13,6 мг/кг. Очевидно, это связано с припосевным или припосадочным внесением азотных удобрений в небольшой дозе, повышенной нитрификацией орошаемой почвы или слабым развитием растений и низким выносом азота. Однако на всех полях азотные удобрения используются в недостаточном количестве и только при посеве или посадке или не применяются совсем. В связи с этим урожаи культур на этих полях низкие или средние, что свидетельствует о недостаточном использовании потенциала орошаемой пашни. В оставшееся время возможно еще одно-двухкратное внесение азотных удобрений в виде некорневой (листовой) подкормки.

Ситуация с обеспеченностью доступным фосфором на обследованных полях, по сравнению с азотом, более благоприятная. Его содержание на полях № 1, 2, 5 и 6 оценивается как повышенное и составляет 30,7...43,8 мг/кг. На клетках № 3 и 4 количество фосфора достигает уже высокого уровня, соответственно 53,8 и 47,9 мг/кг. Такое накопление в почве обусловлено как за счет внесения повышенных ежегодных доз фосфорных удобрений (в основном аммофос, диаммофос, реже сульфоаммофос) за весь период возделывания орошаемых культур, так и в текущий весенний период. Если взять в качестве примера поле №1, то такое содержание доступного фосфора (40,6 мг/кг) позволяет получить урожай картофеля 50-60 т/га, зеленой массы кукурузы 400-500 ц/га, зерна пшеницы 25-30 ц/га.

Содержание доступного калия на обследованных полях крайне неравномерное и зависит от гранулометрического состава почвы. Так, на полях № 5 и 6 с более легким механическим составом (супесчаные) его количество оценивается как среднее -265 и 252 мг/кг. При переходе к легкосуглинистым разностям (клетки № 2, 3 и 4) величина калия

достигает повышенных значений 308-374 мг/кг. При дальнейшем утяжелении гранулометрического состава (поле № 1) обеспеченность становится высокой – 457 мг/кг. Учитывая, что оптимальное содержание доступного калия для темно-каштановых почв Актюбинской области составляет 410 мг/кг и более, то практически все поля нуждаются в обязательном применении калийных удобрений (калий хлористый, калий серноокислый). Калий должен быть применен как в основное внесение, так и в припосевное (припосадочное).

Содержание подвижной серы также сильно варьирует по полям. Если на участке № 3 ее количество низкое и составляет всего 5,2 мг/кг, то на клетках № 1, 2, 5 и 6 она возрастает в 1,5-2,3 раза и достигает значений 8,0-11,9 мг/кг. Максимальное ее содержание отмечается на поле № 4 – 12,6 мг/кг и оценивается как высокое. Очевидно, здесь применялись серосодержащие удобрения, в частности сульфоаммофос, сульфат аммония или серноокислый калий. Для повышения содержания подвижной серы в орошаемых почвах можно применять перечисленные выше удобрения или сложные удобрения (NPK – нитроаммофоска) в состав которых она входит.

Большое влияние на формирование урожая орошаемых культур оказывает содержание микроэлементов в почве (Таблица 2).

Таблица 2 – Содержание подвижных форм микро- и мезоэлементов в пахотном слое почв, мг/кг почвы

Cu (Медь)	Fe (Железо)	Mg (Магний)	Mn (Марганец)	Mo (Молибден)	Zn (Цинк)
Поле 1, площадь 150,14 га, среднее из 33 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,14	2,07	460	15,5	0,08	0,55
низкое	низкое	оч.высокое	низкое	низкое	низкое
Поле 2, площадь 150,1 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,09	2,06	402	13,3	0,09	0,54
низкое	низкое	высокое	низкое	низкое	низкое
Поле 3, площадь 200,18 га, среднее из 42 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,20	2,21	315	18,6	0,09	0,54
низкое	низкое	высокое	низкое	низкое	низкое
Поле 4, площадь 150,16 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,15	2,29	375	17,5	0,07	0,62
низкое	низкое	высокое	низкое	низкое	низкое
Поле 5, площадь 60,54 га, среднее из 14 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,17	1,83	299	16,9	0,06	0,61
низкое	оч.низкое	повышенное	низкое	низкое	низкое

Поле 6, площадь 150,89 га, среднее из 32 почвенных проб (каждая из 15 точек)					
0,25	3,11	519	18,5	0,07	0,75
низкое	низкое	оч.высокое	низкое	низкое	низкое

Оценка обеспеченности микроэлементами дана для третьей группы культур, возделываемых на орошении с высокой урожайностью и большим их выносом.

Обеспеченность подвижной медью на всех полях оценивается как низкая и ее величина практически одинаковая по различным агрофонам – 0,09...0,25 мг/кг. Поэтому возникает необходимость в применении медьсодержащих удобрений под возделываемые культуры. Лучшие способы использования – предпосадочное или припосевное внесение в почву вместе с другими удобрениями, возможна также некорневая подкормка.

По содержанию железа все поля имеют очень низкую (поле № 5 - 1,83 мг/кг) и низкую (2,06...3,11 мг/кг) степень обеспеченности. При этом количество железа находится ниже критического уровня, установленного международным стандартом. Это связано как с низким содержанием этого элемента в зональных почвах вообще, так и с быстрой окристаллизацией железа и переходом его в недоступное для растений состояние в условиях слабощелочной реакции. В перспективе можно предусмотреть применение железосодержащих удобрений. Их не следует вносить в почву, так как железо быстро переходит в труднодоступную форму. Лучший способ применения – некорневая подкормка.

Количество подвижного магния варьирует от повышенного (299 мг/кг – поле № 5) до высокого (315...402 мг/кг – клетки № 2, 3, 4) и очень высокого (460...519 мг/кг – поля № 1 и 6). Во всех случаях его содержание превышает оптимальный уровень и поэтому на данном этапе потребности во внесении магнийсодержащих удобрений нет.

Содержание доступного марганца на всех орошаемых полях оценивается как низкое и варьирует от 13,3 (поле №2) до 18,5 мг/кг (клетка № 6). Если на богарных землях такое количество марганца для всех культур считается средним и высоким, то на орошаемых участках возникает необходимость в применении марганцевых удобрений. Лучший способ их использования – это некорневая подкормка или припосевное и припосадочное внесение.

Содержание подвижного молибдена выравнено по всем полям и характеризуется как низкое – 0,06...0,09 мг/кг. Данное обстоятельство связано с не высоким присутствием этого элемента в почвообразующих породах темно-каштановых почв Актюбинской области. В связи с этим применение молибденовых удобрений обязательно и лучший способ их использования - некорневая (листовая) подкормка. Возможно также внесение этих удобрений в почву, так как слабощелочная реакция усиливает подвижность данного элемента.

Для доступного цинка характерно низкое содержание на всех полях – 0,54...0,75 мг/кг. Это связано с тем, что при высокой насыщенности поглощающего комплекса темно-каштановых почв кальцием и магнием, слабощелочной реакции почвенного раствора, соединения цинка имеют слабую растворимость и труднодоступны для растений. Цинковые удобрения следует применять только в листовых подкормках. При внесении в почву цинк закрепляется в труднорастворимых соединениях.

На обследованных полях планируемый урожай картофеля, овощных, зерновых и кормовых культур будет ограничиваться недостатком азота, калия и микроэлементов в почве. Высокая эффективность расчётных доз минеральных удобрений будет обеспечена только на фоне правильного режима орошения, комплексной борьбы с засоренностью посевов, болезнями и вредителями орошаемых культур.

ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ЯЧМЕНЮ ЯРОГО ЗАЛЕЖНО ВІД ЕЛЕМЕНТІВ ЖИВЛЕННЯ В УМОВАХ ПІВДЕННОГО СТЕПУ УКРАЇНИ

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У статті розглянуто технологічну схему вирощування ячменю ярого різних сортів (сорт Гермес та сорт Аватар) із застосуванням бактеріального препарату Біокомплекс-БТУ-р для обробки насіння та позакореневого підживлення на фоні внесення комплексного мінерального добрива $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ із застосуванням сидерату (гірчиця біла) та деструктора стерні ЕкоСтерн (2 л/га) в баковій суміші з 50 кг/га карбаміду. У наукових дослідженнях вивчали вплив різного поєднання варіантів на біометричні показники рослин культури, урожайність та його структуру. Максимальними вищезазначені показники були саме при застосуванні обробки насіння бактеріальним препаратом, використанні його в обробці рослин під час вегетації, внесенні комплексних мінеральних добрив, сівбі сидеральної культури з обробкою її деструктором стерні з карбамідом. При цьому врожайність сортів Гермес і Аватар становила 4,84 і 5,13 т/га відповідно.

Ключові слова: ячмінь, біопрепарат, мінеральні добрива, сидерат, деструктор стерні, висота рослин, структура врожаю, урожайність

Вирощування сучасної сільськогосподарської продукції з одночасним підвищенням родючості ґрунтів та забезпеченням посівів добривами і водним режимом є одним з головних завдань в Україні. Необхідно розробляти та впроваджувати нові адаптивні, біологічні та сортові методи вирощування зернових культур, які б максимально використовували біологічний потенціал сорту та місцеві природні умови Південного Степу [1-4]. Підвищення врожайності та поліпшення якості насіння цих культур може бути обґрунтоване лише за умови ретельного аналізу біоорганічних та агротехнічних заходів технології.

Удосконалення існуючих та розробка вітчизняних науково-технічних заходів, нових сортів, штамів мікроорганізмів для обробки насіння, обприскування посівів рїстрегулюючими препаратами мікробного походження у поєднанні із заробкою в ґрунт сидератів та інші фактори є важливими передумовами для вивчення адаптивних сортових технологій вирощування зернових культур. Таке поєднання допоможе продукції ярої

пшениці та ярого ячменю залишатися конкурентоспроможною як на внутрішньому, так і на міжнародному ринках [5-10].

Той факт, що біологічні продукти засновані на мікроорганізмах, виділених з природних біоценозів, не завдають шкоди навколишньому середовищу, безпечні для людей і тварин, є однією з головних причин їх практичного інтересу. Вироблення антибіотичних сполук і поліпшення азотного та фосфорного живлення - це все переваги бактеріальних препаратів на основі азотфіксуючих і фосформобілізуючих мікроорганізмів. Оскільки мікробні препарати не завдають шкоди навколишньому середовищу, мають сильний селекційний ефект, прості у застосуванні та мають нескінченні ресурси для росту, біологічний метод є безпечним для людей і теплокровних тварин [9-14].

У наших дослідженнях вивчали вплив бактеріального препарату Біокомплекс-БТУ-р на обробку насіння та позакореневе підживлення ячменю ярого різного сортового складу на фоні мінеральних добрив та культури сидерату. Ми вивчали вплив бактеріального препарату Біокомплекс-БТУ-р при обробці насіння та позакореновому підживленні ячменю ярого різного сортового складу на фоні мінеральних добрив і сидеральної культури з використанням біодеструктора стерні. Досліди проводили у 2020-2021 рр. на базі дослідного поля Навчально-наукового центру Миколаївського національного аграрного університету. Ґрунти дослідного господарства представлені чорноземом південним малогумусним, слабосолонцюватим, важкосуглинковим на лесі. Ґрунтовий профіль дослідного поля представлений наступним розташуванням горизонтів [10, 15-22].

Найнижча вологоємність шару ґрунту 0-70 см - 22,0%, вологість в'янення - 9,7% від сухої маси ґрунту, щільність ґрунту - 1,40 г/см. Вміст гумусу в орному шарі ґрунту становить 2,9-3,2%, рухомого фосфору - 38%, обмінного калію - 332-525 мг/кг ґрунту. В ґрунті міститься 0,20-0,25% валового азоту та 0,12-0,14% фосфору. Вбирний комплекс ґрунту насичений переважно кальцієм і магнієм. Реакція ґрунтового розчину верхніх горизонтів близька до нейтральної або слаболужної (рН = 6,8-7,2), що підвищується вниз по профілю. За своїми характеристиками ґрунт дослідного поля є типовим для чорнозему південного степу України і придатний для вирощування більшості основних польових культур. Гумусовий горизонт 47-52 см темно-сірий з каштановим відтінком, характеризується засоленістю та вузьким співвідношенням Ca^{2+} і Mg^{2+} (2,5-2,8) [15-22].

Схема досліду з вивчення продуктивності сортів ячменю ярого включала наступні варіанти: Фактор А (удобрення): 1. Без добрив (контроль), 2. $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$, 3. $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерати + деструктор стерні ЕкоСтерн + 50 кг/га карбаміду; Фактор В (передпосівна обробка насіння): 1. Обробка води (контроль), 2. Біокомплекс БТУ-р (1,0 л/т); Фактор С (позакореневе підживлення): 1. Без обробки, 2. Біокомплекс-БТУ-р (0,8 л/га).

Загальна площа облікової ділянки 36 м². Облікова площа ділянки - 25 м². Розміщення варіантів - систематичне.

Агротехніка вирощування ячменю ярого в досліді була загальноприйнятою для зони вирощування. Посіви обробляли біопрепаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р (0,8 л/га) в кінці куштиння разом із внесенням гербіциду Гранстар Про (25 г/га). Обприскування фунгіцидом Абакус (1,6 л/га) проводили в період прапорцевого листка культури.

Попередником ярого ячменю в досліді була озима пшениця з подрібненням післяжнивних рослинних решток 5,0 т/га та мінімальною заробкою в ґрунт на глибину 5-6 см, з наступним посівом гірчиці білої на сидерат (згідно зі схемою досліду) та закладенням зеленого добрива в ґрунт на глибину 20-22 см. Перед оранкою було внесено деструктор стерні ЕкоСтерн у нормі 2,0 л/га з 50 кг карбаміду та з виливом робочої рідини 300 л/га. Ранньовесняний передпосівний обробіток ґрунту під посів культури після ранньовесняного боронування проводили на глибину посіву (5-7 см). Сівбу проводили сівалкою СЗ 3,6 з наступним прикочуванням посіву кільчасто-шпоровим котком ЗККШ-6.

Фенологічні спостереження проводили протягом усього періоду вегетації (згідно з методикою державного сорто випробування сільськогосподарських культур, 2000) [23, 24].

Облік урожаю зерна проводили методом суцільного збирання зернозбиральним комбайном Sampro-300 та зважуванням з кожної ділянки.

Математичну обробку результатів проводили методом дисперсійного аналізу за Б.О. Доспеховим [25].

За результатами наших досліджень, в середньому бактеризація насіння ячменю ярого та обробка посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р з одночасним застосуванням біодеструктора стерні та сидерального добрива позитивно впливала на ріст і розвиток рослин обох сортів ячменю. Обробка насіння мала незначний вплив на густоту рослин на стадії сходів, але суттєво впливала на продуктивне кущіння, або густоту стеблостою.

Через це дослідні варіанти найбільше відрізнялися за густотою стеблостою, яка мала найбільший вплив на інші показники агротехнічної продуктивності.

Висота стебел сорту Гермес залежно від обробки насіння та посівів біопрепаратами, а також удобрення перевищувала контрольні на 3,2-13,7 см, збільшуючись з 64,6 см у контролі до 78,3 см у варіанті обробки насіння та сівби біопрепаратом поліфункціональної дії Біокомплекс-БТУ-р на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерати + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід.

Встановлено, що інокуляція насіння ячменю сорту Гермес мікробними препаратами в середньому за роки досліджень мала незначний вплив на кількість зерен у колосі. Так, на фоні природної родючості ґрунту кількість зерен від обробки насіння збільшилася лише з 20,8 до 21,4 зерен у колосі. В той же час, обприскування посівів бактеріальним препаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р на фоні без добрив формувало 21 шт. зерен в колосі культури.

Максимальну кількість зерен у колосі рослин ячменю ярого сорту Гермес в середньому за 2020-2021 рр. (22,1 шт.) отримано у варіанті вирощування культури за обробки насіння біопрепаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р, внесення $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + Карбамід та позакореневого підживлення посівів бактеріальним препаратом.

Маса 1000 насінин ячменю сорту Гермес від обробки насіння також дещо зростала у варіантах без добрив (з 44,3 г до 45,1 г без обробки посівів і з 44,9 г до 45,8 г - при обприскуванні Біокомплексом-БТУ-р). На фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ та $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ з сидератом цей показник зростав, при обробці насіння препаратом він становив 47,0-47,6 г, а на контролі (обробка водою) - 46,6-47,1 г.

Такий показник як натура зерна у сорту Гермес дещо збільшувався із застосуванням добрив та обробкою насіння і посівів біопрепаратом, коливаючись від 638 г у варіанті без обробки насіння і посівів до 664 г на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + Карбамід з обробкою посівів і насіння препаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р.

Початок фенологічних фаз (від кущіння до молочної стиглості) на ділянках, де вносили добрива, спостерігався на 2-3 дні пізніше, ніж на фоні природної родючості ґрунту. На неудобрених ділянках дозрівання насіння ячменю відбувалося раніше, ніж на неудобрених, де рослини продовжували рости ще на 4-6 днів у сорту Гермес і на 5-8 днів у сорту Аватар (завдяки більшій стійкості останнього до листових хвороб).

Структурний аналіз рослин сорту Аватар показав, що кількість продуктивних стебел, їх висота, коефіцієнт продуктивного кущіння та кількість зерен у колосі значно зростали після обробки насіння досліджуваним препаратом, хоча і не так сильно, як після внесення добрив.

Так, кількість стебел на 1 м² у контрольному варіанті обробки насіння (зволоження водою) коливалася від 360,0 шт. на фоні природної родючості до 435,8 шт. за внесення $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ на сидерат, біодеструктора стерні, карбаміду та обробки насіння і посівів препаратом комплексної дії Біокомплекс-БТУ-р. При застосуванні препарату густота посіву зростала, відповідно до фону, з 396,0 до 435,8 насінин на 1 м².

Залежно від досліджуваного фактору в досліді довжина стебла у сорту Аватар коливалася від 63,8 см у варіанті без обробки бактеріальними препаратами та добривами до 77,8 см за обробки насіння та посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід. Коефіцієнт продуктивного куціння на цих же варіантах відповідно збільшився з 1,50 до 1,76 стебел на рослину, а кількість зерен - з 20,3 до 22,9 у колосі.

На масу 1000 зерен у цього сорту більше впливало удобрення, при обробці насіння бактеріями з Біокомплексу-БТУ-р на фонах з добривом і застосуванням сидератів цей показник збільшився з 47,7 г при обробці водою в контролі до 51,4 г в кращому варіанті. Застосування всього комплексу досліджуваних варіантів дало максимальну масу 1000 зерен (51,4 г).

Маса зерна також зростала при обробці насіння цього сорту Біокомплексом-БТУ-р на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід - до 642-677 г і відносно 642 г на фоні природної родючості.

Основним критерієм оцінки ефективності різних заходів щодо поліпшення умов вирощування ячменю є їх вплив на врожайність. В середньому за роки досліджень передпосівна обробка насіння та обприскування посівів бактеріальними препаратами сортів Гермес і Аватар на фоні застосування сидератів суттєво підвищували врожайність культури. Найвищу врожайність було отримано у варіантах обробки насіння та посівів обох сортів поліфункціональним препаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + 50 кг/га карбаміду, яка становила 4,84 т/га у сорту Гермес та 5,13 т/га у сорту Аватар.

Варіант обробки насіння сорту Гермес Біокомплексом-БТУ-р, залежно від фону удобрення та наявності оброблених ним культур, забезпечив прибавку врожаю зерна порівняно з контролем - 0,19-0,52 т/га або 4,1-15,7%. Водночас, відсоток приросту від обробки насіння бактеріальним препаратом суттєво знижувався на фоні з добривами (6,1-8,9% проти 13,0-15,7% на фоні без добрив), а ще більше - на фоні з добривами та обробкою посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р (приріст на 4,1-5,1% порівняно з фоном без обприскування).

Прибавка врожайності сорту Гермес від застосування добрив у нормі $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ становила 0,57 - 0,73 т/га та 0,88 - 1,13 т/га - на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерати + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід. Ще від 0,47 до 1,04 т/га або 11,5 - 28,8% (залежно від удобрення та обробки насіння) було отримано від обприскування посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р у фазі початку виходу в трубку культури.

Послаблення дії мікробних препаратів за обробки насіння відмічено за рахунок покращення загального агрофону. Так, встановлено, що при обробці насіння сорту Гермес мікробним препаратом відсоток приросту врожаю на фоні без добрив становив (відносно варіанту без обробки насіння) 15,7%, тоді як на фоні добрива $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ - 8,9%, а на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід - 6,1%. При цьому на фоні обробки посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р вплив на врожайність ще більше знижувався. Як припущення можна вказати, що ці біопрепарати діють як стимулятори, які більш ефективні в стресових умовах (зокрема, нестача добрив), ніж за оптимальних умов вирощування культури.

Аналіз даних урожайності сорту Аватар показує, що ефективність обробки насіння цього сорту досліджуваними препаратами на удобреному фоні та при передпосівній обробці ще більше знижується, ніж у сорту Гермес.

Так, найбільший приріст врожайності (12,9%) спостерігався у варіанті обробки насіння Біокомплексом-БТУ-р на фоні без добрив і без обприскування ним посівів. Проте найвища врожайність цього сорту була отримана з ділянок варіанту обробки насіння та сівби Біокомплексом-БТУ-р на фоні удобрення $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерати + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід і становила 5,13 т/га, тоді як у варіанті без добрив та без обробки насіння і посівів біопрепаратами вона становила 3,49 т/га.

За обробки насіння сорту Аватар Біокомплексом-БТУ-р прибавка врожаю зерна, залежно від фону удобрення та наявності обробки посівів, становила 0,21-0,45 т/га або 4,3-12,9% порівняно з контролем.

Внесення добрив у нормі $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ збільшило врожайність на ділянках без передпосівної обробки насіння на 0,72-0,73 т/га або 19,9-22,0%, а на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід - на 1,04-1,13 т/га або 28,8-34,0%. Досить високу врожайність ячменю на фоні природної родючості ґрунту можна пояснити хорошим агрофоном та сприятливими погодними умовами.

Таким чином, в результаті проведених досліджень нами встановлено різну чутливість сортів ячменю ярого Гермес та Аватар до застосування інокуляції насіння та обприскування посівів Біокомплексом-БТУ-р на фоні мінеральних добрив та сидератів. Найвищу врожайність отримано у варіанті обробки насіння та посівів обох сортів поліфункціональним препаратом Біокомплекс-БТУ-р на фоні $N_{45}P_{45}K_{30}$ + сидерат + ЕкоСтерн + карбамід, яка становила 4,84 т/га у сорту Гермес та 5,13 т/га у сорту Аватар. Цей варіант мав найкращі умови для зростання біометричних параметрів та структури врожаю як складової результатів досліджень.

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